

**An Investigation into Change Management at Himalayan Bank
Limited (HBL).**

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**Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the
West of Scotland for the award of Doctor of Business Administration**

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DECLARATION

This thesis is the result of my own investigations
and has not been accepted nor concurrently
submitted in candidature for any other degree.

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February 2021

DEDICATION

This thesis is dedicated with love and respect to my parents,

Ejaz Gill & Lubna Ejaz

and sister

Benish Ejaz Gill

Acknowledgments

I owe my immeasurable thanks to Almighty God, who gave me the potential and ability to complete this thesis.

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Abstract

In developing economies, organisations and financial sectors are undertaking significant technological transformations and re-evaluating their strategies, policies, operations, and culture to withstand competition and sustain market share. However, effectively managing change under the purview of change management is one of the biggest challenges that an organisation faces due to the unpredictability of human involvement. Further, research has discovered that organisational changes induce a certain degree of resistance in employee behaviour, affecting the implementation and smooth running of those new strategies. Thus, managers and change agents are eager to learn how to manage and encourage employees to accept the desired changes. The objectives of this research were to examine the perceptions of organisational change and factors contributing to the resistance to those changes amongst employees working in Himalayan Bank in Nepal. Additionally, shedding light on various strategies established and implemented for smooth execution of new changes.

Change and resistance to change in the banking industry in Nepal is relatively an under-researched topic in the existing literature of change management. Instead, similar studies focus more on performance management systems, career growth and employee turnover, and strategic HRD practices in Nepalese Banks. This research gap convinced the researcher to investigate the paradigms of change management in HBL. In general, it is an exciting and well-timed topic, given the current changes taking place in the Nepalese banking industry and financial institutions.

This study is proceeded by a systemic review of literature that includes numerous factors resulting in organisational change and models such as the 3-step change model by Kurt Lewin (1951) and nine cultural dimensions proposed by house *et al.* (2004). This study is a mixed-method approach using a questionnaire and interviews with senior executives and junior participants of various departments. This empirical study explores respondents' views and

experiences on organisational change management and the challenges/barriers faced in implanting those changes. Furthermore, this research also seeks to understand the strategies administered to minimise the resistance amongst employees. Data were analysed using descriptive statistics for the questionnaire and thematic analysis for the interviews. After, common themes from both sets of data were generated for a detailed discussion. The findings reveal that the employees understand the phenomenon and the importance of organisational change within the Bank. However, resistance is monitored in the Bank when any small- or large-scale change strategies are implemented. Autocratic hierarchical leadership, lack of communication, and involvement are the significant critical sources of resistance. On the other hand, key participants view current change reforms positively, raising the prospects for more effective change strategies to be executed in the Bank, which will be well communicated and encourage employee engagement.

This study contributes to the literature on change management, particularly for Nepal. Adding to that, it bridges the gap between employees' viewpoints on organisational change working in the Himalayan Bank and the empirical literature available on this topic. Previous studies have not endeavoured to assemble the views of employees working in the Nepalese banking industry, especially in the Himalayan Bank limited. Lastly, for the future, this study may assist the management and change agents within HBL in assessing, designing, and evaluating new or existing programs in a way that the general employees readily accept.

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Chapter 1 - Introduction

1.1 Introduction

In today's increasingly technological environment, organisations are continually confronting challenges such as competition, development, mergers, and reengineering of work processes. These forces challenge organisations to re-evaluate their strategies, structure, policies, operations, procedures, and culture. Hence, organisational change is unavoidable in this situation, and it is imperative for organisations to adapt to new changes. However, an unignorable fact is that humans have different individual life experiences, knowledge, social-demographic characteristics, values, and behavioural patterns, which may have a negative impact of uneasiness, stress, and tension when required to learn or relearn new practices. Thus, management and change leaders must be prepared for the unprecedented hesitance of employee's beliefs and behaviours towards organisational change when new techniques are proposed and implemented.

This thesis examines the phenomenon of organisational change and resistance to organisational change amongst employees working at Himalayan Bank Limited (HBL). Given that there is no critical data available on the Nepalese banking industry and the current procedures of managing change within Nepalese Banks, this research is an essential addition to the academic literature available in this field. Therefore, this study is combined with primary data collected from the employees working at various departments in HBL globally. Furthermore, organisational change in itself is the most studied and investigated topics in the literature of business management (Burnes, 2004; De Wit and Meyer, 2005; Luecke, 2003; Nelson, 2003; Senturia et al., 2008; Todnem By, 2005), thus makes it vital to look at it from various factors such as economic, political, environmental and social.

This research will consider the perceptions of Himalayan Bank employees towards change and investigate the trends from the data collected. The literature will be cross compared with the data attained to help monitor any observed gaps and need to be addressed. Despite increasing attention on this topic, research argues that countless organisational change efforts fail. It is anticipated that nearly half of the change programs collide, reach a deadlock, or fails to reach the results that they are expected to (Bennebroek Gravenhorst et al., 1999). There are several reasons for this failure. Some of these factors are cost, workload, legislation, adaptation to new technology, lack of communication, customer changing trends, leadership, social factors, management, and culture (Hoag, Ritschard and Cooper, 2002). Furthermore, these factors may also be related to an individual's psychological and financial predictors (Alvi and Ahmed, 1987; Chang, 1999; Goulet and Singh, 2002). These fluctuations of change being so imperative for survival with higher levels of resistance to change made the researcher more curious about why individuals at work resist change.

In this thesis, the researcher will be investigating the employee-employer relationship and their attitudes towards change and resistance. Moreover, it helps the researcher explore what form of resistance towards change has the Bank faced (in past and present) and resistance factors (if any) that occurred amongst the workforces. Finally, the researcher will further examine senior management and practices implemented to help the employees overcome their resistance and ensure the desired change program is executed smoothly.

1.2 Rationale

A large amount of academic literature on change argues its importance for organisational growth and sustainability. However, this phenomenon is merely associated with resistance. What needs to be understood is that resistance, as envisioned, is not always prejudicial for an organisation. The research argues that although resistance is crucial, it is a little contributor

towards the change failure (Gravenhorst et al., 1999). One of the reasons why the researcher is keen on understanding organisational change and resistance in depth is to debate the importance of change implementation factors within HBL and the extent to which resistance is questioned as a challenge, and how that is being supervised and managed by the leaders. Besides, this research will also align and analyse all the findings with the existing literature.

Alternatively, additional ground for recognizing this topic is the research gap existing between the phenomenon(s) and Nepal's cultural context, where the main branch of the Himalayan Bank is based. After thorough research, the researcher believes that there is a lack of empirical literature that would cover topics like organisational change and resistance within the financial institutions of developing economies. Until now, very little is known about how employees in Himalayan Bank (or other commercial Banks) identify change and the factors that play an essential part in triggering resistance to the desired change strategies. Considering Himalayan Bank as one of Nepal's most prominent financial institutions, it would be rather interesting to examine how the management carries out functions that cater to implementing change and minimizing resistance. This study is different from other research conducted on Nepalese commercial Banks that focus more on the adoption of informational technology, human resource development, career growth, job satisfaction, and employee turnover rather than change and resistance to change (Biswakarma, 2016; Sapkota et al., 2018; K.C. and Neupane, 2020). The existing studies are investigating how commercial banks' performance can be improved to sustain competition in Nepal. In contrast, in this study, the researcher looks at the holistic view of various organisational change practices executed, supported, and managed in HBL. Additionally, this study also reveals and explains employee's perception of those changes. What is more, is that this study is mixed methods instead of the above-mentioned studies that are primarily quantitative in nature.

Another base for embracing this research stems from the researcher's personal admiration and keenness towards this genre in business management research. Previously, the researcher had the opportunity to examine similar organisational behaviour genres in a developing country like Nepal. The findings disclosed interesting aspects that aided in filling the gaps and helped construct a pragmatic viewpoint of that area. Likewise, the researcher feels the need to address the characteristics of change and resistance in Nepal's financial setting. The researcher believes this topic will yield unique, wide-ranging data results that will be interesting in discussing the current literature and the collected data.

1.3 Research Aims, Objectives and Questions

This research aims to explore and examine employee's insights on organisational change and resistance to organisational change in Himalayan Bank Ltd.

Following objectives have been prepared to achieve this aim:

- To identify the nature of organisational change that has occurred at the Bank.
- To gauge the perceptions of change amongst employees.
- To identify factors contributing to resistance to change amongst employees.
- To establish organisational strategies implemented to achieve desired change.

Based on the above, this research seeks to answer the following research questions:

RQ1: What nature of organisational change has occurred at the Bank?

RQ2: What are the perceptions of organisational change amongst employees?

RQ3: What are the factors contributing to resistance to change among employees?

RQ4: What are the organisational strategies implemented to achieve desired change?

1.4 Research Methodology

This study investigates the phenomenon of organisational change and resistance within Himalayan Bank by evaluating the employee's participation and experience in change management and strategies. This research discovered the resistance factors with the help of survey and interview findings, and those were then compared with the literature on this topic. The researcher targeted HBL employees from various departments and seniority levels working in Nepal. This was because a diverse pool of employees was able to express their views from different cultural and personal perspectives on the phenomenon being researched. Furthermore, for the interviews the researcher also targeted employees from the senior management positions who have played a crucial part in imposing desired change procedures and strategies. This was essential to gather their insight as to how the change procedures were applied, who were the key players involved in that process, how was the desired change communicated to the employees and what approaches were helpful in controlling resistance and ensuring the transition was implemented smoothly. These employees are the key players that aid in implementing change strategies for the organisation's improvement. Hence, these personnel's opinions served as an indicator for future prospects in improving approaches to minimize resistance and ensure smooth change processes are implemented.

The research approach and design for this study are guided by the subject area and its aims. To achieve aims such as gauging employee's perceptions on change and factors contributing towards resistance, this research preliminarily embraced two research techniques. At the initial stages of data collecting, a questionnaire was distributed amongst the employees at different departments in HBL. The researcher was expecting a 10% response from the participants, but the overall responses received were 59 participants. This questionnaire comprises a 'Resistance to Change' scale subdivided into four categories: Routine Seeking, Emotional Reaction, Short-

term Focus, and Cognitive Rigidity. This questionnaire's structure follows a 6-point Likert scale stemming from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree).

Secondly, in-depth interviews were carried out with junior-level employees and senior executives from different departments. The researcher opted for interviews because of the medium's ability to probate answers and questions that compel further clarification. The researcher was able to observe and collect behavioural information that would have been restrictive when only using questionnaires, for example, technological jargon. As these interviews will be exploratory in nature, the researcher will focus on a relatively small sample size instead of the questionnaire. A pool of 16 employees will be interviewed, including eight junior and eight senior/middle management. These interviews will be carried out online via MS Teams. The reason for selecting this channel for interviews is predominantly for being cost-effective. It is less time-consuming as most of the interviewees for this research are demographically spread out. Furthermore, MS teams can record the interviews for interview sessions that will help future (analysis) purposes.

This research is a collection of both quantitative and qualitative data. In other words, this research is an amalgamation of quantitative (exploratory) research design with the illustration of a (qualitative) case study. Thus, a mixed-method approach is applied to establish a data set incorporating qualitative and quantitative data to represent employees' perceptions in different ways. Furthermore, mixed-method research is seen as highly relevant for undertaking this study. It complements this research by providing a complete detailed picture of individuals' opinions that can be interpreted in relation to the context. This point will be further elaborated upon in the methodology chapter.

1.5 Country's profile

Nepal is an Asian country that is lying along the southern slopes of the Himalayan Mountains ranges. It is known as the landlocked country located between eastern Indian and Western China, with a population of 22 million (Karan, 2021). The capital of the country is Kathmandu. Years of geographic and self-imposed isolation have made Nepal one of the least developed nations (Karan, 2021). This classification is based on account of a low annual per capita of around USD 210, eleventh from the bottom (Gautam, van Dick and Wagner, 2001).

Demographically, Nepal is the only Hindu nation globally (87% Hindu, 8% Buddhist, 4% Muslim), and more than three-fifths of the Nepalese population is under the age of 30. Furthermore, the primary language spoken in the country is Nepali. The economy is heavily dependent on imports and foreign markets for agricultural products. The imports include fuel, metals, construction material, and the majority of the consumer goods. On the other hand, the exports consist of rice, textile and timber (Karan, 2021)

Nepal's culture is similar to the Indian culture, as identified by Hofstede (1980) in his work. His research identifies individualism, power distance, uncertainty avoidance, and masculinity amongst the four different cultural factors associated with work values (Gautam, van Dick and Wagner, 2001). People from individualistic and collectivistic cultures are likely to hold idiocentric and allocentric beliefs, respectively (Triandis, 1995). Therefore, one may assume low individualism, high power distance, uncertainty avoidance, and femininity in Nepalese working culture.

Unquestionably, the banking sector has experienced massive external pressures both in developing and the established economies because of global economic shifts and crisis, deregulation, and technological advancements (Osei-Bonsu, 2014).

Over the past 20 years, vigorous growth has been monitored within the banking industry of Nepal. This was observed in both business volume, assets, and the market (Chaudhary, 2012).

The government has initiated economic reforms that changed the endeavours of several different sectors of the Nepalese economy, including the banking industry (Chaudhary, 2012).

As per these trends, the world's economy has continued to progress sluggishly. The majority of the developed countries have gained dominance over the world economy, particularly the United States of America, China, India, and European Countries (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018). The countries are finding it hard to maintain growth levels. Therefore, the economic growth globally as a whole has continued to be lethargic (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018). As a result, organisations and institutions are constantly changing, re-shaping, and re-organizing to overcome the existing rigid competition (Munir, Baird and Perera, 2013).

However, during the wave of political uncertainty and the country's transition period, Nepal has maintained encouraging growth levels. National and international events have positively impacted the banking industry. The inflow of remittance has recorded a growth of 8.6 percent to Rs 755.06 billion in the review period. Moreover, this year's money supply also increased by 19.4 percent compared to last year's increment of 15.5 percent (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018).

1.6 Organisation profile of Himalayan Bank Limited (HBL)

Established as a joint venture of Habib Bank Limited of Pakistan in 1993, Himalayan Bank Limited (HBL) has been at the forefront of Nepal's banking industry since its inception. Himalayan Bank gained the reputation of being the first commercial Bank and one of the biggest private banks in Nepal. The Bank's head office is based in Kathmandu that consists of 32 departments. HBL currently has a countrywide network of 68 branches with 939 employees and 111 ATMs providing highly reliable and modern banking services to its customers (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018). The Bank's mission is to become the customer desired provider of quality financial services in the country. The two major components in the bank missions include preferred provider and quality financial services.

According to the 26th Annual Report, the Bank has successfully completed 25 years of service during the fiscal year of 2017-18. During the review, the overall performance of the Bank remained robust hence maintaining a healthy financial position (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018). The Bank is monitored to be progressing effectively with the undoubtful faith of customers, direct and indirect support of the shareholders, and creative initiatives adopted by the management (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018). Ever since the start, the Bank has been rigorously working according to its aims of developing a healthy banking system and extending quality service to its customers (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018). Shedding light on the Bank's operations, the total deposit reached for the year 2017/18 is Rs 99.74 billion. This is an increase of 7.39 percent as compared to the previous year., The net assets of the Bank increased by 14.69 percent, reaching Rs 14.14 billion during the review period. Likewise, the total assets increased by 7.77 percent, reaching Rs 116.46 billion (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018).

According to the new expansion plans, Himalayan Bank has opened 13 new branches in various parts of the country that have reached a total of 55 new branches by the end of 2017/18 (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018). Likewise, different strategies have been adopted to improve the service standards of branches and profit centres (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018). Improvements have also been monitored in the technological departments as the Bank has upgraded the T24 banking software and browser (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018). Likewise, the Bank focuses on further improving its technology by changing and upgrading CBS systems and T24 software for better performance (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018).

1.7 Contribution of the Study

This study aimed to investigate the organisational change in HBL and its employee's viewpoints regarding the new practices. Due to the uniqueness of the phenomenon being investigated in this particular Bank, several contributions emerged from this research.

This is the first study using a mixed-methods approach to gauge the nature and perceptions of employees on change and resistance to change in Himalayan Bank. The relatively few studies that are covering related areas on Nepalese commercial Banks, such as those by Biswakarma (2016), Sapkota et al. (2018), K.C. and Neupane (2020), Upadhaya, Munir and Blount (2014) that either uses a qualitative or a quantitative approach. Additionally, the quantitative element allowed the researcher to obtain a relatively larger sample from employees in various departments and branches of the Bank.

This is the first study to gauge the viewpoints of those currently employed in the Nepalese banking industry as they will be relied upon for the Bank's growth, prosperity, and maintaining a market share. Therefore, the views of junior participants are essential for this study as it allows a projection to be made about what the future might hold in terms of the Bank's development and production and differentiates this study from the other studies that are carried on the Nepalese being industry but not particularly at Himalayan Bank.

This study contributes to embarking on a research topic suitable in Nepal's current and fluctuating corporate environment, which can help the directors and senior management take specific preventive measures when applying changes to minimize any kinds of barriers resistances within the Himalayan Bank. The views from junior employees are particularly appropriate at this juncture. The banking industry is constantly changing. Therefore, there is a need to transform the corporate governance that would guarantee a prosperous future for the Bank and improve the corporate ethos for the overall employees.

1.8 Structure of the Thesis

This thesis will consist of 7 chapters. Chapter 1 will introduce the topic and manoeuvre around the rationale, aims and objectives, and a brief background of the studied organization. Chapter 2 will critically review the empirical literature on the phenomenon of organisational change and resistance. Furthermore, the literature will also be highlighting various theoretical concepts

and models relating to change management and resistance. Chapter 3 will be discussing the methodological approaches embraced for this research. This will include all the philosophical underpinnings, design, and data collection methods applied. Chapter 4 will focus on a survey (questionnaire) and describe the empirical findings accumulated from the primary data collection. Chapter 5 will emphasize interviews and discuss the detailed findings from those in-depth interviews with key participants from various Bank sectors. Chapter 6 will be analysing and examining the results of the questionnaire and interviews in the context of literature and theoretical models discussed in the literature. Lastly, chapter 7 will summarise the study being conducted, including the limitations of this research. This chapter will also highlight recommendations and suggestions for future research and include the main contribution of this thesis to the paradigm of business intelligence.

1.9 Conclusion

The subject of organisational change has been the most studied and researched topics in the previous and recent organisational management studies. However, the lack of empirical data on organisational change in a country like Nepal pushes the researcher's eagerness to explore this phenomenon.

However, due to this research's nature, light is shed on the dynamics of organisational change with resistance to that change. One of the most successful commercial banks existing productively in macho hierarchical culture makes it more exciting and justifies the researcher's enthusiasm to pursue the study of change and resistance in that area. This thesis will employ a mixed-method approach, involving the data collection from both quantitative and qualitative methods and other various sources. The participants for this study are the current-active employees and employers of HBL. The findings that will be discovered and generated will contribute to the gaps and lack of available research on organisational change in a developing

country's banking industry. This will add to the change management studies being conducted in a similar geographical and organisational setting in the future.

This chapter has set the base and topic for this research by presenting an overview of several rationales behind the adoption of this study and the main aims and objectives that will be accomplished. Lastly, the structure of this thesis has also been laid out in this chapter.

1.10 Summary of the Achieved Research Objectives and Questions

The table below mentions the research objectives and questions that have been accomplished to fulfill the study's aims and the data collection methods used to achieve those research objectives and questions.

Research Objectives	How the Objectives are met
1. To identify the nature of organisational change that has occurred at the Bank.	Interviews
2. To gauge the perceptions of change amongst employees.	Survey and Interview
3. To identify factors contributing to resistance to change amongst employees.	Survey and Interview
4. To establish organisational strategies implemented to achieve desired change.	Interview
Research Questions	How the Questions are met
RQ1. What nature of organisational change has occurred at the Bank?	Interview
RQ2. What are the perceptions of organisational change amongst employees?	Survey and Interview
RQ3. What are the factors contributing to resistance to change among employees?	Survey and Interview
RQ4. What are the organisational strategies implemented to achieve desired change?	Interview

Chapter 2 - Cultural Context of Nepal

2.1 Introduction

This chapter presents an overview of Nepal, including the countries' geography, history, political and economic systems, and a brief background on the Nepalese banking sector. Additionally, this chapter will provide a current summary of Himalayan Bank Limited (HBL)

2.2 Nepal

2.2.1 Background

The geography, history, and people of Nepal create a unique environment that impacts banking and many other aspects of commercial life. Nepal is a relatively small and thinly populated country located in South Asia. The Himalayas run the country's length, adding to its remoteness and presenting challenges for government and organisations to embrace a sustainable future of growth and greater prosperity. An appreciation of Nepal's geography, legal, social, 12 ethnic and religious background is an essential precursor to considering the governance of financial institutions of Nepal (World Bank, 2011).

Nepal is a small landlocked country with few natural resources and rugged terrain bounded by two giant, nascent economic superpowers, India, and China. It occupies only 0.03 percent of the total global land area and 0.3 percent of Asia. It has 147,181 square kilometers (56,827 sq. mi) and approximately 27 million in the population (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2012). Kathmandu is the capital city and the country's largest metropolitan city (World Bank, 2011). The government mainly depends on low-productivity, primarily subsistence agriculture, for income and employment (World Bank, 2011). Remittances from abroad have steadily increased over the last 15 years and now represent over 15 percent of gross domestic product

(GDP). Economic growth accelerated in the 1990s following democratization and economic liberalisation (World Bank, 2011).

Nepal is rich in culture, natural beauty, architecture, craft, language, literature, music, dance, festivals and presents a diverse religious spectrum (Dhakal, 2000). The country's population is ethnically and linguistically diverse, with 103 different ethnic and caste subgroups that can be clustered into two main groups, the Tibetan-Nepalese and the Indo-Nepalese (World Bank, 2011). There are four castes and thirty-six different ethnic groups with multiple languages and religions. The religion in Nepal is a system of social coherence based on certain rituals and the binding force that ties all people together (Acharya, 2018). The main religions are Hinduism (81.3%), Buddhism (9.0%), Islam (4.4%), Kirat (3.1%), Christianity (1.4%), and others (0.76%). Although most people in Nepal are Hindu, respect is given to all other religions (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2012).

2.2.2 Geography

Nepal is topographically divided into three geographical regions: The Himalayas to the north, the middle hills, and the Terai to the south. The Himalaya (mountain) region is situated 4,000 meters above sea level. It includes the highest peak in the world, Mount Everest, and another seven of the world's ten highest peaks (Acharya, 2018). Furthermore, the country is divided into five administrative development zones: Eastern Development Region, Central Development Region, Western Development Region, Mid-Western Development Region and Far-Western Development Region. The country is further divided into 75 administrative districts and districts are sub-divided into smaller units (Acharya, 2018).

According to the National Population Census 2011, the total population of the country in reached about 26.5 million with a sex ratio 1.04 male(s)/ female (Acharya, 2018). About one quarter of the population (25.16 per cent) lives below the poverty line according to the Nepal

Living Standards Survey 2010/11, and the Gini-Coefficient, which indicates an inequality in income distribution, is 0.328 (Central Bureau of Statistics, 2012).

2.2.3 Political system

As with other countries, Nepal has gone through rapid political changes in its history. The monarchy system was prevailing in the country until 1990, where the King used to hold the nation's executive power. However, due to the tremendous Communist movement against the King, in 1990, the political system was changed to a parliamentary monarchy where King Birendra was the head of state. The democratic prime minister was the head of government. In April 2006, there was a change in the nation's governance: an interim constitution was promulgated with the King giving up the power. A temporary body and government were formed along with the Maoists (Acharya, 2018). On December 10, 2007, under the leadership of the Maoists, a bill was passed through the interim parliament to make Nepal a federal republic, with the prime minister being the head of state. On April 10, 2008, the first election was conducted for a constitutional assembly. Then again, on May 28, 2008, they declared Nepal to be a republic by eliminating 239 years of the royal monarchy system, and Girija Prasad Koirala became the Prime Minister of Nepal (Acharya, 2018).

According to research, it can be argued that the political instability present since 1990 is likely to have contributed to the World Bank Governance Indicators, which rank Nepal below the fortieth percentile in every category: voice and accountability (33.5), political stability, and the absence of violence (16.2); governmental effectiveness (13.5); regulatory quality (25.0); the rule of law (26.9); and control of corruption (35.6) (World Bank, 2016).

2.2.4 Economy

Nepal is one of the least developed nations of the world, with a per capita income of US\$743.32 per annum and a GDP of US\$ 21.195 Billion (World Bank, February, 2015a). It ranks 144 out of 187 countries in the Human Development Index ranking. The overall inflation of the country

was 10 percent during the FY16 (Konema, 2016). Agriculture accounts for almost 40 percent of gross domestic product (GDP) (the highest share in South Asia) and remains a critical sector (World Bank, 2016). In rural areas, where 85 percent of the population lives, 93 percent of households are engaged in agriculture, accounting for some 60 percent of total household income. Low-productivity subsistence farming is the dominant form of agriculture, and only a tiny proportion of agricultural output reaches the market (World Bank, 2016). However, the commercialization of agriculture has increased in recent years. Exports have also increased, from less than 5 percent of agricultural GDP in the early 1990s to over 35 percent (World Bank, 2016).

Over the period reviewed, macroeconomic policy and outcomes were remarkably stable. Growth was supported throughout most of the period by prudent fiscal and monetary policies consistent with the macro-financial program supported by a three-year International Monetary Fund (IMF) Poverty Reduction and Growth Facility (PRGF) arrangement (November 2003–07). Revenue mobilization improved significantly with government revenue as a ratio of GDP increasing on average by two percentage points over the 2000s (from 9.4 percent of GDP on average in 1985–2001 to 11.6 percent over 2002–07). Public expenditure declined from 17 percent of GDP to 15.5 percent, mainly due to implementation constraints. The fiscal deficit averaged about 4 percent of GDP. It was financed by a combination of very low-cost foreign assistance (about two-thirds of the deficit) and domestic borrowing (about one-third). The deterioration of the trade deficit, led by a decline in the export to GDP ratio, was offset by increased inflows of remittances (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020). Overall, the external current account balance improved from an average deficit of 5.6 percent over 1985–2001 to a surplus of about 2 percent of GDP over 2002–07 (World Bank, 2016).

On the contrary, Preliminary data from the Central Bureau of Statistics indicate that gross domestic product (GDP) is estimated to grow by 2.3% in the fiscal year 2020 (FY2020 ended

July 15, 2020) from 7.0% a year earlier (Figure 1). According to the Asian Development Bank (2020), agriculture, which accounts for about a fourth of GDP, will likely expand by 2.6% in FY2020, down from 5.1% a year earlier due to pest infestation and floods in early July 2019. After growing by 7.7% in FY2019, the industry will only moderately increase by 3.2% a year later (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020). Services, contributing about half of GDP, will probably accelerate by 2.0%, down from 7.3% in FY2019 on a significant slowdown of wholesale and retail trade and contraction of the hotels and restaurants subsector and transport (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020).

Figure 2.1: Supply-side contributions to growth

(Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020)

Average inflation edged up to 6.2% in FY2020, up from 4.6% a year earlier (Figure 2.1). Both food and non-food inflation nudged up with the continued disruption of the supply chain, one weak agriculture yield, and higher prices for Indian imports. Average food inflation accelerated to 8.1%; non-food inflation, however, eased from 5.9% in FY2019 to 4.6% on the back of weak domestic demand (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020).

Figure 2.2: Contribution to headline inflation

(Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020)

The fiscal deficit marginally increased to 5.8% of GDP in FY2020 from 5.6% of GDP a year earlier as total revenue (including grants) slumped by 0.3% and Capital expenditure fell by 20.6% in FY2020 (Figure 2.2). Recurrent expenditure, however, increased by 9.8% in FY2020 as social protection measures ramped up and mobilization of health and security personnel increased (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020).

Figure 2.3: Fiscal balance

(Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020)

Growth in broad money (M2) supply expanded from 15.8% in FY2019 to 18.1% in FY2020 on rising net foreign assets and a modest increase in net domestic assets (Figure 2.3). Credit to the private sector decelerated from 19.1% growth in FY2019 to 12.6% a year later.

Figure 2.4: Monetary sector

(Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020)

Export earnings fell by about 8.0% in FY2020, with a contraction in exports of significant commodities except palm oil, herbs, and ayurvedic medicine. Imports of primary items, namely, petroleum products, transport equipment, vehicle, and pieces of machinery, shrank, narrowing the merchandise trade deficit to 28.2% of GDP in FY2020 from 37.1% of GDP in FY2019. Interestingly, workers' remittances fell by a mere 3.4% in FY2020 despite overseas migrant workers losing jobs and being laid off in this crisis with a substantial decline in the trade deficit amid a sizable remittance inflow, the current account deficit significantly narrowed to -0.9% of GDP in FY2020, down from 7.7% in FY2019 (Figure 2.4). Foreign exchange reserves in the fiscal year improved by 22.6% to \$11.6 billion, providing an import cover for 12.7 months of imports of goods and services (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020).

Figure 2.5: Current account indicators

(Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020)

GDP growth is anticipated to fall to 1.5% in FY2021. Industrial output will diminish due to a manufacturing contraction and a slowdown in construction (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020). Service growth will be significantly lower as international tourism remains closed mainly for the time being (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020). Agriculture growth may rise as paddy yield is expected to increase on the back of a normal monsoon. Nonetheless, delay in

the timely procurement of fertilizers may dampen potential agriculture growth (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020). Inflation in FY2021 is forecast to moderate to an average of 5.5%, down from 6.2% a year earlier, assuming a good harvest, modest oil prices, and subdued non-food prices on weak domestic demand (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020). Delayed economic recovery in advanced economies in 2021 may further dent prospects for employment of Nepali migrant workers, undermining Nepal's external position (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020). Furthermore, non-performing loans in the banking system may pose some risk to financial stability under a prolonged containment period (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020).

2.2.5 Financial/Banking system

The Nepalese financial system consists of banking and non-banking sectors. The banking sector includes the central bank, Nepal Rastra Bank (NRB), and commercial banks. The non-banking sector consists of few cooperatives and non-government organisations undertaking limited banking activities under the regulations and supervision of Nepal Rastra Bank (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020). In the same way, the financial system also comprises non-banking financial institutions such as provident funds, for example, Employee Provident Fund (EPF) and pension fund – Citizen Investment Trust (CIT) operating under Ministry of Finance 24 regulations, the Nepal Stock Exchange Ltd (NEPSE) under the regulatory jurisdiction of Security Exchange Board of Nepal (SEBON), cooperatives under the Department of Cooperatives, and insurance companies under the regulatory jurisdiction of the Insurance Board (Khadka, Nakarmi and Gurung, 2020).

The history of financial institutions in Nepal can be studied under three different phases by different milestones (Maskay & Subedi, 2009). The first phase begins with the initiation of the formal domestic banking system in Nepal up to the establishment of NRB. The establishment of Tejarath Adda in 1880 can be considered the starting point for credit mobilization in Nepal.

It was only after the establishment of NBL that the formal banking system was established in Nepal. The second phase begins with the establishment of NRB continuing until 2002. After its inception, various rules and regulations were developed, and financial liberalization policy was formulated (Acharya, 2018). Three joint venture banks were established during this period – Nepal Arab Bank Limited (later named Nabil Bank Ltd.) in 1984; Nepal Indosuez Bank (later named Nepal Investment Bank) in 1986; and Nepal Grindlays Bank (now Standard Chartered Bank Nepal) in 1987. During this period, significant policies were changed, such as the shift from controlled to deregulated framework of interest rates; emphasis on open market operations as the primary policy tool; direct to indirect methods of monetary control; permitting a market-determined exchange rate of the Nepalese currency against convertible currencies; and full convertibility of the 26 Nepalese currency in the current account (Acharya, 2018). During this period, three different institutions were established by the Government of Nepal. The first was Nepal Industrial Development Corporation (NIDC in 1959, with the objectives of mobilizing capital to the industrial sector and facilitating industrial development in the private sector); the second was Rastriya Banijya Bank (RBB in 1966 to provide banking services throughout Nepal and contribute to the socio-economic development of the country); and the third was Agriculture Development Bank, Nepal (in 1968 to provide banking services throughout Nepal and contribute to the socio-economic development of the country).

The third phase begins with NRB Act 2002 (later amended in 2006) replacing NRB Act 1955. This act provides more autonomy for central banks to formulate various monetary and foreign exchange policies and monitor, regulate, and control Nepal's banks and financial institutions. Later, the Bank and Financial Institution Act (Bank and Financial Institution Act), 2006, was established by classifying all the banks and financial institutions into four categories based on their responsibilities (Acharya, 2018). The four categories are commercial banks (group A),

development banks (group B), finance companies (group C), and microcredit development banks 27 (group D) (Acharya, 2018).

In mid-January 2017, there were 169 banks and financial institutions: 28 commercial banks under Group A; 57 development banks under Group B; 36 finance companies under Group C; and 48 microcredit development banks under Group D. There were 15 savings and credit cooperatives and 25 NGOs, both being allowed by NRB for undertaking limited banking transactions, 26 insurance companies (Insurance Board Nepal, 2016) and one employee provident fund, one citizen investment trust and one postal saving bank. (Nepal Rastra Bank, 2017).

2.3 Himalayan Bank Limited (HBL)

Established as a joint venture of Habib Bank limited of Pakistan in 1993, Himalayan Bank Limited (HBL) has been at the forefront of Nepal's banking industry since its inception (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2020). Starting banking services from the employees' provident funds building at Thamel, Kathmandu, HBL currently has a countrywide network of 68 branches and 138 ATMs to provide highly reliable modern banking services to its customers across Nepal (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2020).

Himalayan Bank holds a vision to become the leading Bank of the country by providing premium products and services to their customers, thus ensuring attractive and substantial returns to the stakeholders of the Bank. Likewise, the Bank provides a clear mission to become the best quality provider for the financial services in the country. HBL's mission is based on two components: preferred provider and quality financial services. Hence the Bank believes in satisfying these two components with the customer's focus (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2020).

2.3.1 Review of the Bank's Operations

During the review period, the Bank's total deposits reached Rs. 131.86 billion, an increase of 16.60 percent compared to the previous year (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2020). Similarly, the loans and advances reached Rs. 107.29 billion during the review period, while the total assets increased by 17.07 percent and reaching Rs. 155.88 billion (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2020). Following the guideline of the regulatory body, Nepal Rastra Bank and institute of chartered Accountants of Nepal, the Bank was able to post an operating profit of NPR 3.41 billion during the fiscal year, with a net profit at NPR 2.59 billion (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2020).

HBL holds a good history in the banking industry in Nepal. The first Bank to introduce telebanking services and the CBS system in the country (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2020). Today it has Rs. 155.89 billion of asset size, Rs. 131.86 of deposits and Rs. 107.29 billion of loan investments with a total of 629,648 customers (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2020). These figures have allowed the Bank to secure a prominent position in the Nepalese Banking industry. As per the HBL's annual report of 2020, the Bank has maintained to provide the best and most innovative products to their customers, both in deposits and loan schemes. For the past two years, HBL has concentrated on upgrading its mobile banking application and internet banking services, prioritizing its customer's safety and convenience (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2020). Additionally, since its commencement, the Bank has been discharging its corporate social responsibilities through various social and allied institutions. The Bank, in the review period, has focused on its CSR activities in the field related to education, orphanage, healthcare, sports, culture, nursing homes, preservation of cultural heritage, and rehabilitation of victims of natural calamities and social services (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2020).

For the coming years as well, the Bank is active in the development of sports and culture. The Bank is fully aware of its corporate social responsibilities towards the community/nation and committed to continuing its CSR initiative in the coming days. Furthermore, HBL firmly

adheres to regulatory compliance by incorporating efficient policies, practices, and proper corporate governance to manage the growth and development of the Bank and also meet stakeholders' aspirations.

As mentioned in the earlier chapter, the current setting of the financial banking systems, particularly Himalayan Bank Nepal, was considered the leading choice for the researcher to conduct this study because of the Bank's rigorous transformations over the years, especially in technology and digitalisation. Their key focus has been providing the best quality services to their customers as well as withstand competition. Furthermore, due to the previous research conducted in the same organisational setting, the researcher had relatively more accessibility to this Bank than other organisations. The fondness for examining HBL is inclined from the researcher's personal interest in analyzing a Nepalese Bank due to her familiarity with this current Bank and the Nepalese culture. Lastly, the researcher was also keen to shed light on the organisation providing top-quality services, maintaining its profits, and successfully competing with global competitors. As previously, no research is conducted in Himalayan Bank Limited.

2.4 Conclusion

This chapter provides the background about Nepal from a broader perspective covering its geography, history, economic and political systems, and providing a context of the Himalayan Bank Limited (HBL), where the primary research for this study is conducted. A strong and resilient banking system is a significant prerequisite for a nation's financial stability and economic progress. The banking sector has become an indispensable part of the functioning of the entire industry, and its stability is crucial to the health of the whole. Furthermore, the banking sector also seems to have made a significant contribution to the development and expansion of Nepal's economy (Poudel, 2005). Financial indicators and the overall condition of the sector have remained satisfactory during the last decade and plan to do the same for the

coming fiscal year. The banking industry now needs to coordinate across business functions, employee health, lending portfolio, and recovery. It must focus on reviving all services with robust internal and external communication strategies and a recovery plan. Therefore, to ensure the smooth operation of the banking sector and handle the future crisis, adequate, timely measures and actions should be taken by the government and the central bank.

Chapter 3 - Review of Literature on Organisational Change and Resistance

3.1 Introduction

According to Hart (1998), a literature review is known as "the use of ideas in the literature to justify the particular approach to the topic, the selection of methods, and demonstration that a research contributes something new" (p. 1). In other words, A literature review is considered as a collection of summaries of paper or a detailed bibliography of multiple research manuscripts (Webster & Watson, 2002). It is further argued that a useful literature review helps create a foundation for advanced knowledge, facilitates theory development, and helps a researcher uncover areas where research is needed (Webster & Watson, 2002). Before conducting a literature review, one must first understand the place of the research review (Webster & Watson, 2002). Thus, two questions must be answered: What is research? Why is a literature review needed for any quality research endeavour?

One of the critical reasons for conducting the literature review is to allow the researchers to determine what is already known. However, it is essential to remember that not everything reported in the literature is in equal rigor (Ngai & Wat, 2002). Likewise, quality literature stimulates additional research studies, thus providing validation of the original theory proposed (Barnes, 2005). Building a theoretical foundation based on quality resources enables researchers to explain better and understand problems and solutions that address actual issues which practitioners are struggling (Levy and J. Ellis, 2006).

This chapter will discuss different aspects of organisational change, supporting the research aims of measuring organisational change perceptions and identifying factors causing resistance to change amongst the employees. The first part will discuss the concept of organisational change and why it is essential. Next, the chapter will discuss various types of organisational

changes such as planned, emergent, radical, transformational, technological, and incremental, as well as change models such as Lewin's 3-stage model of change, GLOBE studies and cross-cultural dimensions. Each will be discussed and reviewed individually. Further in the chapter, resistance to change and factors causing resistance to change will be examined. The various aspects that stem from resistance to change, such as dispositional resistance to change, RTC scale, and culture, will also be discussed. The last part of this chapter will be focused on highlighting the strategies that can be implemented to execute the changes successfully with minimum resistance.

As mentioned above, the literature review will highlight the necessity of this research to explore further organisational change and resistance from the employee's perspective within organisations.

3.2 Organisational Change

The pace of the current business environment is changing rapidly. Globalization, the desired and required technological advancement, repeated occurrence of economic turbulences, and the competitive business pressures have made it compulsory for change not just to be incorporated as a significant factor of corporate life but have compelled the organisations and other business associations in delivering high-speed change, profoundly than ever before (Dobson, 2001). According to De Jager (2005), change through the following terms it occurs whenever we replace the old with the new. It is about traveling from the old to the new, leaving yesterday behind in exchange for a new tomorrow. According to Rieley and Clarkson (2001), organisational change is an integral part of organisational strategy, while Burnes (2004) argues that it is a universal and dominant feature of organisational life. For many organisations, change comes like a hurricane season. Everyone knows it is coming. It is the same every year. The only thing individuals are not aware of is "whom will it hit this time?". To other organisations, change comes like an earthquake. Organisations may never foresee it coming but have this

nagging feeling that it is (Thames and Webster 2009:12). Organisational change is a concept of great importance that has attracted researchers' interest for many years. Without a doubt, it is crucial for enhancing and improving organisational effectiveness and ensuring organisational growth (Cummings and Worley, 2014).

The rise in technological advancements and customer demands is increasing the pressure on organisations to change. Whatever it is, organisations must prepare in advance for the shift and not react when the environmental jolt is experienced (Rieley and Clarkson, 2001). Oppositely, some authors debate that organisational change is adopted merely to gain competitive advantage, but it is a means for survival (Kotter, 2012). Furthermore, it is argued that change cannot be considered a desired task, activity, or process, but the organisational innovatory requirement that befalls within its own time, step by step rather than entirely at once (Wilson, 1992). However, it must be kept in mind that this phenomenon's philosophical interpretations vary according to the various organisational situations. Suffice to say, the word "change" is characterized as multidimensional with multiple meanings because it refers to and is synonymous with concepts such as "transformation, development, metamorphosis, transmutation, evolution, regeneration, innovation, revolution and transition" (Stickland, 2002). Change is, therefore, one of those processes that benefit from some careful thoughts and deliberate planning (Honey, 1988).

Considerable research on change indicates that it is fundamental for influential organisations and co-operations to undergo moderate and significant changes at least once every four-five year, respectively (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008). The requisites for gaining a competitive advantage and increasing organisational performance induces the organisations and their leaders to undergo continuous change (By, 2005). Although, as per the contextual basis, many academics underline the importance of adopting efficient change strategies to improve organisational functioning in today's competitive environment. However, many change

agents/leaders cannot do so. Due to this, the changes that are desired face resistance. Balogun and Hope-Hailey (2004) reported that more than 70 percent of the organisational change programs fail due to a lack of research and consideration before executing changes.

On the other hand, some studies also show that few organisations' change efforts are inclined towards failure, whereas some tend to succeed (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008). Change agents must help resolve objections to change and encourage alignment (Stjernholm and John, 2005). Thus, change can be seen as an essential element for development and success that requires careful and well thought planning to bring about positive outcomes and smooth progressions.

3.3 External environment and organisational change

The adoption of this area for this literature is mostly dependent upon the observation that maintaining the organisation and its process, to an extent, depends upon the degree of exchange with the external and/or outside parties (Child, 2005). This observation was advanced by Sadler and Barry (1970), who argue that, for an organisation to progress in ways that indicates their goals, needs or motives is rather challenging as it has to bend towards the constraints that are compulsorily imposed by the relationship of the organisation with the external environment (Child, 2005). As supported by Manuela and Clara (2003), the main aim of organisational change is adaptation to environmental changes to improve performance. This view that organisations operating within the constraints of a multi-dimensional environment has various supporters, such as the work by Peter Checkland (1972), the development of soft system model, Nadler (1988) generation of a systems model for organisational behavior, and Stacy (2003) initiated the usage of systems concept in the discussion of organisational change (Senior and Swailes, 2010). Similarly, Brooks (2004) stresses that environment is a universal concept incorporating all the external forces that can affect the organisational activity (Senior and Swailes, 2010). Many scholars have further stressed that to sustain organisational growth, the environment where change occurs has to be recognized (Eales-White, 1996).

Studies also argue that initiative for change in the organisation arises from opportunities and problems existing in the internal or external environment (Robbins and Barnwell, 2006). To overcome the crisis and understand the nature of organisational change, it is vital to understand an organisations environment and ensure that the change is identified before applying solutions implemented in the past. The PESTEL analysis (Figure 3.1) is the most common approach that acknowledges the external business environment. It considers all the diverse groups of the external factors affecting the organisational activity.

Figure 3.1: PESTEL factors and organisational change

(Scanning the Environment: PESTEL Analysis, 2016)

An organization’s ability to compete and respond successfully to changes in the external environment ultimately determines the organisations success or failure (Tahir, 2019). Organisations have their own culture and their ability to respond to changes in the external environment is a characteristic of that culture. The internal factors determine how the organisation moves forward, both as a self-contained organisational entity and in response to its external environment (Tahir, 2019). According to Senior (2002) changes in technology, HR policies such as overtime work, pay, power reallocation and transfers, changes in

administrative structures and any changes in the internal design in terms of a group or an individual are the key internal factors that force organisational change. On the other hand, External factors affecting an organisation change are political, economic, social, technological, legal and environmental factors. Political factors are the extent to which policymakers intervene in the commercial environment of an organisation. Political factors often impose costs upon organisations, such as taxes. The governments are often trying to protect firms in their countries from foreign competition through tariffs and import restrictions and encourage their development through cheap loans and large government contracts (Tan et al., 2012). Likewise, commercial restrictions and political stability are also imperative factors that could determine the success or failure of a business (Sammut-Bonnici and Galea, 2015). Economic factors have the most apparent impact on the profitability and overall attractiveness of a market or industry (Sammut-Bonnici and Galea, 2015). Factors include local, national, and world economic impact. Rates of economic growth, unemployment, and interest rates will affect consumer's and businesses' spending power, which impacts the nature of competition in an industry (Tan et al., 2012). Social factors dictate work patterns and attitudes, consumer tastes and preferences, and the type, form, and volume of demand for a product or service. The monitoring of social trends enables an organisation to reposition its products or services to fit the changing expectations of customers (Sammut-Bonnici and Galea, 2015). The other social factor is cultural aspects, health and safety consciousness, population growth rate, age distribution (Tan et al., 2012). The rapid pace of technological change is driven through innovation, which is created through entrepreneurs who seek to push the boundaries of present limitations. With the emergence of globalization and technological advancements, old technology becomes obsolete, and any competitive advantage is short-lived. Technological breakthroughs can either spell the demise of some industries/ organisations or create opportunities for new ones (Sammut-Bonnici and Galea, 2015). The technological factors

include the maturity of technology, competing for technological developments, research funding, technology legislation, and discoveries (Tan et al., 2012). Organisations must be aware of what is and what is not legal to trade successfully. Legal factors include how local, national, and global legislation affects the organisations. Organisations must adjust their products and operations to the regulatory and legislative frameworks that govern their productivity and operating countries (Tan et al., 2012). Environmental factors include local, national, and global environmental issues. The general environmental problem such as global warming and pollution is the environmental factor in PESTEL analysis. The concern on global warming has resulted in a global agreement on emissions of greenhouse gasses. Additionally, many organisations are getting more involved in practices such as corporate social responsibility (CSR) and sustainability because of the growing awareness of the potential impacts of climate change on societies and individuals (Tan et al., 2012).

3.4 Types of organisational change

In this current turbulent and frequently changing business environment, one can take a look at Lewin's revolutionary theories on change with higher gratitude, especially with the available evidence of high failure in implementing change programs (Burnes, 2004). Most of the contemporary organizational change theories are deep-rooted within the early work by the social psychologist Kurt Lewin (1951), who developed a 3-step classic model based on field theory, group dynamics, and action research to observe organisational change (Liebhart and Garcia-Lorenzo, 2010). The planned change or the planned approaches to change are constructed on the ideology of corporate planning. This process includes the systemic creation of long-term strategies that helps the organisation in achieving its objectives. These include the restructuring and remodeling of the desired organisational elements (Holbeche, 2006). In an organisation where there is a wish for creating an environment that qualifies all the employees

to reach their full potential, a planned change or organisational practices is necessary to reach the desired outcome (Thomas, 1991). Planned change is essential when understanding the origin of change; as explained by Benn, Dunphy and Griffiths (2014), planned change strategies are predicted; thus, their direction, implementation, and analysis of such changes are pre-defined. Ven Poole (1995) argued that planned changes are intentional actions taken after conscious reasoning to ensure the organisation meets the demands of its internal and external environment. Described simply in Senior and Swailes (2010), planned change is whereby the agent authorizing the change takes required deliberate actions to move the organisational productivity from one state to another.

Likewise, as stated above, the planned models maneuvered around strategies enhancing and altering organisational and employee behaviour (Burns, 2005). Shedding light back to Lewin, also known as the father of planned change studies, created a three-stage model with the basic assumption to balance the environmental forces calling for change. This model's first stage is unfreezing, where the desired change needs to be identified and implemented. Similarly, at this stage, the unhelpful behaviour within the organisation needs to be precise and discontinued. The next stage is the freeze stage, the implementation of change, or moving towards the change. With the help of research and trial-error basic, the required alterations are implemented. Lastly, the refreeze stage begins. At this stage, it has to be ensured that the new change is embedded within the organisational processes and values to be learned, adapted, and maintained in the future (Liebhart and Garcia-Lorenzo, 2010). However, it has to be kept in mind that the new behaviour must be aligned with the employees' behaviours, personality, and working environment involved for this model to be successful (Schein, 2004). It was further emphasized by Esain et al. (2008:21) and Nicholson (2000), arguing that swift changes occurring today make it impossible to line up new behaviour with the environmental demands before the change.

Although planned approaches to organisational change are applied and favoured by many researchers, that does not keep this theory free from criticism. Wilson (1992) criticizes this idea of change that it can be planned and managed logically. Planned change relies on a single view of change and assumes that the environment can be controlled when planning any change (Senior and Swailes, 2010). However, this in the construction of reality is unfeasible. Wilson (1992) further disapproves by arguing that this view fails to consider the context in which the change has to occur, for example, political and cultural components influencing the implementation of planned change (Senior and Swailes, 2010). Correspondingly, some authors disapproved of this approach for ignoring the environmental factors as the inconsistent with the initiates of planned change (Livne-Tarandach and Bartunek, 2009). Changing organisational productivity from one state to another is not as easy as it sounds. Garvin (1994) stated that it is relatively trickier for change to be implemented from one state to another (Bamford and Forrester, 2003). These criticisms of planned theories of change are not baseless. Failure rates were measured and were high, up to 70 percent (Sackmann et al., 2009). Weick (2000) puts forward that planned change gained much appreciation in the decision-makers' eyes as it delivered new strategies for survival. However, it rarely can change organisational nature, and the problems would persist (Liebhart and Garcia-Lorenzo, 2010).

While planned change forces are known to diminish the deterring environmental factors, emergent change focuses on recognising the factors and improving them to maintain equilibrium. Unlike planned change, emergent change is categorised as unintentional, unpredictable, and can ascend from anywhere, internal, or external (Weick and Quinn, 1999). Stacy (2005) emphasizes that current organisations function at the edge of chaos together with stability and instability. Therefore, organisations must learn to operate within any situation (Liebhart and Garcia-Lorenzo, 2010). Burns (2006) highlights that emergent change nurtures ongoing learning, strategy management, and realignment with the environment (Burns, 2006).

Similarly, emergent theories on change emphasize the study of the process rather than discrete events or organizing (Hosking and Morley, 1992). Some of the theories developed under this approach are Hinings and Greenwood's (1988) change dynamic model, Pettigrew's (1985) Process/Content/Context model, and Kanter et al. (1992) Big Three model on organisational change (Bamford and Forrester, 2003). In practice, it was observed that planned changes often produce unintended relations that lead to non-linear emergent change (Beer and Nohria, 2000). This observation was further recommended by Burns (2005), who claimed that leaders within an organisation should not solely consider implementing planned organisation change, nor should they solely react towards the emergent change approach. Instead, both approaches should be merged to create change interactions (Liebhart and Garcia-Lorenzo, 2010).

Just like the planned change, this approach also attracted criticism. It was argued, emergent change theories and models tend to be more associated with the disbelief towards the planned change models than to be an agreed alternative (Bamford & Forrester, 2003; Dawson, 1994). Although there is a vast literature on the nature and forces of emergent change (Seel, 2006), what lacks is empirical evidence on how the emergent change progresses overtime (Livne-Tarandach and Bartunek, 2009). Beer and Nohria (2000) noted that while organisations adopt the emergent approach to change, they transition through periods of rapid planned change that are not fully absorbed by the emergent change model (Livne-Tarandach and Bartunek, 2009). As mentioned above, adopting these two change approaches individually is a conflict within its own. Therefore, it is crucial to consider both the planned and emergent ways of forming organisational change if the change is understood adequately (Livne-Tarandach and Bartunek, 2009).

To understand the intensiveness of change, strategies are divided into incremental and radical changes (Burnes, 1992; Goodstein and Warner, 1997; Wang, 2012). Bessant and Caffry (1997) were among the key pioneers and carried out substantial literature on an incremental

and radical change in organisational development (McAdam, 2003). As per their findings, continuous or incremental can either be small, but their primary purpose is to improve the overall business function (Samuel, 2011). That is why most organisations implement incremental change strategies in their initial stages of change (McAdam, 2003). Similarly, Badarch (2014) argues that incremental change is based on routine and continuous modifications, which are imperative for the business to adapt to withstand the business environment.

On the other hand, Burnes (2004) further distinguished between incremental and continuous change and stated that continuous change allows the business to continually change to adjust to the rapid and fast-changing rhythm of change, such as transforming technology and structure. In contrast to incremental change, where the existing established processes and organisational structures are extended and improved, radical change is prone to replace the status quo with new structures, processes, and operations that can cause severe disruption (Gallivan, Hofman and Orlikowski, 1994). Furthermore, it can be argued that radical change is a change across all the organisational parameters (McAdam, 2003).

While some researchers solely debate on the change itself, others focus on the specific nature of change. With that discussion, these incremental and rapid approaches to change are not free from disparagements. Kanter (1983) argues on adopting rapid change rather than incremental change because the slow implementation of change leads to resistance to change from the employees (Kanter, 1985). Likewise, Rogers (1983) noted that rapid change often leads to disastrous results (Gallivan, Hofman and Orlikowski, 1994). On the other hand, other researchers argue that incremental change is relatively more effective within an organisation in general (Gallivan, Hofman and Orlikowski, 1994). Even though there are conflicts in the literature amid the fast or slow pace of change, what remains significant is the existing gap by

the researchers of not being able to specify and recommend the nature of change (Gallivan, Hofman and Orlikowski, 1994).

Further strengthening the argument for change models that go beyond the concepts of status and equilibrium, Chia (1999) discusses organisational change frameworks that take into account the "movement" of change, stating that hierarchies, typologies, and taxonomies that seek to classify change are simplistic and miss the "intrinsically changing, fluxing and transforming social reality" (p.210). Chia argues for a consistent change model, stating that earlier change models describing temporal and processual aspects of change are not sufficiently 'process-based' to capture the dynamics of change (p. 209) adequately. Viewing change through a metaphysical lens is interesting but presents many problems when understanding variables that identify continuous or constant change (Weick and Quinn 1999). Shedding light at only those easily identifiable variables, such as those mandated by managers, to correct a perceived shortcoming or reach a specific goal. However, these changes may point to changes within the organisational structure but are generally representative of episodic change, not continuous change (Walker, Achilles, and Bernerth 2007). Such a concise approach could lead one to miss the subtle and nuanced changes that go on within the organisation's interior but never quite reach the status of formally recognized change (Tsoukas and Chia 2002).

The concept of organisational change is comprehensive; consequently, researchers have looked at it from various perspectives. For example, some researchers have identified the need for change, the human behaviour and attributes associated with change, and studying the precipitating factors and the interpretive processes involved (Aninkan, 2018). One inquiry method would be to view change from a "micro-process" level, that is, to examine organisational change not from a top-down view but from personal and individual analysis of the everyday workings for those who are affecting the change within the organisation. This echoes the premise put forth by Oilikowski (1996), who sees organisational change as a process

that is not organised from the top. Instead, it is grounded in the ongoing practices of organisational actors and the emerging accommodations to and experiments with the everyday contingencies, breakdowns, exceptions, opportunities, and unintended consequences that they encounter (p. 65). It can be established here that the metamorphic process of continuous change relies on the actions of the individuals who initiate and champion change. Studying change from an individual perspective provides a conceptual lens from which organisational change can be analysed. Indeed, change can occur separately or concurrently and at many levels, including individual, managerial, or cultural (Buchanan et al. 2005). Correspondingly, research also suggests that supervisors and non-supervisory staff have different attitudes toward and perceptions about organisational change, arising from their disparate experiences of the change process, which reflect differences in power, autonomy, and influence (Armstrong-Stassen, 2005). Individual-level changes, such as changes in behaviour and attitudes, of individuals must be altered to their day-to-day activities and beliefs in order for changes to become sustainable (Buchanan et al. 2005; Danter et al. 2000; Fernandez and Rainey 2006; Tsoukas and Chia 2002;).

To understand the timings and the extent of change, the light will be shed on transformational change. This type of change is emphasized in countless pieces of literature on organisational change due to its popularity and importance in big organisations. The shift from different types of planned, incremental, continuous, and radical to transformational changes is based on several assumptions about the depth, scope, and speed of change (Vermaak, 2013). Transformational change is often associated with in-depth change (fundamental, genuinely new, revolutionary), large scale (the whole system), or quick (achieved in a relatively short amount of time). Transformational change is corporation-wide and characterized by radical shifts in business strategy, reorganization of systems and structures, and changes in power distribution across the organization (Balogun and Hope Hailey, 2008). The role of leadership

is of high importance and critical for successful change in transformational change because it must engage and include all members of the organisation (Amis et al., 2004; Kezar and Eckel, 2002; Newhouse and Chapman, 1996; Pettigrew, 1987). Research on transformational change by Kezar and Eckel (2002) underlined that senior administrative support, cooperative leadership, vision, and design are all strategies essential for transformational change. Pettigrew (1985, 1987) highlights that leadership is only one ingredient of change that must be balanced with the context, content, and the need for change in order for the organisation to fully understand a transformation (Pettigrew, 1987).

On the other hand, this type of radical shift can bring about job loss, reduced status, threats to self-esteem (Nadler, 1982). Additionally, Employee's report feeling confused and anxious about the nature of such changes (Kanter, 1983). There can be a loss of many work and environment features, including power, rank, and a sense of mastery (Callan, 1993). Furthermore, it is argued that transformations are difficult to affect, the outcome is difficult to predict, and there has to be a good reason for undertaking them (Balogun et al., 2016). This type of change involves all members of the organisation and must be planned and driven with close consideration of multiple perspectives (Amis et al., 2004; Kezar and Eckel, 2002; Pettigrew, 1985).

3.4.1 Technological change

Technological change has become an increasingly important topic over the past 20 years because technological innovation is vital and significant for any organization's survival (Eveleens, 2010). That compels the researcher to fully understand technological changes and innovations to comprehend the various aspects and nature of organisational change. The term technological change refers to the overall process of invention, innovation, and diffusion of technology or processes (Jaffee et al., 2002). Therefore, there has been intense interest in technological change processes such as technology innovation, diffusion, adaptation,

implementation, and use of connecting technology and development (Heeks and Stanforth, 2015). According to Mark (1987), new technology has become vital in all sectors to reduce cost and compete with the national and internal markets. Johnstone and Michel (2008) believe that technology change is a crucial initiator that allows people to be innovative and efficient. According to Peter (2011), adopting new technologies with new strategies and approaches enable a business to produce effective outcomes. Although, the rate of change differs amongst organisations in terms of production and performance. Furthermore, Metha (2006) highlights that technological change can also lead to job satisfaction, stress, working conditions, operational efficiency, and productivity. Nevertheless, these fears can be mitigated by imparting training to the employees in different phases and at different levels.

In line with Malecki's (2009) research, one of the factors that drive technological change in an organisation is corporate evolution. This is due to the external market implications that compel organisations to change their policies according to their culture, values, and objectives. Alternatively, Peters and Watermann (2004) argue that globalization is one of the critical factors affecting technology. In order to survive and withstand the competitors, organisations need to undergo technological changes frequently. On the other hand, Chapman (2002) emphasizes the fast-paced, changing nature of technology. Technology is continuously innovating, allowing organisations to perform faster, better, and cheaper (Chapman, 2002). Research on the technological change also underlines that organisation that adapt to technology can extend their communication level beyond regular correspondence and globally share their collaborative learning practices (Young, 2009).

There are factors in technological change that affect the business positively and negatively. Positive results are mainly exhibited when all the workforce of an organisation accepts the change and focuses on the development of the organisation. Additionally, it can further be claimed that technological developments help develop technical standards, improve

accessibility, and increase communication capacity. It allows organisations to compete globally and stabilise the costs (Suebsin and Gerd Sri, 2009). On the other hand, technology change is far more resisted by employees than any other changes (Beer and Nohria, 2000). This is because employees fear that technology changes might increase work pressure, higher responsibility, accountability, uncertainty, and redundancy (Chapman, 2000). The negative perceptions of employees regarding technological and other changes will be discussed in detail in the next section.

In conclusion, it can be argued that the term organisational change is rather broad and generic that includes various types and natures of change that occur in an organisation. These are major or minor changes in an organisation such as changes in structure, strategy, technology, and processes (Senior, 2002), changes in culture, behaviours, and attitudes (Lewin, 1947), changes in skill, performance, and leadership (Reardon and Rowe, 1998). Therefore, it is conceptualized that any organisational change is considered a continuous process of improving an organisation's strategy, structure, processes, and capabilities (Senior, 2002). This debate on organisational change is long continued. Even though there is an immense literature on change and its various forms, it is imperative to understand that change is an emotional roller-coaster for many individuals and is not well accepted. The next part of this chapter will shed light on the resistance and other facets attached to organisational change due to such observations.

3.5 Resistance to change

In 1973, 13 well-known authorities were chosen to speculate the significant management issues that might develop in the next 20 years. The central theme developed through their reports was the organisations' alarming ability to counter environmental and organisational change (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008). Resistance is defined as behaviour intended to prevent the implementation or use of a new system or prevent system designers from achieving their objectives (Goldberg et al., 1999). It is further declared that people are reluctant to change as

it is a human characteristic to resist change as expressed by Egan and Fjermestad (2005) that the natural human response to change is resistance. People become attached to familiar ways of doing things, even ways they initially regarded as cumbersome, costly, or ineffective. According to Honey (1988), introducing change in an organisation usually leads to resistance. Furthermore, Honey argued that resistance to change had become a common pervasive in most organisations when implementing change. Even though many managers know this fact, only a few acknowledge it before the organisational change is implemented to assess who might resist change and why. Researchers argue that even though change is implemented for positive reasons (e.g., to adapt to changing environmental conditions and remain competitive), employees often respond negatively toward change and resist change efforts. This adverse reaction is large because change brings increased pressure, stress, and uncertainty for employees (Armenakis & Bedeian, 1999; McHugh, 1997).

Organisational change is a rational activity and an emotional one that challenges deep-seated human fears and inspires human hope. Indeed, Kotter and Cohen (2002) argued that change is predominantly about heart matters, not the head. Organisations can operate in mechanical ways, but they also comprise living human beings who want meaningful work that allows them to have a life outside of work. Assuming that all organisational change is rational and logical in nature where fear, political positioning, and turf wars rage, one wonders why any change initiative might work (Aninkan, 2018). Not only 30 or 40 years back, but this genre of resistance to change is long discussed. Niccolò Machiavelli stated, 'it is essential to understand that is nothing more challenging to carry out, nor more uncertain of success or more dangerous to manage than, to instigate a new order of things' (Machiavelli, 1995). This phrase has become the typical heading and the most favoured topic within management textbooks. It has also been deep-rooted amongst the management vocabulary, and this topic is instilled in the expectation of the new generations of managers (Dent and Goldberg, 1999).

Change efforts in any organisation, firm, business, or enterprise tends to encounter some human resistance. Although many business executives and managers are aware of this fact, few take their time to systematically assess the employees or individuals who would resist that change initiatives, for whatever their reasons. Around change, managers tend to fix their thinking to a specific set of past practices and beliefs; field workers are independent and distrustful of their top management; therefore, they are bound to resist change. Such an approach can source problems because factors causing resistance to change stem from various individual and group aspects that have to be catered differently. Unquestionably, individuals who have faced change do undergo some emotional turmoil. Radical changes initiate loss and uncertainty amongst individuals (Luke et al., 1973). Nevertheless, there are many reasons why people resist change, from resisting to violently undermining it to finally embracing it (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008). Some of them are explained in detail in the next section.

3.5.1 Nature of Change

Research on change and resistance also highlights that employees' perceptions of change may be affected by the type of change being implemented. For example, incremental change occurs over time in small, orderly steps and with democratic leadership that includes employee consultation (Gersick, 1994). As this type of change encourages employee participation and involvement, employees have more positive attitudes about such changes. In contrast, radical change involves sudden, substantial changes to organisational processes and routines. The organisation's vision, goals, and values are redefined, resulting in significant changes to the organisation's structure (Gersick, 1991). This type of change is mainly driven by the top management and often requires directive leadership (Dunphy and Stace, 1993). Thus, lack of employee participation in changes leads to negative attitudes about such changes.

Similarly, changes caused by the external factors are also led by directive leadership that causes hesitance amongst employees (Tushman and Romanelli, 1985). In contrast, Manuela and Clara

(2003) concluded that transformational and radical change leads to higher resistance levels. That is because employees are connected to a culture that stresses loyalty and cohesion as a key-value and, at the same time, it limits their innovation and creative capabilities (Manuela and Clara, 2003, p.153).

3.5.2 Behavioural Factors

Researchers argue that the term 'resistance to change' is frequently used in the context of employees' attitudes towards organisational change (Ristino and Robert, 2000). As a general rule, anticipated changes are not resisted by people, but they resist the impact of those changes on them personally. When employees are comfortable in their jobs, current working environment, and relationships with co-workers and managers, they resist changes as they find them stressful. Thus, disruption of the behavioural dynamics of employees leads to resistance to desired changes. Coch and French's (1948) classic study highlighted employees' unwanted behaviour as a result of the management-imposed change around their working methods and at their overall job (Piderit, 2000). Their experiment examined that resistance has the power of involving violence and undesirable behaviour and those encouraging employees to participate in planning the change might decrease their resistance levels. Due to this study, there was an increase in research under participative decision-making and resistance (McCaffrey, Faerman, & Hart, 1995). Various studies on resistance are generated under behaviour; Brower and Abolafia (1995) outline resistance as a particular employee action or inaction, whereas Ashforth and Mael (1998) categorizes resistance as an intentional act by an employee of disobedience or omission (Piderit, 2000).

Oreg (2003) acknowledges that people are different from one another in their inclination to resist or adapt to change. These responses can be observed in employees' perceptions and attitudes towards voluntary and imposed changes. Furthermore, Oreg (2003) stated that employees who have dispositional resistance to change would incur adverse emotional

reactions such as anxiety, anger, fear, etc. These dispositional reactions have strong perceptions of one employee's emotional reaction. Therefore, management should be aware of employees' feelings concerning resistance to organisational change and consider employees' emotions and their willingness to remain in the organisation because these factors help bring employee commitment to the organisation that helps achieve the organisation's long-term objectives.

Research also indicates that resistance is cognitive as it includes negative feelings about the change. According to Armenakis, Harris and Mossholder (1993), resistance is termed as behavioural but is often preceded by the cognitive state called readiness. In the same way, Coch and French (1948) experiment can be reinterpreted and argues that participation can, to an extent, have cognitive and motivational effects on the resistance, suggesting that the term cognitive is an interrelated part of the resistance phenomenon (Piderit, 2000).

3.5.3 Fear of failure

In Business Management and organisations, authors Dubrin and Ireland (1993) consider resistance to change slightly different from the other authors. They have added fear as a significant factor of resistance to change. Individuals or employees fear poor outcomes from changes. For example, they may be assertive that the organisation has undergone the change where they might be required to work overtime with depleted capabilities that would result in lower productivity and task failures. Furthermore, Individuals also fear the unknown, and employees fear the resulting problem, realising that the change process was faulty and overlooked by their management (Dent and Goldberg, 1999).

On the other hand, employees might resist because they fear their job may be at risk, and or the change required may lead to the loss of their capabilities (Griffin, 1993). Furthermore, research reveals that employees do not necessarily resist the change itself but resist the undesirable outcomes of change (Dent & Goldberg, 1999). In contrast, the organisation's history in terms of successes and failures plays a vital role in determining the fear of failure

level. When initiating a new change, past experiences will come up into employees' minds affecting their degree of confidence and readiness to accept the proposed change (Toribio and Hernández, 2011).

3.5.4 Technological factors

Researchers on technological change consider technological innovations an irrational process that needs to be deeply understood to minimise resistance. Wargin and Dobiey (2001) discussed three reasons why people resist technological changes:

1. People are hesitant because they do not have the required skills to use or benefit from the new technology.
2. Traditional companies and organisations do not understand the application of new technology and its execution.
3. New technology changes organisational structure that causes uncertainty amongst employees.

Furthermore, Chapman (2002) stated that most employees oppose new technologies because they feel that change will not solve all the problems in one particular period. Additionally, Kailash and Thomas (1998) believe that adopting new technology is challenging for organisations. It alters job design and the role and responsibilities of employees and can negatively affect employees. Researchers accentuate that changing from one system to another is not merely a matter of learning a new system. An employee adapting to technological innovation requires a substantial change in approach and procedure in performing tasks (Ellen, Bearden and Sharma, 1991). Thus, the adoption and understanding of new technology will affect the task and the structure of the relationship between employee and the adopting organisation (Ellen, Bearden and Sharma, 1991). In contrast, Hiltz and Johnson (1990) believe that the most frequently mentioned risk associated with technological change is the

psychological risk related to an individual's perceived ability to successfully utilise the innovation.

3.5.5 Demographic Factors

Demographic and social factors such as age, gender and education levels also influence resistance to change. Attempts have been made to study demographic factors' influence on the resistance to change by various researchers (Martin, Quigley, and Roger 2005; Lombard and Crafford 2003). According to Lombard and Crafford (2003), there is a relationship between demographic factors and resistance to change. In terms of age, research claims that employees who are 50 years and above tend to be more resistant to changes, especially technological changes. Moreover, senior-level managers do not accept change and want to be stable in their current position; this means that the older one is, the more one is likely to resist change ((AL - Ameri, 2013). Alternatively, employees at a higher position in organisations resist changes because of their current position and status. They believe that if any change takes place, it will negatively influence their status, and hence their current position may be affected (AL -Ameri, 2013).

3.5.6 Parochial Self-interest

One of the powerful reasons people generally resist change is that they feel that change will make them lose something of value. In such cases, people emphasize and consider their self-interest important, i.e., (employees in an organisational setting) rather than a collective organisational interest. This leads to politics or also known as political behaviour (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008). Simplifying this with an example, after years of sustaining rapid growth, the organisation's executives decided that the vice president handle product planning and development and new staff processes. Operationally this change meant eliminating the decision power of other vice presidents like engineering and marketing over the new products, also decreasing their status. After the announcement of this new change, other executives proposed

many ideas that grew louder as to why this change will be chaotic and eventually fail. Due to their influence, the president had to ultimately disregard the change idea (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008). Similarly, when organisations switch from traditional counselling groups that monitor their employees' work-relations and motivation to rigid appraisal systems, change is resisted. They feel as their relationship is altered from being peer-oriented to boss-oriented, and pressures are placed to disregard such change initiatives (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008). Political behaviours can arise anytime between the change process or post-change. This behaviour mainly favours the employees' best interest or groups rather than the entire organisation. According to studies, political behaviour is usually dialogue-oriented and occurs smoothly. However, this behaviour is sometimes ruthlessly imposed by individuals or employees who feel the change might violate their implicit or psychological contract with their organisation (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008).

3.5.7 Misunderstanding and Lack of Trust

Individuals often resist change when they believe that the results of that change might cost them more than their gains. For example, situations form when there is a lack of or no trust between the initiators of change and the employees involved. It is also said that change agents fail to restore trust within the employees that often triggers negative behaviours both before and during the change (Ford, Ford and D'Amelio, 2008). For example, the executives of a small manufacturing company decided to impose a flexible working schedule, which leads to resistance. This was because the clerical and plan personnel distrusted the management and could not understand what flexible working meant. Some employees thought of working according to their means and availability that created chaos. Hence, management had to shelve the idea of such change (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008). There is no or little trust between the change agents and employees, misunderstanding and breaches occur.

Various academics argue that individuals do not resist change knowingly. Instead, it is the breach of their personal trust and belief that prompts them to behave in a certain way to protect their wellbeing instead of the entire organisation, leading to his or her resistance (Kotter & Schlesinger, 1979). This observation compels the writer to look at the concept of psychological contract and resistance to change. A psychological contract merely focuses on the mutual promises in an organisational context, also known as the social exchanges, that sources' trust' between an employer and employee (Taylor & Tekleab, 2004). Experimental literature shows that the contract may get breached if the employees distinguish between what they received and what they were promised (van den Heuvel and Schalk, 2009). The literature on resistance and distrust by change initiators argues that agreements such as implied and psychological contracts are broken when the change agents intentionally or unknowingly renege a promise and expect cooperation from employees (Ford, Ford and D'Amelio, 2008).

Research on trust and justice also claims that when employees consider being treated equally and fairly, their attitudes emerge as more positive, and they accept the change positively (Cobb, Wooten and Folger, 1995). Alternatively, when employees sense betrayal and injustice, they register resentment desire for retribution that leads to lower work quality, decreased cooperation levels, and declines employees' trust and obligations towards their employers (Robinson, 1996). Additionally, research suggests change executives or agents are more likely to face less resistance by employees who re-establish the damaged trust before and during the change process. Similarly, the past broken agreements and psychological contracts are proven to provoke adverse effects on employees' future actions leading to resistance and or revenge (Ford, Ford and D'Amelio, 2008).

3.5.8 Dissimilar Evaluation and Perception

Individuals resist change because they perceive the situation differently instead of their managers or change initiators and focus on benefits not just to themselves but also to the

organisation rather than the costs. For example, when a CEO proposes economic changes that are not well accepted by the employees (only because, in the long run, it would be harmful to the company's image), it leads to resistance (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008).

Generally, employees individually or in groups differ in terms of information possessed, and such differences in analysis lead towards resistance (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008).

Marlow (1957) claims that an organisation consists of both formal and informal groups. Both of these groups act differently, and why these groups accept or resist change depends merely on some of the themes generated in group dynamics. On this view, Ahmad (2000) debates that the effect of organisational change depicts that non-supervisors as change recipients report higher levels of role ambiguity and overload, lower job satisfaction and commitment, lower perceptions of job security, and lower acceptance of the organisational change. Moreover, Nelson et al. (1995) explain that job satisfaction and mental and physical health are declining more among manual and junior workers than managerial and supervisory staff overtime. In contrast, managers and supervisors, whose roles are more like change agents and change managers, perceive higher levels of organisational support, more opportunity, and access to information during change (Luthan & Sommer, 1999). Likewise, different attitudes between managers and staff arise because managers are more involved in the change process.

Furthermore, it was claimed to investigate these groups and the forces that bring change or resist it (Dent and Goldberg, 1999). Group dynamics and resistance to change were also mentioned by Lewin (1947), who explored that any group life, formal or informal is not without change. Studies also show resistance from a social perspective. They argue that resistance can transpire from employees' personal and rational assessment of the outcome and differs from the management one envisioned. The difference in such opinions creates doubts amongst the employees regarding the change's worth and may compel them to stand opposite their management (Waddell and Sohal, 1998).

On the other hand, employees' reaction to the desired change is also constituted on their preferences and predispositions that are not essentially grounded on the change's economic rationale assessment. For example, this may include employees who do not wish to accept the new technology, prefer working in a particular place, or even employees who may not wish to relocate their offices (Waddell and Sohal, 1998). As mentioned above, recent studies show that employees might resist change because they would want senior management to address issues that employees believe are imperative for their organisation to sustain high performance (Ashford et al., 1998).

In most cases, management feels that this (unrequired) resistance is mandatory from the employees, and therefore, they tend to fight it (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008). This assumption was selected by Watson (1982), who pointed that managers tend to perceive the resistance negatively because, according to them, employers or individuals resisting change are disobedient (Piderit, 2000). Even if the managers consider employees as narrow-minded and improvident, they are curiously drawn by their language of resistance and treat employees as obstacles (Piderit, 2000).

3.5.9 Low or no tolerance for change

All human beings differ in their adaption to skills and capabilities, with some people being much more limited in adaptation to new skills than others. People resist change because of this universal fear possessed in most of us, and not developing the new proficiencies and the behaviour required (Bennis, Benne and Chin, 1985). Organisational change carelessly requires the individual to adapt and change too much, speedily. Peter F. Drucker (1954) argues that sometimes managers also find the inability to change as the most significant obstacle with organisational growth (Drucke, 1954). He further argues that even when the change initiators intellectually understand the change emotionally, they sometimes may not implement it. This

is supported by several studies that discuss individuals' reluctance to give up their old habits as a common factor associated with resistance to change (Walter and Tichy, 1985).

The majority of the organisational changes come with the necessity of learning or developing new skills or abilities and acquiring new knowledge. Kanter (1985) argues that employees resist changes because they do not have confidence in themselves, and they feel incapable of meeting the demands. They struggle to accept and adjust to the new change because lack of necessary skills usually contributes to fear of failure and concerns over job security. People resist change because they think that they will not be able to develop the required skills and behaviours needed for the new situation and have no tolerance to upgrade their capabilities. Employees' inability to change their behaviours and skills with the speed that the organisation requires often creates obstacles to organisational growth (Toribio and Hernández, 2011).

Some academics have expressed this reluctance as the 'familiarity breeds comfort' (Oreg, 2003). When employees come across new stimuli, their current and familiar responses can negate the new situation, leading to stress and anxiety that become an association of the new incentive (Oreg, 2003). On the other hand, studies show that people's limited tolerance for change sometimes compels them to resist change even to their benefit. In simpler terms, if an employee gets a desired job due to change and is happy, they may resist giving that up because a new job requires enhanced skills, behaviour, new work-relations, and loss of current satisfactory activities and relationships (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008). The research assessed the cognitive factors underlying employee's response to the organisational change (as mentioned above). They were further establishing the traits of dogmatism or dogmatic behaviour (Rokeach, 1980). Dogmatic employees were observed to be inflexible and close-minded when it came to change, and therefore, their willingness to adapt to new situations is very low (Oreg, 2003).

3.5.10 Reluctant to lose (or give up) control

Some studies have highlighted the unwillingness to lose control as a significant imperative cause of resistance (Conner, 1993). An observed general human-trait is to resist any form of regulation of power imposed over them. Employees resist change because of their ingrown fear of losing control over their life situations due to the imposed change, rather than self-initiated (Oreg, 2003). The most common adopted activity to overcome this type of resistance is the encouragement of employee involvement and participation in organisational decision making (Sagie and Koslowsky, 2000).

3.6 Dispositional resistance to change

Dispositional resistance to change focuses on an individual's personality aspects that may compel some individuals to resist change instead of others (Judge et al., 1999). In specific and more straightforward terms, dispositional resistance to change has been categorized as a personality-based phenomenon of an individual resisting change (Oreg, 2003). It comprises of four dimensions: Routine seeking (to what extent are individuals feel comfortable with the contemporary routine and desire to maintain that in their lives); emotional reaction (is taken into consideration the degree to which the imposed or desired change provokes anxiety and discomfort amongst the individual); short-term focus (includes the extent to which the individuals focus on short-term problems arising with the change versus the long-term benefits); cognitive rigidity (can also be categorised as a form of an individual stubbornness. Individuals who are cognitively rigid struggle with changing their opinions and attitudes as required by the change). All these dimensions add to an individual's negative resistance to change (Oreg, 2017). Overall, individuals who have higher dispositional resistance are significantly less likely to pledge change and will mostly exhibit negative reactions towards any form of change imposed on them (Oreg et al., 2009).

Studies claim the concept of dispositional resistance to change was explicitly established to highlight the aspects of an individual's personality that relate to and can affect the notion of change (Oreg, 2003). Likewise, this concept is related to a distinctive form of trait-like risk aversion (Slovic, 1972), intolerance for uncertainty and ambiguity (Budner, 1962), sensation/emotional seeking (Zuckerman, 1994), and unrestricted to new experiences (Digman, 1990). This concept has been applied to numerous studies (Burnes and Walk, 2017). It has helped identify employee's attitudes and behaviours beyond other related traits in the context of organisational change (Oreg, 2003). In comparison, the assessment of dispositional aspect of change, parallel with resistance to change, was discovered to be more economical in its application rather than measuring a broad range of numerous factors such as self-esteem, anxiety, ambiguity, tolerance, risk-aversion; each of them tapping a different aspect to change (Oreg, 2003).

In practical significance, it can be said that Oreg et al.'s (2009) understanding of dispositional resistance to change is essential for gaining insight on personal selection. Hence, organisations undergoing or expecting to apply significant changes must consider their employees' dispositional resistance and other resistance factors such as capabilities, experience, progression, promotion, and development (Michel, By and Burnes, 2013). The question remains, is it ethical to source decisions around promotion and appointment on tools like the RTC scale? Is it acceptable to be judgmental that dispositional resistance to change is predominantly negative to an organisation? Measuring an employee's capabilities and skill set is one thing but measuring and anticipating factors providing personal insights into a future situation is vague and uncertain (Michel, By and Burnes, 2013).

Furthermore, the idle usage of dispositional resistance to change was promoted (apart from the other factors causing challenges) to measure staff development levels within an organisation. Just as Belbin's (1981) team role self-perception inventory and Myers-Briggs type indicator

(1943) are frequently used to monitor staff's progression and development needs (Arnold et al., 2010), dispositional resistance can be implemented alike. This adoption of behaviour is restricted to the individual level and promotes the teams to enhance their behaviour as per the change should benefit the organisation. On the other hand, researchers claimed, if the actual resistance is sparked from other factors such as the situation, then the organisation should be able to modify their change approaches in a way that would influence the situation, further reducing the actual level of resistance (Michel, Todnem By and Burnes, 2013).

3.6.1 Resistance to Change (RTC) scale

As per the findings above, resistance to change is a multidimensional phenomenon including behavioural, emotional, and cognitive elements (Piderit, 2000). A resistance to change scale was created to observe an individual's tendency to avoid and resist changes, generally diminishing change and the reasons for their aversive behaviour across types of change, contextually (Oreg, 2003). Recently, studies have focused on different antecedents related to resistance, such as self-discipline, alignment towards creative achievement, and lower defensive inflexibility levels, reflecting the individual's adaptability to change (Mumford et al., 1993). Judge, Thoresen, Pucik and Welbourne (1999) connected several other work-oriented measures of change. This included a 12-item scale that monitored employee's evaluation for the desired change, insights on their ability to cope up with the required change, and their observations as the initiators of change (Oreg, 2003). Personality traits were merged to create two concepts: the positive self-concept factor and the risk tolerance factor. The positive self-concept covers locus of control, self-esteem, over-all efficiency, and positive affectivity. Risk tolerance comprises openness to experiences, acceptance of ambiguity, and risk aversion (Oreg, 2003). Both of these concepts were proven to contribute towards managers coping with organisational change. Wanberg and Banas (2000) developed a similar concept, which included self-esteem, optimism, and psychological resilience (as a measure of perceived

control), which predicted employees' readiness to accept or decline organisational change (Oreg, 2003). A 17-item scale includes four factors: routine seeking, emotional reaction to imposed change, short-term focus, and cognitive rigidity. Furthermore, a 6-point Likert scale was generated for the respondents, stemming from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly agree), as shown in the appendix.

Several researchers have used this RTC scale to study and investigate reactions to change. Oreg (2006) examined a defence company undergoing restructure where employees who resulted high in RTC scale were likely to hold on to their negative attitudes towards change and less likely to initiate change (Stewart et al., 2009). As per Nov and Ye (2008), the RTC scale was a significant predictor of determining perceived ease of using the digital library (technology) amongst U.S university students (Stewart et al., 2009). Furthermore, Naus, van Iterson and Roe (2007) discovered the interaction of rigidity. While studying organisational cynicism under a Dutch trade union, Mudrack (2004) highlighted significant predictors as to which employees were inkling to leave their jobs (Stewart et al., 2009).

3.7 Culture and Resistance

According to Edgar Schein (2010), organisational culture is a pattern consisting of (group) shared assumptions developed and learned by solving external adaption and internal integration problems. These assumptions can be considered valid to be educated to the new member as an appropriate means to perceive, think and feel about those problems (Tharp, 2009). It was further argued by Schein (2010) that culture could be analysed at several different levels. He categorized culture in three divisions: Artefacts; the structured environment of the organisation, technology, architecture, visible and audible behavioural patterns, employee orientation, agreements, and so on, Espoused Beliefs and Values; includes individual's reasoning for their behaviour, ideologies, and the rationalization for their behaviour, Basic Underlying Assumptions; expectations that are mainly unconscious but genuinely reflect on how the group

member or individual think, perceive and feel. These assumptions initially arose as exposed values, but gradually, these values transform into the underlying assumptions of how things are (Schein, 1984).

The capability of an organisation to implement change leading to meet its objectives is primarily affected by its values and assumptions and the interplay between organisational culture and environment, as mentioned earlier. Making decisions and interpreting and managing the organisational environment affected by corporate culture clearly determine an organisation's performance and competitive position (Smircich, 1983; Cook & Yanow, 1993). Child (1981) pointed out that culture is an autonomous or external force. Each country develops its own distinct knowledge, ideologies, and rituals. The people in different cultural contexts reflect these separate national cultural attributes in social institutions. The identification and comparison of these different cultures emphasize variations in managerial and employee behaviours and practices across countries. The national cultural differences generate unique characteristics of organisations that evolve in different cultural contexts. Hence, this research will be looking into the cross-cultural dimensions of culture in the Nepalese context.

According to Geert Hofstede's (1980, 2001) research, values in an organisation are influenced by culture. He stressed that the problems within the management of any organisation would remain over time, and their solutions will differ less from period to period and country to country (Gautam, 2019). According to his definition, culture is precise. It focuses on collective mental programming: it includes part of our conditioning that we share with other members of our nation, region, or group but not with other nations, regions, or groups (Hofstede, 1983). To avoid cultural complexity, four dimensions of culture were proposed. These are power distance, individualism vs collectivism, uncertainty avoidance, and masculinity vs femininity. These four cultural dimensions are explained in detail to get a greater insight into the Nepalese organisational culture.

Power distance concerns the fact that all individuals in societies are unequal. Therefore, this dimension expresses the extent to which the less powerful members of institutions and organizations within a country expect and accept that power is distributed unequally (Hofstede, 2010). Individualism is the high side of the index that has a loosely knit social framework. This means that individuals are expected to look out for only themselves and their immediate families. On the contrary, Collectivism represents a tightly knit social framework within society. It pertains to societies in which people from birth onward are integrated into strong, cohesive in-group, which throughout people's lifetime continue to protect them in exchange for unquestioning loyalty (Hofstede, 2010). Uncertainty avoidance concerns the problem that the future can never be known. This ambiguity brings anxiety, and different cultures have developed different ways to alleviate this anxiety. The extent to which the members of a culture feel threatened by ambiguous or unknown situations (Hofstede, 2010). Lastly, society is considered masculine when emotional gender roles are distinct: men are supposed to be assertive, demanding, and focused on material success, whereas women are supposed to be more modest, tender, and concerned with the quality of life. On the other hand, society is considered feminine when emotional gender roles overlap. Both men and women are supposed to be modest, tender, and concerned with life quality (Hofstede, 2010).

Linking Hofstede's (2010) cultural dimensions to the Nepalese context, the research implies that the high-power distance in Nepalese culture indicates that they accept inequalities among the people and have clear hierarchical structures in organisations. The relationship between employees and employers has a wide gap in most organisations which helps to understand employees' attitudes. The employer is considered a dominant personality, and employees are generally expected to follow their commands and be obedient towards their supervisors/leaders. So, it is established that Nepalese organisations indicate high power distance and focuses on autocratic leadership (Gautam, 2019). Regarding the second spectrum,

Nepal is considered a collectivistic society, and employees in Nepalese organisations prioritise group success and commitment instead of individual benefits (Gautam, 2019). Hence, employees foster loyalty, responsibility, and strong relationships amongst their groups. Regarding the third dimension, employees in Nepalese organisations attain a low preference for avoiding uncertainty. This means that employees prefer a relaxed and flexible working environment (Gautam, 2019). Additionally, there is a greater acceptance for new ideas, innovative products, and employees who are most willing to try something different, whether it pertains to technology or organisational practices (Gautam, 2019). Similarly, for the fourth dimension, the research shows that, in general, the Nepalese society is feminine where individuals are conscious of equality, quality of well-being and working life, solidarity, and solves conflicts by negotiation and compromise (Gautam, 2019). It is further claimed that Nepalese women are treated equally to males in all aspects, and discrimination and differentiation amongst gender are very low (Gautam, 2019).

This research will incorporate the recent work by organisational and management science on culture and cross-culture values and practices when discussing organisational change and culture. The GLOBE study (Global Leadership and Organizational Behaviour Effectiveness Research Program) by House et al., (2004) provides a broader theoretical foundation on cultural dimensions. The GLOBE study uses the Hofstede (1980) dimensions as a baseline and has further extended the original five dimensions of the earlier studies to nine. These nine cultural dimensions are: (1) assertiveness, the degree to which individuals in societies are assertive, confrontational, aggressive, and straightforward; (2) uncertainty avoidance, the extent to which members of a society avoid uncertainty by relying on established social norms and practices; (3) power distance, the degree to which members of a society expect and accept that power is distributed unequally; (4) collectivism I (institutional Collectivism), the degree to which societal institutional practices encourage and reward collective distribution of

resources and collective action, as opposed to individual distribution and individual action; (5) collectivism II (in-group Collectivism), the extent to which members of a society express pride, loyalty, and cohesiveness in their organisations or families; (6) gender egalitarianism, the degree to which a society minimizes gender role differences; (7) future orientation, the degree to which members of a society engage in future-oriented behaviours such as planning and investing, and; (8) performance orientation, the degree to which a society encourages and rewards group members for performance and excellence, and (9) humane orientation, the extent to which a society encourages and rewards its members for being fair, altruistic, caring, and kind to others (Diehl and Terlutter, 2006).

The importance of the GLOBE study for this research is that it allows organisational effectiveness to be viewed from the leadership perspective. Each organisation has leaders with their leadership characteristics that are often culturally based. In order to conduct changes that are thoroughly communicated and accepted by the employees, leaders might need to adapt or be flexible in their leadership characteristics (Gunnell, 2016). For example, suppose the leader is more autocratic in giving power to the employees in a Nepalese organisation, and the work productivity is still low. In that case, the leader will have to adapt to the cultural dimensions of self-attaining power and authority over the employees. As further argued by Rijal (2010), most Nepalese organisations tend to be high in bureaucratic orientation compared to Western countries. Additionally, the employees prefer maintaining formal relationships with others, seeking security from in-group orientation, inflexibility, and avoiding risks.

Cultural understandings and systems that are evolved and established within an organisation play a key role among employees in what to think and how to act and thus characterize how things are done in an organisation (Danışman, 2010). Although, culture provides frameworks for interpreting events and solving problems. However, it cannot be changed easily because of its societal roots and psychodynamics nature (Meek, 1988). Thus, any attempt to change

organisational policies, strategies, and systems may not be directly supported with a corresponding change without understanding the organisational employees' existing culture and meaning systems (Danışman, 2010). It is then likely that such cultural understandings and meanings, when incompatible with change initiatives, may cause resistance to change (Zaltman & Duncan, 1977). In this way, a study by Amis, Slack, and Hinings (2002) validates that when the proposed changes do not coincide with employees' cultural values, some resistance is presented. Indeed, Kirkman and Shapiro (1997) provided thorough insights into how employees' cultural values affect resistance to change regarding self-management teams. For example, employees with a strong cultural emphasis on high power distance, orientation, and determinism resist change. This is because of self-management, in which individuals set goals, self-monitor, and self-evaluate, that is incompatible with such values. It is further declared that when employees are not culturally ready for organisational change, they usually foster resistance to change (Orlikowski & Hofman, 1997).

Likewise, Schein (1992) insists that the fundamental reason for resistance to change is the organisation's culture. When change initiative does not accord with or support the existing cultural understandings and meaning systems, culture-based resistance will result (Amis et al., 2002). There is a well-accepted understanding that a conservative organisational culture can delay the implementation of new organisational changes. Resistance to change backed up with the existing culture can suspend the enhancement of customer-oriented reforms (Johansson et al., 2014). Academic argues that when initiating organisational change, one of the critical areas that should be considered pre- and post-change is the organisational culture and sub-cultures. Routines, attitudes, behaviour, and rules of everyday activities can vary from the contemporary organisation setting to the desired one (Johansson et al., 2014). Moreover, resistance to change initiative will be more likely in an organisation where societal-based understandings and values are deeply rooted, as they remain reasonably impervious to change.

3.8 Managing Resistance to Change

There are several misconceptions about what resistance to change is, who resists it, what it means to the organisation, and why it should be managed. Managers need a richer understanding of the phenomenon to appreciate its value and its adverse effects minimised (Smollan, 2011). It is generally perceived that resistance to change is harmful and is the greatest obstacle to attaining change objectives (Muo, 2014). Some academics have labelled resistance to change as a brick wall and a dangerous roadblock to transformation. In contrast, others see resistance to change as one of the nastiest, most debilitating workplace cancers (Burke, 2008). To Foote (2001), there is no more powerful, paradoxical, or equal opportunity killer of progress and good intentions. Many managers underestimate the variety of ways people react to organisational change and how they can positively influence specific individuals and groups during a change (Kotter, & Schlesinger, 2008).

Academics claim that finding the cause of resistance requires researchers to understand an individual's facts, values, and beliefs. Although these facts, beliefs, and values are not visible and the role an individual plays in creating resistance can be difficult to separate (Hultman, 2003). Fortunately, it can be argued that observation plays a vital role in understanding and attaining information for this task. For example, observing what people do or say. Thus, everything that people do act and say provides clues about the role these variables play in resistance.

In contrast, it is risky to assess the causes of resistance by observing only what a person does. It is easy to misinterpret other's behaviour. While it's possible for resistance to stem from a single fact, belief, or value, this is unusual. More commonly, several facts, beliefs, and values are linked together to form a pattern, so it is essential to gather all relevant data (Hultman, 2003). According to Eisenhardt (2000), there are many ways that change agents or managers can adopt to reduce resistance to change within their organisations. The senior management of

the organisation must explain to their employees the need for change and emphasize the benefit of those changes on individuals and departments and be willing to answer questions raised by the employees. Resistance not only disrupts the employee-employer relationship but hampers the productivity of the employees and the overall organisation in the long-run. Thus, it is quintessential to acknowledge and fully understand the nature of resistance. Once it is identified, several strategies can overcome resistance to change within organizations (Eisenhardt, 2000). Some of the critical strategies vital to this research are explained below

3.8.1 Communication

Communicating with the employees regarding the present situation and the desired state brings trust among the employees, which is essential. Thus, the change agents or senior management should encourage consultation with employees before and during the change processes (Kafouro and Lock, 2005). The communication channels within all hierarchal levels should be open and accessible to all the employees to access information available and discuss it. Likewise, it is vital for management to understand their employees' feelings when confronted with change because these feelings and perceptions may influence their subsequent actions (Krantz, 1999). Correspondingly, Horgan and Simeon (1988) stated that communicating with employees effectively will help overcome change. It can be observed that ineffective communication leads to low-level job satisfaction that may affect employees' job performance. This is mainly observed when there is a change in technology, management, or work structure. Besides, ineffective communication also leads to other factors such as job stress, a lack of a work-life balance, fear of coping with new changes, etc.

Rick and Jeanenne (2011) claim that communication is a vital strategy to overcome resistance as any negative impressions about change can be cleared by communication with each other. They further debate that resistance occurs when there is a lack of communication between management and employees. Employees feel that they are not involved in the process and have

not received any communication about the change process. Employees' feelings can be understood by communicating with them and understanding their perceptions. Furthermore, Rick and Jeanenne (2011) stated that employees who communicate with management positively impact solving the change process's problems. This argument also links with the research conducted by Cornelissen (2014). As per his work, the degree to which managers involve their employees in decision making and communicate with them has a direct and substantial impact on employee morale and commitment to the organisation.

3.8.2 Employee Engagement

When employees are involved in any way within their departments, they tend to have a positive job-related attitude, a strong identification with work, improved mental health, performance, motivation, and better access to personal resources (Näswall et al., 2008). Hence, a well-involved and guided employee feels more connected to its organisation and the leadership (Näswall et al., 2008). Likewise, Jaussi (2007) stresses that the more employees feel integrated and involved in organisations, the less resistance and the better task performance will be.

On the other hand, encouraging involvement can strengthen the psychological contract between employees and managers, and the trust that is developed is manifested in employee's behaviour and attitudes positively (Weber and Weber, 2001). Besides, research further underlines that having a positive leader is crucial during organisational change as a leader provides a vision of change, supports employees, and model appropriate behaviour. Such actions help build stability during change and enhance employees' commitment to it (Schweiger et al., 1987; Covin & Kilmann, 1990).

3.8.3 Training

As per the research of Butterfield (2010), organisations continuously change, and, accordingly to that, employees need to change themselves within the working environment. One strategy that is heavily underlined in the research of resistance to change is training and development.

In order to ensure the changes are implemented successfully, employees must learn how to operate them. For example, new technology and new procedures should be learned to improve workplace productivity and quality. Thus, managers need to implement innovative training sessions to build a robust environment (Butterfield, 2010). These training sessions are vital in enhancing employees' motivation levels to improve their performance and help them achieve the organisation's overall goals. Adding to this, Dent and Goldberg (1999) argue that senior management must educate individuals and groups in an organisation regarding the need for change and create awareness in the individuals and groups that change is a positive factor and inevitable in today's marketplace. They further added that motivation and training are two primary tools to implement desired change strategies successfully. A successful change process can be carried out by making employees part of the change and providing them with training that enhances their skills and capabilities (Dent and Goldberg, 1999).

According to Dean and Linda (2010), training should be an ongoing process concerning motivating employees to accept the change. The training should include planning for the new changes, objectives, resources, and considering the results. Each employee should be aware of these steps before any changes are put to practice. Furthermore, through training, employees will know precisely what the company expects them to do. During the explanations in the training's employees will come to know the procedures and each step will be explained showing why it is important. This measure will deliver a clear and straightforward statement of affairs. A demonstration of each step of the new plan(s) procedures allows employees to adapt to change as quickly as possible and avoid future consequences. Training can motivate employees because it helps them to understand their work and to envision the future.

3.8.4 Motivation

Motivation is known as individuals' willingness to exert high levels of effort toward organisational goals that are conditioned by the effort's ability to satisfy some individual need

(Yusoff, Kian and Idris, 2013). In other words, motivation helps boost employee performance levels through assistance, monitoring, guidance, and discussions. It is the management's responsibility to ensure that their employees are motivated enough to execute desired changes. Adding to this, Hutchin (2001) argues that employers must provide counselling sessions to their employees to discuss their issues and work problems. This helps in clearing employees' uncertainty regarding any new policies or strategies and boosting their working morale. Adding to this, Gabriel and Carr (2002) argue that employee engagement helps establish respect and self-esteem amongst employees. Senior management has to ensure employees are treated equally and fairly to avoid unconstructive feelings and mistrust, which are the essential ingredients of resistance (Yusoff, Kian and Idris, 2013). According to Rebecca and Rolf (2009), motivated employees find adopting changes easy instead of unmotivated employees. They further argue that motivation can differ from time to time and from person to person when the change process occurs. The initial stages of change, such as introducing new technology, would require the management to train, guide, and motivate their employees and inform them of the importance of change (Yusoff, Kian and Idris, 2013).

3.8.5 Reward Policy

According to Stavrakakis (2008), compensation and recognition in the form of money or something of equal value brings satisfaction to employees and boosts their morale. Such rewards are extrinsic motivators that management can give their employees to support and overcome negative feelings and attitudes towards organisational change. Rewarding employees based on performance is one of the strategies that management should apply to overcome resistance. Equally, Dennis, Schraeder and Mike (2009) stated that one motivating strategy is rewarded. Employees are motivated by different things, but a rewarding strategy that includes financial rewards is the best motivation.

On the other hand, financial rewards do not always motivate employees, and for management, managing resistance using financial rewards is costly. In this regard, Dennis, Schraeder, and Mike (2009) suggested various measures that can be performed by the management to let their employees know their efforts are recognised and to ensure that rewards will be appreciated. Continuous interaction with employees and recognising 'a good job well done' can motivate employees (Dennis, Schraeder and Mike, 2009). Consequently, motivated employees that perform well are rewarded and valued by senior management. These rewards include compensation, quality in the work-life balance, benefits recognition, and career opportunities. Hence, this strategy can bring satisfaction to employees, and in the long run, that would also increase their productivity. It is further stressed that change can be implemented smoothly if employees are manipulated by providing them with benefits like bonuses, pay rise, etc., and withholding information (Dent and Goldberg, 1999). Adding to that, rewarding employees for their work sends positive signals to other co-employees that they will also be recognised and rewarded for efforts made in reaching company milestones and goals (Malecki, 2009).

It is clearly understood from the literature that resistance to change is expected and encountered by most organisations. How to overcome this resistance is a big task for management. As discussed in the earlier sections, organisations have to initially identify the reasons, factors, and driving forces that cause resistance to change and then plan and formulate strategies to overcome such issues. If an organisation successfully implements effective strategies (as discussed above), it will help employees improve performance and overcome resistance issues.

3.9 Summary of Key Model and Theories Used.

Key Models and Theories used in this Research	Summary
Lewin's 3 stage Model (1947)	Kurt Lewin (1947) developed a change model including three stages of planning and implementing change. Unfreeze, change and refreeze. This model is applicable as it helps change agents articulate the change with a basis of trial and error and ensure all the employees' transition with the change for its successful implementation.
PESTEL Analysis	PESTEL analysis or framework helps organisations screen and analyze the macro-environmental factor that can impact the business. These include political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal factors. For organisations to implement desired changes, the external environment plays a vital role in determining the organisation's success or failure.
Hofstede's cultural dimensions (1980)	The cultural dimensions model by Greet Hofstede (1980) provides five dimensions of national culture. These are power distance, individualism vs collectivism, masculinity vs femininity, uncertainty avoidance, and long-term vs short-term orientation. In order to understand an organisation's management/leaders and their competence to carry decisions, it is essential to recognize the cross-cultural dimensions of individual's which differs from society to society and country to country.
GLOBE Study/Project (1991)	The GLOBE project is founded by Robert House (1991), and it is a multi-phase, multi-method research study that examines inter-relationships between societal cultures, societal effectiveness, and organisational leadership. It includes nine cultural dimensions: performance orientation, assertiveness,

	<p>future orientation, humane orientation, institutional collectivism, in-group collectivism, gender egalitarianism, power distance, and uncertainty avoidance. It was essential to incorporate this study in this research because employees in various organisations have different expectations from their leaders, who are influenced by their cultural values.</p>
<p>Dispositional Resistance to Change</p>	<p>The concept of dispositional resistance to scale is established by Shaul Oreg (2003) that is used to analyze and validate the resistance to change (RTC) scale. This theory is a personality trait concept that pertains to an individual's tendency to resist change and consider changes as aversive across distinct contexts and types of change. This concept is incorporated in this research because it gives a broader perspective on behavioral, psychological, and personal factors that cause employees to resist changes and why.</p>

3.10 Conclusion

The purpose of this chapter is to provide greater insight to change and resistance theories that are relevant to this study. It is essential to understand this research's theoretical underpinnings. It serves as a basic understanding of how employees' perceptions of organisational change and factors triggering resistance have emerged over time. The literature critically reviewed, and the theoretical models discussed in this chapter refer to several change studies and theories that explain why organisational change is vital and the uncertain factors accompanying that change in organisations and societies worldwide.

The survey questionnaire for this research is based on a resistance to change scale (RTC) developed by Oreg (2003). This scale was best suited for this study because it monitors employees' understanding of the desired change and delves into their ability to cope with

changes and their personal interpretations as the initiators of change in various organisations around the world. Furthermore, this scale also assisted the researcher in developing the questions for the in-depth interviews along with the behavioural and social features so that the holistic perspective of employees undergoing change and encountering resistance to those changes is investigated.

Selected empirical literature is derived from the previous studies on change management in Asian countries, particularly India, Pakistan, and Nepal, due to their cross-cultural similarity. On the contrary, no previous studies have been conducted in the genres of change management in the banking industry in Nepal. Similar studies on HRD, employee perception, evaluations, and performance measurements systems in the Nepalese Banks were examined to get a generic insight into the employee behaviour in the operating commercial Banks of Nepal. Hence, (as per the researcher's comprehension) this is the first mixed-methods research investigating change management in Himalayan Bank.

The literature on organisational change is consistent in indicating that change is not a single or a continuous process. Instead, it is broken down into several different steps. The literature further reveals that regardless of the primary demographic factors, employees in any (small or large) organisations tend to struggle with change at personal or work levels and environments. Although change is necessary for survival and growth, change brings risks, and with risks, resistance. Leaders and managers must carefully plan the implementation of desired change(s), and it should be considered that employees are well-communicated on their shifting working environment. The managers or change agents need to be aware of other changes that are also occurring and acknowledge the risk that one set of changes may be overwhelmed by the combination of other changes. Moreover, the literature sheds light on the importance of managing resistance to change as it is an essential skill in today's increasingly complex and

competitive world. By implementing the concepts and models presented in this literature, one can help their organisation carve out a path to a successful future.

The Findings depict that change is perceived positively amongst the majority of the HBL employees. There have been various modifications to the CBS and technological systems to improve the Bank's competence. However, there is still resistance monitored, particularly with the changes associated with the digitalisation of tasks amongst some senior employees. Furthermore, the findings also reveal practices that the Bank's leaders should observe to ensure changes are thoroughly communicated to all the employees and to minimise the current resistance levels amongst the employees affected.

It can be concluded that change is an initiative that every organisation must take to sustain and compete in changing environments and in being flexible in all aspects. The organisation and the workforce must be committed to a change process and take positive steps towards new heights, sustainability, and profit. The next chapter will discuss the methodological underpinnings of this research.

Chapter 4 – Methodology

4.1 Introduction

In business studies, the word research has multiple meanings, and its particular definition differs from expert to expert and discipline to discipline (Kumar, 2019). It is argued that research is not solely a skill (set) that is achieved but it also a way of thinking (Kumar, 2019). Within the framework of a researcher's thinking, observations are crafted which are then questioned to be further explored, explained, and understood. Additionally, these observations, conclusions and inferences are drawn to develop skills and improve the knowledge base (Kumar, 2019). The fundamentals of research are using one or more research methods and approaches that would be suited to answer a study's aims and objectives. Likewise, research methods refer to the practices and procedures attained to analyse data (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2007). Research methodology refers to the concept of how the research should be undertaken (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2007). These practices include various methods and approaches such as quantitative, qualitative, interviews, questionnaires, action research, case study and so on (Kumar, 2019).

It has to be understood that research is not just collecting facts with no clear purpose or recording information without interpretations (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2007). Each research that is carried out is based on distinctive terms and approaches and is tailored to answer particular questions designed for that research.

It is claimed that research develops and enhances a researcher's rationale that is logical and encourages to critically examine the research aspects (Kumar, 2019). It allows the researcher in understanding and developing guiding principles that administer a particular procedure related to an individual's research. The importance of research methodology is that: it is the channel that helps the researcher in revealing techniques that are crucial to discover the answer

for a particular research (Kumar, 2019). Studies claim that researcher faces barriers when investigating a research problem. However, these barriers can be removed by employing the correct research methods or methodology (Taylor et al., 2015).

This chapter will be presenting the methodological frameworks for this research and justify methods that are adopted to carry out the research. Moreover, other areas associated with research methodology will also be covered.

4.2 Research aims and Objectives

The aims of this research are to explore and examine employee's insights on change and resistance to organisational change in Himalayan Bank Ltd.

Following objectives have been prepared to achieve this aim:

- To identify the nature of organisational change that has occurred at the bank.
- To gauge the perceptions of change amongst employees.
- To identify factors contributing to resistance to change amongst employees.
- To establish organisational strategies implemented to achieve desired change.

From this stage, it is suitable for the researcher to mention the type of data collected for this study and explain the methods used to collect that data. This will be influencing our discussion on research philosophy and approaches relevant to this research. These areas will be discussed later in this chapter. In order to execute the desired objectives, this study is a mixed method study. Where quantitative data is collected through questionnaire and qualitative data through in-depth interviews. The patterns and structure for survey and interview is designed specifically for Himalayan bank employees. Further details of data collection methods used in this research are presented and explained later in the chapter.

4.3 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy is defined as the development of research knowledge, its assumptions, and the nature of that knowledge (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). In other words, it is precisely what a researcher must do when going ahead with research, that is developing new knowledge for those assumptions (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012). Studies argue that various types of assumptions are made (Burrell and Morgan 1979). These assumptions depict how the researcher understands the research aims, the methods, and the interpretation of findings (Crotty 1998). It is also argued that well-thought-out and consistent assumptions will help establish a credible research philosophy that will underpin the research strategy, data collection, and analysis (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

Collis and Hussey (2009) claim that a research paradigm is a philosophical framework that directs how scientific research should be conducted. According to one interpretation, the paradigm is a set of beliefs representing a worldview (Guba & Lincoln, 1994). Generally, paradigm refers to scientific paradigms, philosophical paradigms, or research paradigms. Similarly, a paradigm can also be characterised as a mental model or framework of thoughts or beliefs through which reality can be interpreted (Thakkar, 2020). Furthermore, other studies refer to a paradigm as a collective belief system and the accompanying methods (Gliner, Morgan and Leech, 2009). In the simplest form, a paradigm is a way of how research is thought and carried out. Not particularly a set methodology but it a pathway for a researcher towards conducting their study. As a philosophy can, be clearly described with the help of paradigms (Gliner, Morgan and Leech, 2009), there are several reasons why a researcher must understand a research philosophy before investigating a particular field.

According to Mackenzie & Knipe (2006), if a researcher is clear on what philosophy to adopt for their research, choosing the methodology, research strategy, and design becomes relatively

easier to decide on. There are few reasons highlighted by Easterby-Smith et al. (2012), who state these as follows:

- It is a researcher's responsibility to clearly understand the fundamental issues associated with philosophies. In the future, they are conscious of their reflective role in research methodology and design. This will help the researcher tackle issues related to the theory of knowledge and help them make a further contribution in their fields.
- A proper philosophical stance can explain research design. This considers the data evidence required for the research and how it will be gathered and interpreted. Furthermore, it also helps simplify the answering to the questions that are being investigated.
- Understanding the knowledge of philosophy will benefit the researcher with a creative and exploratory skill to identify the research methods and designs suitable for their study.

Depending on personal sets-beliefs, researchers are likely to practice research following their beliefs about phenomena and the world. If a researcher is interested in people's experiences, such studies will be investigating human experiences to understand the world (Sefotho, 2015). Researcher's understanding of the world is underpinned by the philosophy they adopt. Philosophy is aimed at understanding the world as it is a broad and complex concept, and therefore, the metaphor for understanding these worldviews and paradigms needs to be examined (Kamil 2011). The world can be understood from our own experiences and those of others. The world, in this sense, refers to a social world and the experiences of people in that social world. These many experiences form one's view of the world, popularly known as a world view.

While discussing these philosophical stances of various worldviews, it is essential to distinguish between philosophies regarding this study's relevance. For this purpose, a useful

approach is to consider the philosophical categorisations by Saunders et al. (2015), who distinguish between realism, positivism, interpretivism, and pragmatism. Due to the nature of this research, it will focus on the philosophy of pragmatism. By adopting this philosophy, researchers are less restricted in terms of how they can carry out research as pragmatism considers “what works” to answer research questions rather than making choices between positivistic and constructivist paradigms (Creswell and Clark, 2011). When paradigms are defined as shared beliefs among members of a speciality area this means that there is less emphasis on the ontological and epistemological perspective adopted for the research and more on developing a consensus as to which methods work and can be established by the speciality area (Creswell and Clark, 2011). Hence, it will be useful to review this philosophical underpinning to support outlining the methodological approach taken in this research.

4.3.1 Positivism

Auguste Comte (1853) argued: "all good intellects have repeated...that there can be no real knowledge but on what is based on observed facts." (Easterby-Smith et al, 1991, p.22).

Comte (1853) proposed that all knowledge is derived from human observation of objective reality and emphasized that the investigated objects are based on empirical facts (Bourdeau, 2010). Researchers following this tradition hold the role of objective analysts that understands data by separate facts and its value, as mentioned by Robson (2002) and Saunders, Lewis & Thornhill (2003). It claims that the correct procedure to establish specific knowledge is through objectivity and quantification (Kamil 2011). Objectivity in this paradigm implies that the researcher and the reality being investigated are separate entities, and objective reality exists beyond the human mind (Weber 2004). Adding to this, this paradigm assumes that data and data collection are independent of the researcher's interests and qualities. Hence, their perceptions and beliefs have no value to influence the researcher (Heeks and Bailur, 2007). Following the positivist standpoint, the researcher should only have minimum contact with the

research participants if necessary (Smith, 1998; Wilson, 2010). Some of the standard features and assumptions of positivism gathered by Robson (2002: 20) are as follow:

- Objective knowledge and facts can only be gained by direct experience or observations and are the only knowledge available and acceptable to science. Other theoretical entities are rejected.
- Science is 'value-free,' which means it separates facts from values.
- The data is primarily based quantitatively and derived from particular rules and procedures, fundamentally unlike common sense and visual interpretations.
- Most scientific propositions are derived from facts, and then these facts are tested against the hypothesis.
- The purpose of science in this paradigm is to develop casual laws. These laws are then applied to help and explain the causing of events.

Whilst positivism may seem to have some relevance to this study as some of the data collected for this research is quantitative data collected via a questionnaire, and questionnaires are often associated with a positivist paradigm, in reality this study does not have a positivist nature. This is because the questionnaire despite being associated with a quantitative approach is going to be analysed qualitatively to provide data that would support the interview findings.

One of the biggest criticisms that this philosophy has faced is understanding and investigating human beings as a separate entity, disconnecting them from their social world where they reside. Thus, it is impossible to understand people without considering their perceptions influenced by their professional and personal environment (Collis and Hussey, 2003). Other researchers have also criticised this paradigm on the element of subjectivity and personal interference. The criticisms are as follow:

- Quine argues (1961) that the knowledge we derive from making sense of the 'phenomenon' is involuntarily mediated by the concepts used to analyse it. Therefore, experiences cannot be classified or described without 'interpretation.' He further adds that 'facts' are not separate entities. In reality, theory influences the fact that we emphasise and how those facts are interpreted. In turn, if the facts appear to falsify the theory, the conclusion may be affected.
- This paradigm makes it impossible to measure phenomena related to people's beliefs, attitudes, and thoughts because these may not be explicitly observed or measured, with or without evidence (Hammersley, 2013).
- Johnson & Onwuegbuzie (2004) argue, since the objective stance of positivism generalises all large-scale results, there is a risk of the truth being neglected and overlooked. Hence, by not including individuals whose interpretation and understanding of that phenomenon, issue or event could be essential for results.

In essence, positivism is based on the fact that everything's measurable and the researcher is an outsider with no attachment to the study. However, collecting statistical and numerical data does not quite answer to comprehend beliefs, meaning, and experiences. This topic's nature requires the researcher to understand employees' perceptions and experiences associated with organisational change in Himalayan Bank. The statistical findings will be analysed to answer the aims of this research. However, in reality, numerical findings may lack the rich quality of data required to interpret and gauge participants' perspectives regarding change and resistance.

4.3.2 Interpretivism

In contrast to positivism, at the other spectrum of research paradigm, there is interpretivism. This approach assumes that there is no 'universal truth' instead of other approaches and individual voices are equally important as the 'democratic' voices (Al-Darmaki, 2015). It is initially embedded that implemented methods to understand knowledge related to human and

social sciences cannot be the same as using physical sciences. This is because humans interpret the world they are in, and then their actions are based on those interpretations, whereas the world does not (Hammersley, 2013). Adding to this, Gill and Johnson (1997) state that interpretivism focuses on examining people and their social behaviour. So, it can be concluded that interpretivism can be defined as “a focus on exploring how human beings make sense of experience and transform experience into consciousness, both individually and as shared meaning” (Patton 2002, p.104).

Hence, this philosophical stance focuses on the empathic understanding of human behaviour rather than using the forces to act upon it (Bryman and Bell, 2011). Equally, this philosophical approach accuses the positivist approach of lacking the necessary understandings of business and management's evolving and complex world. Some of the standard features and characteristics of interpretivism are as follow:

- In the interpretivist perspective, the researcher tends to gain a much deeper insight into the phenomenon and its complexity in its context instead of generalising the base understanding for the whole population (Creswell, 2007).
- Interpretivist researchers view the world as infinitely complex and open to interpretations (O'Leary, 2004).
- The world is ambiguous and regimented that initiates complexities when understanding things and behaviour in reality (O'Leary, 2004).
- Interpretivists consider that the worlds contain multiple facets and angles to interpret reality. This means that truth differs from person to person. It is not single and contains an element of bias (Al-Darmaki, 2015).
- The researcher is considered a social actor who reflects and points differences amongst people while investigating the phenomenon. To reflect on the issues diversely, the

researcher may employ multiple research methods (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2012).

This approach is considered a fundamental and natural approach for data collection and mainly includes interviews, observation, and focus groups. Concerning this study, a vital element of this research is embedded within the interpretivism philosophy with qualitative data collected via in-depth interviews to explore and understand employees' views on organisational change and resistance. This will help the researcher gain insights on the participants in their natural settings by employing methodologies such as a case study to gain authentic information regarding the objective (Tuli, 2010).

Despite having affirmative characteristics, this paradigm is also not criticism-free. Some of them are as follow:

- Interpretivist paradigm aims to excavate in understanding the knowledge of phenomenon within its complexity rather than generalising results to other people and contexts (Cohen, Manion & Marison, 2011). Hence, it tends to ignore the gap in verifying the study's validity and usefulness while using scientific procedures.
- Specific studies argue that interpretivism follows the tradition of being subjective rather than objective (Mack, 2010). Due to this, the research outcomes are mostly affected by the researcher's personal interpretations, beliefs, and cultural preferences, leading to bias in results.
- The paradigm lacks addressing the political and ideological impact on social reality and its knowledge (Thi and Pham, 2018).
- Data collection in this paradigm can be tedious, and the analysis plus the interpretation of data is considered to be more difficult than other traditions (Saunders et al. 2007).

4.3.3 Pragmatism

Pragmatism is a paradigm based on the philosophical foundation that embraces a plurality of methods (Maxcy, 2003). As a research paradigm, it is based on the proposition that researchers should use the philosophical or the methodological approach to well-suit the particular research problem that is being investigated (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 1998). This philosophical approach is often associated with mixed-method or multiple method research and must employ formal and informal rhetoric (Creswell and Clark, 2011).

The word pragmatism is originally derived from the Greek word "pragma," which means action (pansiri, 2005). Pragmatist philosophy holds that human actions can never be separated from past experiences and from the beliefs that have originated from those experiences. Human thoughts are thus intrinsically linked to action. People take actions based on the possible consequences of their actions, and they use the results of their actions to predict the outcomes of similar actions in the future (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). A central contention of pragmatist philosophy is that meaning of human actions and beliefs is found in their consequences. External forces do not determine humans: they can shape their experience through their actions and intelligence (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). Pragmatists believe that reality is not static—it changes at every turn of events.

Similarly, the world is also not static—it is in a constant state of becoming. The world is also changed through actions—action is the way to change existence. Actions have the role of an intermediary. Therefore, actions are pivotal in pragmatism (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). A major underpinning of pragmatist philosophy is that knowledge and reality are based on beliefs and habits that are socially constructed (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). Pragmatists generally agree that all learning in this world is socially made, but some versions of those social constructions match individuals' experiences more than others (Morgan, 2014).

Pragmatists believe that we are free to believe anything that we want, although some beliefs are more likely than others to meet our goals and needs (Morgan, 2014). Biesta (2010) reminds us not to merely understand pragmatism as a philosophical position but rather as a set of philosophical tools of value for addressing problems. As a research paradigm, pragmatism orients itself toward solving practical problems in the real world. It emerged as a method of inquiry for more practical-minded researchers (Creswell and Clark, 2011). For pragmatists, an investigation—in both social life and social work research—is effective only if it achieves its purposes (Hothersall, 2019). Pragmatism rejects the traditional philosophical dualism of objectivity and subjectivity and allows the researcher to abandon the forced dichotomies, which are post-positivism and constructivism (Creswell and Clark, 2011). In pragmatism, empirical is preferred over idealistic or rationalistic approaches (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). Rather than assigning post-positivism and constructivism in two different ontological and epistemological camps, pragmatism asks the researcher to focus on the two approaches to inquiry (Morgan, 2014).

Pragmatist researchers' choice of one version of reality over another is governed by how well that choice results in anticipated or desired outcomes (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2008). Goles and Hirschheim (2000) elaborate on this with the following example: For a more positivistic researcher, an object with a flat surface and four legs would always be a table. For a constructivist, based on their perspective, the same object would be a table if s/he was eating from it, a bench if s/he was sitting on it, and a platform if s/he was standing on it. However, a pragmatist would define the object based on its utility; for instance, the object would be a table if they intend to eat from it, a bench if s/he intends to sit on it, and a platform they want to stand on it. In this example, it is essential to notice that the pragmatist would not define the object based on what it is or what it is being used for but instead based on how it would help the pragmatist achieve their purpose (Goles and Hirschheim, 2000, p. 261). Pragmatists believe

that we are free to believe anything that we want, although some beliefs are more likely than others to meet our goals and needs.

This research argued in favour of adopting pragmatism as the appropriate paradigm for undertaking mixed methods research in the Himalayan Bank, particularly when paradigms are regarded as shared beliefs among members of a specialty area that is being researched. Here, mixed methods researchers can choose the combination of quantitative and qualitative methods to answer their research questions (Johnson and Onwuegbuzie, 2004). Alternatively, the other reason why the researcher adopted this paradigm is that, unlike deductive for positivism and inductive for interpretivism, pragmatism assists in the application for abductive reasoning that has been applied in this study (Morgan, 2007). This paradigm was also well-suited for this research because it was essential to understand and accept that individuals have their unique interpretation of the situations and perceptions as pragmatic researcher. Hence to gain a clearer insight into the phenomenon being researched, the researcher relied on the external reality of the participants and chose explanations that best produce the desired outcomes (Parvaiz, Mufti and Wahab, 2016).

Furthermore, the rationale for adopting pragmatism links directly to the purpose and nature of the research problem being investigated (Creswell, 2003). In pragmatism, instead of being dominant, the research problem is viewed as an essential concern (Creswell, 2003). Thus, the adopted data collection methods (interview, questionnaires, observation and articulation/documentation, etc.), narratives (qualitative and quantitative), and the analysis (descriptive, factor, content, thematic and discourse, etc.) are deemed to be the most likely factors to provide a deep insight into the research problem (Creswell, 2003; Mackenzie & Knipe, 2006). Thus, pragmatism explicitly hails the foundations for the mixed method researcher.

Like others, this paradigm is also not criticism-free. When translating epistemological concerns into research methodology and deciding the research methods, pragmatism raises some methodological concerns. For instance, if a research problem has different layers, how can all the layers be measured or observed? Indeed, a critical strategy for inquiry would be to employ multiple methods, measures, researchers, and perspectives. However, this must be done reasonably and practically (Patton, 2002). As a result, studies employ diverse methodological combinations to address the research questions. For instance, some studies use intermixing of interviewing, observation, and document analysis, and some studies rely more on interviews rather than observations or vice versa (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019). Alternatively, critics of pragmatism have noted several practical challenges associated with identifying a socially situated research problem. For instance, Thompson (1997) pointed out the contextual, problem-centred nature of pragmatism that, according to the researcher, limits the paradigm's ability to identify and analyse structural social problems. Another important consideration is the aspect of pragmatism that is a part of a researcher's worldview and, therefore, can influence the way researchers conduct their project. This is important as not all research questions are fundamentally important, nor are the methodologies automatically appropriate. Ultimately, the researcher makes the choices and decides which question is essential and what methodology is suitable. Those choices are certainly influenced by the researcher's socio-political location, personal history, and belief system (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019).

Additionally, there are arguments that pragmatism should focus on methodology, as methodology is an area that connects abstract philosophical issues to actual mechanical methods. It has been emphasized that pragmatist researchers should study both methodology, which is related to research itself, and epistemology, which are the warranted beliefs that influence how we conduct our research. It is essential to focus on methodology as a tool to

connect the thoughts about knowledge rather than separating philosophical threads from the research design (Kaushik and Walsh, 2019).

Based on the above factors and the nature and objective of this study, it is sufficient to argue that this research will follow a mixed-method approach. The philosophical underpinning applied in this study is pragmatism

4.4 Research Approach

Research approaches are the procedures and plans for research that bridge steps from broad assumptions to detailed data collection methods, analysis, and interpretation (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2012). The plan here involves applying an appropriate approach that would comply with the philosophical underpinnings and further explain the reasoning for the research design and data collection methods embraced in this study. The researcher can then make informed decisions regarding their research project, identify the approach that would be well-suited based on the research aims and strategy being adopted, and utilise all the available resources and facilities to collect data (Sekaran and Bougie, 2010). The relationship between data collection and analysis and between theory and data can be discussed with the help of research approaches. Easterby-Smith et al. (2002) point out two approaches traditionally recognized in the framework of undertaking research. These are known as deductive and inductive approaches.

The deductive approach or deduction begins with a specific rule or a theory and goes on to examine and explain how the raw data supports that rule or theory (Reichert, 2007). The deductive approach is where the research strategy is designed to test a theory; a plausible hypothesis is suggested that hypothesis is then refined with observations and logical deduction (Rubin and Babbie, 2010). In contrast, an inductive approach or induction is based on the conception that a general law can be concluded based on numerous cases. The researcher uses

these cases to identify the pattern that formulates a general statement (Thornberg and Charmaz, 2014). Furthermore, an inductive approach is where the researcher initiates the study with observations, seeks patterns, and follows the data closely. It assists in revealing new understandings of the existing data (Reichertz, 2007).

In respect of data collection and analysis, deduction embraces a highly structured methodology and focuses on collecting quantitative data. The hypothesis deduced from the data is then used to gather data (Bryman and Bell, 2011, p. 11). Alternatively, induction involves generating theory based on observations (Gill and Johnson, 2010). This approach focuses on collecting qualitative data, and there is no requirement to test the hypothesis at any stage. Unlike deduction, this approach emphasizes the importance of understanding how humans perceive events and the context being researched (Neuman, 2003). However, both these approaches have their critics. The deductive approach has been criticized for lacking clarity regarding the formulation of hypothesis and the testing of theory (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2019). The research merely focuses on the prescribed theory and overlooks other external aspects of data. The induction approach has been questioned because there is insufficient empirical data to enable the theory generation (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2019).

This research will be using the third approach, which is a combination of both deductive and inductive approaches, also known as the abductive approach or abductive reasoning (Ho, 1994). This approach emphasizes on formal logic. This logic is divided into two categories: formal and informal logic. Formal types include symbolic logic, whereas the informal types include critical thinking (Ho, 1994). This approach keeps on shifting back and forth between deduction and induction (Suddaby, 2006). Abduction starts with observing the facts and then developing a theory that justifies the occurrences (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2019). Furthermore, this theory can also test and explain the plausible theories (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2019).

The researcher finds this approach well-suited for this research because it will collect quantitative and qualitative data. The collection of quantitative data is often related to deductive and qualitative data with inductive (Bryman and Bell, 2011, p. 11). This approach permits to move back and forth between the data, which will benefit this research in providing the best possible explanations on the phenomenon when comparing and analysing questionnaire and interview responses. Although this research will not be testing any theory or framework, this approach is still applicable. It does not eradicate the idea of using pre-existing theories and graphical depiction as a source of identification and interpretation of patterns (Flick, 2018).

4.5 Research Design

Research design is considered as a plan that a researcher takes upon to explain and answer research aim(s) and question(s) (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2012). It will cover the research strategies adopted, the sampling techniques used, and specify how sources are intended to collect and analyse the data. The research design conceptualised for this research is guided by this research's primary aims and the formulation of objectives to meet these aims.

The subjective nature of this research focuses on capturing and interpreting employee's indulgence and lived experiences on the phenomenon of organisational change and how it is/was managed. This study will be reflecting on a mixed-method research design that will aid this study by capitalizing on the strengths of each approach. The adoption of mixed-method research does not signify that the other two quantitative and qualitative designs are not good enough individually. The researcher suspects that adopting any one of these designs alone is insufficient to gather enough information that profoundly addresses the research questions. The objective representation of quantitative design (alone) will be unfavourable to this study due to the design's insignificance of comprehending process, or the meanings people attach to their actions (Easterby-Smith et al., 2002). However, this does not imply that quantitative methods

will be excluded from exploring the phenomenon, but rather it will be combined with qualitative methods for mixed-method design.

4.5.1 Mixed method design

According to Creswell (2007), mixed-method research is described as a research method designed with philosophical assumptions and methods of inquiry. As a methodology, it involves philosophical assumptions that guide the direction of collecting and analysing data and the mixture of qualitative and quantitative approaches in many phases in the research process. As a method, it focuses on collecting, analysing, and mixed quantitative and qualitative data in a single and series of studies. Its central premise is that the use of both approaches in combination provides a better understanding of research problems than either approach alone (Tashakkori and Teddlie, 2003). This research is using a mixture of data that includes numbers, graphs, statistical and text analysis

This study will be applying quantitative design, and its subsequent analysis will offer a general understanding of the research problem. However, it has to be considered that this research will not be testing any hypotheses or frameworks. Hence, the adoption of positivist philosophy with a quantitative design is because it is consistent, precise, and can be explained descriptively. On the other hand, qualitative methods will be used to understand the dynamics of organisational change and factors triggering resistance to change. Likewise, it will support this research by refining and explaining those statistical results by exploring participants' opinions in more depth (Ivankova, Creswell and Stick, 2006).

Creswell and Clark (2007) argue that quantitative and qualitative data offer a united understanding of a research problem. The analysis of this approach can strengthen the context of research in this area and widen its implications. Frechtling, Sharp, and Westat (1997) claim that it is beneficial to the researcher to use a mixed-method study to enhance the understanding of the research findings. Adding to this, the combination of both approaches in the research

design allows the researcher to simultaneously simplify results from a sample to a population to gather a deeper understanding of the phenomenon being examined (Hanson et al., 2005). To support this study, a sequential explanatory design (QUAN -> qual) is chosen. This sequential nature determines that a researcher first collects and analyses the quantitative data before proceeding to the qualitative data collection and analysis. Hence, the qualitative aspect falls into the second phase in the sequence, and it helps to explain and elaborate the quantitative results obtained in the first phase (Ivankova, Creswell and Stick, 2006). This is thought to be useful for this research. The questionnaire's data will help construct interview questions, thereby eliminating unobserved aspects and results from the quantitative study. Essential for a study where a phenomenon is being investigated that falls into the category of being subjective in nature, qualitative data will refine and explain the quantitative results in detail.

The strengths and weaknesses of using mixed methods design have been widely discussed in the literature (Creswell et al., 1996; Green and Caracelli, 1997; Moghaddam et al., 2003). Its advantages include straightforwardness and its ability to explore quantitative results thoroughly. This design can be beneficial when unexpected results arise from a quantitative study (Morse 1991). Even though this design is widely appreciated in the context of this study, it is still criticized for being time-consuming and lengthy in collecting and analysing both types of data (Ivankova, Creswell and Stick, 2006).

4.5.2 Research Strategies

In research, there are many different research strategies that can be used to design a research project. Some of these explained in this chapter include survey, case study, and focus groups. These strategies belong either to the deductive tradition or the inductive tradition, although as Saunders et al. (2012) emphasise, allocating strategies to one approach is unduly simplistic.

4.5.2.1 Survey

Survey research comprises a cross-sectional design where data(s) is primarily collected by a questionnaire or a structured interview on one or more cases (Bryman and Bell, 2011). These designs are applied to collect quantitative or quantifiable data connected with two or more variables (Bryman and Bell, 2011). This strategy is used in business research to answer what, who, where, and how questions. Therefore, the research that adopts survey design tends to be associated with deductive approach and uses exploratory and descriptive research (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2012).

The choice of the survey can be determined by the requirement of the research. For example, research can have a written survey, a verbal survey, or both. A written survey is where the data requires minimum available resources such as the staff, time cost and are best suited for extracting confidential information (Glasow, 2005). Written surveys may be distributed using either postal, electronic mail, or in-person to a group of respondents (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2016). Thus, written surveys allow the respondent the most significant latitude in pace and sequence of response (Glasow, 2005).

On the other hand, verbal surveys can help capture verbal inflection, gestures, and other body languages. A skilled researcher can obtain additional insights into the answers provided by observing the respondent's body language (Glasow, 2005). Thus, they are well suited to long or complicated questionnaires and for reaching the correct respondents.

A survey in research methods has been subjected to multiple weaknesses. It is observed that this design provokes biasness, either in the lack of response from intended participants or in the nature and accuracy of the responses that are received (Glasow, 2005). Other sources of error include the data collected via a survey is not likely to be as wide ranged as other strategies. For example, there is a limit to questions that a questionnaire can contain as the responses can

be repetitive. The questionnaire can be presumed tedious and time-consuming for the respondents (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2012).

4.5.2.2 Case Study

The case study approach has been widely accepted and implemented in business research, and the majority of the renowned research is preliminary based on this design (Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2007). A case study is defined as an in-depth inquiry into a topic or a researched phenomenon within its real-life setting (Yin, 2014). A case study research may refer to a person (e.g., an employee), a group (e.g., a work team), an organisation (e.g. a business), an association (e.g., a joint venture), a change process (e.g., restructuring a company), an event (e.g., annual general meeting) as well as many other types that can be referred to as case subjects (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2012). According to Kazdin (1982), the significant characteristics of case study are as follow:

- This design involves a thorough study of an individual, group, institution, or other levels that can be considered single units.
- The information is highly detailed, comprehensive, and typically reported in narrative form instead of the quantified scores on a dependent measure.
- Case study design attempts to convey various shades of the case that includes specific detailed context, unnecessary influences, and idiosyncratic details.
- The information that is examined within a case study can be archival or retrospective.

To clarify the structure of the case study design, it is often required to identify the nature of the case study strategy according to thorough research. Yin (2018) distinguishes between four case study strategies based on two dimensions: Single case versus multiple cases and Holistic case versus embedded case.

A single case is adopted purposely because it offers an opportunity to investigate an atypical or exclusive phenomenon that is not considered by many in terms of investigation (Saunders,

Thornhill and Lewis, 2012). It is when a case is unique and rare in its own researched context. On the other hand, multiple case studies are adopted when predicting similar results, and the findings are replicated across cases (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2012). Alternatively, a holistic case study is where a researcher decides to investigate an organisation that he/she may work in, and research is concerned with that organisation as a whole (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2019). Conversely, suppose research is being carried out within a single organisation, but the researcher may wish to examine different departments or units within that organisation. In that case, that case study will be considered as an embedded case study (Saunders, Thornhill and Lewis, 2019).

Choosing between the different case study designs largely depends upon the nature of one's research. The rationale for using a case study design is because it allows empirical investigation of a contemporary phenomenon being investigated in detail within a real-life context (Yin, 2009). Similarly, the design's flexibility when aligned with different methods. For instance, this design applies to both exploratory and explanatory research. It can also be used in mixed-method research as long as it justifies a particular researcher (Verner and Abdullah, 2012). Mainly for this research, a case study will permit mixed methods to address complicated research questions and gaps and gather a more prosperous and healthier range of evidence (Yin, 2015). Adding to this, the researcher will be opting for an embedded case study. This is because this type of case design will allow the researcher to investigate Himalayan Bank and gather information from different departments. The researcher was inclined towards the embedded case study because this medium can contribute successively towards theory and knowledge development by challenging, confirming, or expanding the theory (Yin, 2018).

4.5.3 Sampling

Sampling refers to the process, technique, and act of selecting a sample. A sample is justified as a fragment of a population that is selected to be investigated for a particular study (Bryman

and Bell, 2011). Likewise, sampling is described as: "The selection of specific data sources from which data are collected to address the research objectives" (Gentles et al 2015, p.1772). In this research, sampling techniques are applied when selecting the sample for both, questionnaire and interviews. The samples are selected or derived from the total population that the researcher intends to explore. Selecting a sample, the population needs to be represented in a meaningful way that can be justified when answering research questions and meeting objectives (Becker, 1998). According to Saunders et al. (2015), sampling is categorised into two main types: probability and non-probability. Probability samples are the gold standard in sampling methodology and ensure the generalisation of the study results to the target population. Selecting probability sampling means that each individual in the population has an equal chance of being selected in the study (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Quinlan (2011) outlines some standard probability sampling techniques: simple random sampling, systematic random sampling, stratified random sampling, and cluster sampling. In contrast, non-probability sampling is where the probability of each case being selected from the total population is unknown. Some units in this sampling are more likely to be selected than others. Some examples of non-probability sampling are convenience/purposive sampling, quota sampling, and snowball sampling (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

In the case of the survey strategy applied in this study, the questionnaire's sample was via non-probability purposive sampling. The researcher relied on her insights when selecting the participants for this study. Purposive sampling is most commonly used in research where participants meet the inclusion criteria for the particular study. The advantage of applying this sampling method is that they are easily applicable and less expensive. On the other hand, the disadvantage is that the bias variability and bias cannot be measured or controlled. Secondly, the data results cannot be generalised beyond the sample (Acharya et al., 2013). The rationale behind selecting this group of respondents is in line with Quinlan's (2011, p. 213) assertion that

the criterion for inclusion in the research is the participant's capacity to inform the research. The researcher targeted to receive around 10% responses of the targeted population of 830 employees (approx.). However, due to the sluggishness of the responses, 59 respondents were the maximum the researcher could gain of the total population who attempted the questionnaire. This strategy helps collect a more representative or comparative view of a population of interest, thus supporting transferability, or the ability to apply findings to the population at large (Krefting, 1991). For the questionnaire, the researcher targeted the employees from various departments and managerial levels and considered this approach useful in yielding diverse data. These participants were those who were available to fill out the survey from the total population of 830 employees of the Bank.

The interviews amongst key informants were conducted using criterion-based purposive sampling. The criteria strategy is commonly used in qualitative research to select a characteristic or group of characteristics known to vary within a population (Teddlie & Yu, 2007). The criteria for in-depth interview participants are to select 8 junior-level employees and 8 senior executives (as per their availability). It was essential to have a mix of employees who were willing to participate in the interview. The mix includes junior employees at operational and managerial employees in senior positions. Furthermore, it was also important to have participants from various departments such as HR, IT, compliance etc. The initial step was referring back to the survey responses and filtering out the employees who consented to be contacted for a further in-depth interview. Furthermore, stage-2 (in-depth) interviews were conducted to help the researcher gather data directly from the bank employees that would complement the gathered data via questionnaires.

4.6 Data Collection Methods Used for This Research

Neuman (2003) believes that every research investigation needs a suitable blend of approaches to collect and analyse the information with specific techniques. He further adds that the nature

of a research study influences the method adopted. Therefore, the methodology should complement the aims of the study. This research adopts a survey strategy involving distributing a questionnaire and an interview strategy whereby interviews were conducted with various participants amongst different managerial groups. The survey strategy is usually associated with quantitative research within a positivist paradigm. In contrast, interviews are connected to qualitative research within an interpretivist paradigm.

The data for this research is gathered from the Himalayan Bank Ltd. The initial interest of the researcher was to investigate this bank, which is one of the profitable commercial banks in Nepal (Naseer, 2019). However, as the research progressed, the researcher considered underlining the perspective on organisational change from a diverse pool of employees working in this bank. Employees at different hierarchal levels would tend to have different attitudes towards organisational change. These employees will help highlight how their bank implements affirmative strategies ensuring all key workers are a part of the change management process and approaches adopted to minimise uncertainty.

In terms of the key participants, this research focuses on all employees in general and those who were readily available for filling out the survey. This generalisation of employees is significant to gather data from different genders, ethnicities, management levels, and geographic locations. Once satisfactory responses were received, the researcher then shortlisted a small sample of employees from the targeted population who participated in the questionnaire for a further in-depth interview.

4.6.1 The use of Questionnaire in this Research

A questionnaire is defined as a list of questions or statements to which a person is asked to answer in writing though the answer may vary from a checkmark to a comprehensive written statement (Wiersma and Wiersma 1985). Saunders et al. (2015) write that using a survey is a popular and useful technique in social research. Using a questionnaire gives the researcher

more control over the research process. Thus, questionnaires provide a large amount of collected data from a sizeable population economically.

According to Sarantakos (2012), questionnaires have many advantages and disadvantages. This strategy allows trouble-free collection of data from a wide-spread population that can be easily explained, elaborated, understood, and compared (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Questionnaires are cheap when compared to other methods, and their results have a smaller chance of bias. On the other hand, the disadvantage includes the inability of the researcher to clarify the questions asked. Often the researcher cannot judge if the right person has answered the questions, and the reliability of their answers can be questioned. Likewise, attaining additional information once the questionnaire is sent is also tricky.

There are two types of questions in a questionnaire: structured or closed and unstructured or open questions. Structured questions have set responses for the respondents. These are either multiple choice or yes/no answers. This type of questionnaire is less time consuming and easy to fill out. The weakness with such a questionnaire is that it may force respondents to choose that may not reflect their opinions. In contrast, unstructured questions do not limit the respondents but allow them to express their opinions freely. The common weakness with such questionnaires is that these are time-consuming and difficult to analyse (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

4.6.2 Data Collection Methods Used in this Research - Stage 1

A pre-developed questionnaire on resistance to change has been implemented in this research (Oreg, 2017). This was mainly done to ensure the questions were reliable and certified. The resistance to change scale developed by Oreg (2003) fits well within the research being carried out, and the questions can be easily understood by the respondents (Foddy, 1994). The resistance to change scale consists of 17 questions that are narrowed into four intercorrelations. These are routine seeking, emotional reaction, short-term focus, and cognitive rigidity (Oreg,

2003). The pattern of the questionnaire is as followed; the first five questions fall under routine seeking, the next four under emotional reaction, the next four under short-term focus, followed by the last four falling under cognitive rigidity (Oreg, 2003). Adding to this, the resistance to change scale is a six-point Likert scale ranging from strongly disagree (disagree, inclined to disagree, inclined to agree, agree) to strongly agree (Oreg, 2003).

This questionnaire is suitable for this study because it undertakes the phenomenon of change and resistance with multidimensional concepts that cover behavioural, cognitive, and affective components (Piderit, 2000). All such are essential in understanding change management (Oreg, 2003). Furthermore, this scale helps understand resistance to change within an organisational setting and explains the aspect of resistance above and beyond any contextual causes (Oreg, 2003). A Likert scale allows for a collective approach to be established if there is any consistency amongst the different number of scale items when used together (Likert, 1932). The usage of Likert scales has been argued to be simpler and understanding among individuals, and the responses are more straightforward to code (Hasson and Arnetz, 2005). These scales are extensively pragmatic in research in psychology and behavioural sciences (Colquitt et al., 2009). The following include the key phases involved in the construction and execution of the questionnaire:

- The survey for this study is developed using Qualtrics. This platform is easily accessible, reliable, and resourceful with the data. The website comes with a defined guide for its users that is very helpful. The essential advantage of using Qualtrics is that it allowed the questions to be constructed accordingly to the research and its needs. The questions are allowed to be created in any type or form, such as multiple-choice, matrix tables, scales, text entries, etc. Furthermore, it also permits the researcher to adjust each question as per its responses' validation. Qualtrics helps them in modifying and creating various surveys that can be easily accessible from computers, tablets, mobile phones,

etc. A host of ethical approval is met before the survey is tested. The questionnaire is approved by the Director of Studies and the Ethics panel at the University. This is executed to comply with the universities' data protection guidelines of data protection and ethical requirement for research.

The questionnaire was sent via email to all the employees working in the Bank. 59 participants responded to the questionnaire, successfully. Hence, the data for 59 respondents is analysed in the next chapters.

- A short pilot study was undertaken to test the questionnaire's validity and the use of the questionnaire as an appropriate data collection method (Quinlan, 2011). For this study, the researcher conducted a pilot test amongst two females belonging to the banking industry. One of the respondents (A) is a current employee working for a bank in Pakistan, whereas the other respondent (B) is a former employee of a bank in the same country. The reason as to why these both were chosen is because of their similarity of the same profession compared with the actual respondents in the Nepalese Bank. The main aim is to ensure that the respondents understand the questions and their association with the research (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). They can answer them freely and can follow all the instructions accurately (Fink, 2013). After completing the pilot study, their responses were examined, and necessary changes were fixed.
- Questionnaires were sent via email. Web-based questionnaires are mainly delivered through a web link (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). The email or the web link is used to display the web link to the questionnaire and is addressed to the relevant employees useful in filling out the survey (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Similarly, the link was generated from Qualtrics that was copied and forwarded to the employees via their email. The advantages of using a web-based survey are that it

allows the participant sufficient time and ease in filling out the survey, unlike presenting the questionnaire in paper form (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). Similarly, such surveys are quicker to administer as they can be sent out to a more significant sample quickly than telephonic or phone-based surveys (Bryman and Bell, 2011). The disadvantage was the slow response rate instead of other types of questionnaires, especially when the research has a limited time frame (Bryman and Bell, 2011) and lack of IT access to employees.

- The researcher broadcasted a follow-up email to make sure that all participants have completed and submitted the survey. The survey link was deactivated once the majority of responses were obtained.

4.6.3 The Use of Interviews in Research

An interview design in business research is identified as a conversation between two or more people, during which a person asks a precise and unambiguous question and listens to the other person(s) talking (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). The person asking a question is known as an interviewer, whereas those who are answering are known as interviewees. By thorough and active listening, an interviewer can explore their point of interest and clarify the contextual meanings (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016).

Interviews can vary from being highly structured to being highly unstructured. Structured interviews are where the interviewer controls the interview procedure in an orderly manner, whereas unstructured interviews are conducted using a flexible approach (Hair, Page and Brunsveld, 2016). Structured interviews are also known as standardised interviews or a researcher-administered survey. These are applied in quantitative research methods within survey research (Adam and Kamuzora 2008).

Alternatively, an unstructured interview or in-depth interviews is where the questions are not prepared in advance but mainly evolved during the interview process (Quinlan, 2011). Here

the interview questions tend to be open-ended. The flow of communication between the interviewer and the interviewee is open and free. This allows further questions to be followed up by the interviewer throughout the interview process.

The final category of an interview is called the semi-structured interviews. This interview process entails an interviewer having a list of questions set before the interview on the particular topic this is being investigated. It is also known as the interview guide. Here the interviewees are allowed to answer as per their terms (Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill, 2016). The sequence of the questions can be varied and modified throughout the interview process.

For this study, the researcher will be using semi-structured in-depth interviews. The main advantage of semi-structured in-depth interviews used in this study was that it offered the researcher an opportunity to obtain rich information while using a small number of participants (Jensen, 2013) while helping to develop an understanding of the reality in the eyes of the participants (Collier, 1998).

4.6.4 Data Collection Methods Used in this Research - Stage 2

After completing the survey, the researcher moved on to stage two, the main qualitative data collection stage involving in-depth semi-structured interviews with key informants. In-depth interviews were conducted in this study with 18 key informants. These informants were chosen from various departments and managerial levels. Both the senior and junior levels employees were asked their set of questions that covered most of the pre-developed themes. The nature of this investigation is such that both qualitative and quantitative data are required to meet the objectives of this study. The interviews further fulfil the interpretivist aspect of this research and will produce qualitative data in line with the qualitative aspect of this research. The following include the key phases involved in the construction and execution of the in-depth interviews:

- The interview questions and their themes were based on the statistical findings of the survey. These questions were open-ended that permitted participants to contribute as much detailed information as they desire and allowed the researcher to dig deeper into understanding the phenomenon being researched. The questions were divided into two sets. One set was for the managers and senior employees, whereas the other set was for the junior employees. This helped the researcher to address key issues from both the sets individually.
- These interviews were carried out based on one-to-one participants via Skype. Skype interviews will allow the researcher to maintain a close relationship with the participants. Their body language, behaviour, and interpretations were observed thoroughly, and the phenomenon of change was investigated from their assessment and past experiences. Prior to the interview, the participants were sent an interview participation form and a consent form. The interviews only took place once all the participants read and signed their consent to participate in the study.
- To ensure that the participants clearly understand the questions, the researcher held two pilot interviews with the participants who did not take part in the actual set of semi-structured interviews (Quinlan, 2011, p. 273). The pilot interviews did not reveal any issues in respondents' understanding of the questions or themes, so it was decided to adopt the interview schedule as the second stage of data collection for the research. The researcher ensured that any questions or themes deemed sensitive by participants on the personal or professional note were avoided.

4.7 Ethical Issues

Ethics are one of the integral parts when undertaking research. The researcher's responsibility is to be highly ethical when pursuing their research strategies and approaches to the subject being studied alongside the participants or respondents (McMillan and Schumacher, 2014). It

is of utmost importance for the researcher to gain permissible access before collecting data, ensuring never to cause any harm, and continuously maintaining privacy and confidentiality (Punch, 1994). In principle, it is strictly stressed that an investigation cannot be conducted as a matter of right. Before research, consent must be requested, and the investigator must prove that their research is worthy of pursuing (Cohen et al. (2013).

Initially, the researcher was a little doubtful in gaining access to data collection in Himalayan Bank. However, the researcher had previously carried out an investigation in the same bank for her master's degree. Because of the familiarity, the researcher was permitted to conduct the first stage of research.

Throughout the process of data collection, the researcher had to be cautious and sensitive towards the employee's feelings concerning the phenomenon and the contextual nature of the questions being inquired. It was imperative for the researcher to ensure every participant was aware of the confidentiality and the feasibility of opting out of the research at any point if it was affecting their comfort level. During the survey, respondents were asked to be contacted for an in-depth interview for the future. Those who agreed gave out their emails, which later assisted in generating the sample for in-depth interviews.

The University of the West of Scotland (UWS), where the researcher is undertaking her doctorate, has a robust framework in place for ethical approval. UWS does not permit any research to commence until it has been approved through its peer-reviewed ethical approval process. The ethical approval process is regularly evaluated and revised in line with good practice recommendations for the conduct of scholarly research and any legal requirements such as the new law on data protection (GDPR regulations). The ethical approval process takes full knowledge of issues such as confidentiality, anonymity, data protection, and consent.

The initial part of this process involves providing would-be participants with a researcher's participant information sheet. This sheet highlights the purpose of the research, including the

study's aim and objectives. It underlines the voluntary nature of the research and the option to withdraw participation at any time. It also sets out the level and nature of involvement required from participants (e.g., to complete a survey or take part in an interview), why they have been invited to take part and confirmation that participants will not be exposed to any physical, psychological or legal risk or harm. This is all explained thoroughly in the participation/consent forms and on call (face to face) to all the interviewees. Only if the participants have indicated their willingness to participate, they are asked to sign a consent form and, where relevant, their consent to be video/audio recorded. It is also explained to would-be participants what will happen to data collected and how it will be managed, including how it will be stored, protected, used, and disposed of. Any questions from the participants regarding the study are answered before the interview.

In this research, a full application for ethical approval was submitted by the researcher. The researcher commenced working on the data collection once the application was approved. Participant information sheets were emailed to all the participants only once they were all signed and received back, the researcher mailed the online link of the survey to the participants. As a part of the ethical process, all the would-be participants were assured that care would be taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity and that data collected would be managed in such a way as to ensure that the data and participants' identity would not be disclosed to any unauthorized party.

In terms of ethics and data management, all data collected and captured was stored securely and out of the reach of any unauthorized party. UWS is registered with the Information Commissioner's Office who implements the Data Protection Act 1998. All personal data on participants are processed under the provisions of this act. Following recent legislation, all data on participants will now be processed according to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

4.8 Data Analysis

Data analysis includes ways of working with information (data) to support the aims, plans, and goals of the study being investigated (Richmond, 2006). Academics argue it is essential to see data analysis as part of a process. This signifies that data analysis involves goals, relationships; decision making; and ideas, in addition to working with the actual data itself. The "process" is elaborated as piecing together data, shedding light on the invisible obvious, recognising significant from the insignificant data, thereby linking unrelated facts logically (Moore et al. 2012).

For this research, two data sets are collected: the data is from a questionnaire and interview. For the questionnaire, a survey software known as Qualtrics was used to develop and analyse the questionnaire responses. This generated descriptive statistics that were used to describe the data gathered. The descriptive statistics generated were mainly frequencies and percentages and were illustrated via tables and graphs (Zikmund et al., 2010).

This research did not invest further in analysing the quantitative data statistically. This is because of the exploratory nature of the aim and objectives. The data gathered did not permit adopting a complex approach in the analysis that would be time-consuming and not yield anything of significant value instead of descriptive analysis. Once all the results were received and complied with, data from Qualtrics was transferred to Microsoft Excel into a spreadsheet. Different spreadsheets were created, and data was distributed amongst each sheet using demographic factors such as gender, age bands, and managerial positions. Next, the numerical data was formulated into bar-charts, bar- graphs, histograms, and pie charts. All of the graphical representation was done using Excel. Once all the graphs were constructed, the researcher analysed different charts and graphs individually. The data is narrated into changing trends and patterns, mean, mode, and occurrences. The researcher believed that descriptive statistics would help in presenting the quantitative data in a manageable form. Hence, these type of

statistics assists in simplifying extensive complex data into a more straightforward summary (Trochim, 2020)

The second stage of data collection involves collecting qualitative data. This comprised of in-depth interviews that were conducted via Skype. Each interview session was recorded using the Skype recording feature. This feature supports recording the interviews directly and saves them in the iCloud for future reference. The researcher observed the behaviours' signals and gestures of the interviews and how they respond to specific questions like adapting to change and managing resistance. These actions were also handwritten during the interview session and used later in the analysis. The interview recordings from the iCloud were transferred to the researcher's password-protected drop-box. The digital files were played back, and each interview was transcribed using all the content and handwritten notes.

The researcher applied thematic analysis to analyse the interview data. The analysis was done in the following steps: the first stage was to familiarise and understand the depth and breadth of the interview recordings and the hand-written notes. The second stage consisted of the description of data. This is where the researcher moved from the unstructured data to developing ideas on what's going on in the data sets via excel. Once the data was coded and collated, the researcher used the coded data and extracted them into relevant themes that were then labelled and categorised as per the study's requirements. Lastly, the themes were used to write up the final analysis for the interview data. Findings from both; questionnaire and interviews are discussed in detail in chapter 5

4.9 Bias and Limitations of the Methodological Approach

The manifestation of any bias is essential to consider when conducting research. Anything that has the ability to compromise or contaminate the study is considered as research bias (Quinlan, 2011). For example, values that reflect personal beliefs or the researcher's feelings can introduce bias into the research. Concerning this research, the researcher has given her best to

conduct this research with an open mind and not allow her personal feeling and enthusiasm (for this phenomenon) to be transmitted to this research. Somewhat familiarised with the bank and the staff members, the researcher, did not allow her conscience and judgment to be clouded by previous experiences and personal relations.

The researcher estimated the questionnaire should have gained more responses. In terms of the sample size, the ideal assumption was 10% that should have ranged between 80-100 employees. However, the survey responses for this study ceased at 63 respondents out of which 59 completed the questionnaire. All necessary steps were taken to ensure participants are aware of their contribution to this study. Constant reminders were sent out for the non-participants to participate in the survey. Thus, the researcher considers more responses would have generated more diversified data for analysis.

The researcher opted for a sampling strategy that she believed was well-suited and precise for both the survey and interview. Due to the nature of rigor of the bank, purposive sampling was deemed to fit best with this study. This can also be considered as a delimitation of this case study. For the survey, this sampling criterion was explicit to involve all levels of personals involved in change (current or past) within the bank. For interviews, participant selection was varied between employees to gain diverse perspectives. Likewise, in terms of biasness from respondents, the researcher ensured all the participants are well aware of the study's nature, consented to be a part of the investigation, and were presented with the significance of ethical anonymity. All measures will be taken to certify honest responses are returned from surveys and interviews.

Through-out this investigation, the researcher has reflected continuously upon her relationship within the research area and how her views may impact and affect the process of conducting research. Naturally, individuals can potentially bring their own biases to a research project. However, it is up to them to ensure that they are competent in counteracting these biases and

not allow those to influence their research, a point supported by Saunders et al. (2012, p. 292) and Bryman and Bell (2011, p. 30).

4.10 Reliability and Validity

"Reliability and validity are tools of an essentially positivist epistemology." (Watling, as cited in Winter, 200, p. 7)

The notions of reliability and validity are argued to be associated with sole quantitative research paradigms and are not as straight forward in qualitative research paradigms. (Bashir et al., 2009). Winter (2000) agrees with this argument and states that quantitative researchers attempt to disassociate themselves as much as possible from the research process. In contrast, qualitative researchers embrace their involvement in their research. Nevertheless, it is certainly expected that both qualitative and quantitative researchers demonstrate that their studies are credible (Patton, 2011; Wilson, 2010; Bryman, 2012; Saunders et al., 2012). In other words, research reliability and validity refer to show that the research is credible. Joppe (2000) defines reliability as: The extent to which results are consistent over time and an accurate representation of the total population under study is referred to as reliability. If the results of a study can be reproduced under a similar methodology, then the research instrument is considered to be reliable (p. 1).

For the survey, this study employed a pre-developed scale by Oreg (2003) known as the resistance to change scale (RTC). The researcher is confident of the scale's reliability is high because many studies on organisational change and resistance (before this) have incorporated the scale for collecting data. There is no reason to suggest otherwise as this scale was carefully studied and applied to this study. A pilot study was also conducted to monitor the fitness of this scale for this investigation.

We must also acknowledge that the question of reliability is interpreted differently by social constructionists and interpretivists, and qualitative measures such as interviews do not need to be reliable in the positivist sense (Collis and Hussey, 2014). Instead, the emphasis is more on establishing protocols and procedures that establish the authenticity of the findings (Collis and Hussey, 2014). In the case of this research, clear protocols were implemented at every stage of the data collection to ensure the research's reliability.

The research also needs to reflect on the aspect of validity. Joppe (2000) provides the following explanation of validity: validity determines whether the research truly measures which it was intended to measure or how truthful the research results are. In other words, does the research instrument allow you to hit "the bull's eye" of your research object? Researchers generally determine validity by asking a series of questions and will often look for the answers in others' research (p. 1).

In terms of validity and questionnaire, a pre-developed resistance to change scale is adopted, as explained earlier. The fact that the scale is not tailored to correspond to any specific type of change predicted resistance behaviour across various settings demonstrates its value in explaining resistances above and beyond any contextual causes. The neutrality of this scale allows different subscales on the change to be highlighted in a different context. Following the theoretical content further demonstrates the validity of the scale and the extent of its relevance. Additionally, the survey was also pilot tested. It is essential to pilot test a survey questionnaire because it improves the validity of gathering and collecting data using this design (Saunders et al., 2012, p. 394). In terms of validity and interviews, the questions were crafted explicitly for this study. They considered the critical components of the questionnaire that will be looked at in detail. Hence, these questions will be used to ensure they retrieve measurable responses linked to this study's aims and objectives, and the results of those are drawn from the collected data (Saunders et al., 2012).

When talking about validity, light must be shed on the generalisation of results. This means the collected data results can be generalised beyond the particular context of a study (Bryman and Bell 2011). However, some limited generalisation of data can be achieved from the themes emerging from the interviews' results (Veal, 2006). Bryman and Bell (2011) argue that themes can provide a comprehensive description that can be used to transfer possible data to additional contexts. Adding to this, qualitative findings tend to be oriented to the contextual uniqueness and significance of the social context studied (Bryman and Bell, 2011).

In contrast, quantitative research allows and expects the researcher to make generalisations to a broader population. The survey questionnaire is the primary data collection strategy opted in this study that yielded quantitative and qualitative results. The aims were to gauge the perception held by Himalayan bank employees on issues like organisational change. However, this questionnaire applies to various studies and genres, so it can be argued that the questionnaire can be generalised (in its application to different studies), but the findings cannot. For example, the general public or employees from other banks may not share the same feelings and opinions about the sample population for this specific investigation.

4.11 Conclusion

Research methods are crucial since the validity of the results depends upon them. This chapter provides justifications for adopting methodological choices such as research strategies, frameworks, and design used in this study. This study follows a pragmatistic approach in terms of research philosophy, which allows researchers to delve deeper into the human experiences on the phenomenon being researched. This was essential for this study because knowledge and reality are based on beliefs and habits that are socially constructed. The study's aim and objectives influenced the decision to implement a mixed-method approach and utilise an abductive approach. Likewise, the use of quantitative data collection methods such as a survey

questionnaire and qualitative methods in the form of semi-structured in-depth interviews allowed the investigating issue to be explored and examined from more than one perspective. As discussed above, the survey questionnaire consisted of a Likert scale that gave a generic understanding of participant's views on change and resistance to change. Subsequently, the open-ended and semi-structured questions for the interview assisted the researcher in providing valuable data on employee's and senior management's perceptions on the Bank monitoring and implementing desired change policies. The researcher would like to stress that due to the time constraints, this study could not get the desired participant response for the survey. The obtained results and findings from the different data collection instruments used in the research will be presented and further explored in the next chapter.

Chapter 5 – Survey Findings

5.1 Introduction

To make it easier to digest the findings from the fieldwork carried out, the findings are presented across two chapters. This chapter focuses on presenting the results from the survey questionnaire undertaken with the employees working in Himalayan Bank. In the next chapter of the thesis – the second of the finding's chapters - the findings from the primary data collected via interviews with key participants and interviewees are presented.

The questionnaire used in this research is based on the multidimensional concept presented by Oreg (2003), described as 'dispositional resistance to change' (RTC). The concept helps record individuals' inherent tendency to resist change: while some individuals are more open and adaptive to change than others who avoid them. This scale includes four dimensions: routine seeking, emotional reaction, short-term focus, and cognitive rigidity. These four dimensions of this scale (RTC) have been operationalised through the questionnaire using 17 questions.

Change is ambiguous and, individuals react to it differently in their work or personal surroundings. Hence, this scale is well-suited for this research because it helps the researcher understand the individual differences towards change, their tendency to resist and devalue change, generally. This scale also helps the researcher identify those individuals and recognize their personality and characteristics that drive such resistance.

This survey is constructed using Qualtrics. The survey was then sent to all the participants via an email link that was generated through the same platform. For developing a survey questionnaire, this was considered a secure medium instead of the other platforms available. Furthermore, Qualtrics allowed the researcher to modify details such as the question's design and the format, and the research requirements. Apart from the 17- pre-set questions from the (RTC) scale, the survey also comprises seven demographic questions such as – gender, age,

ethnicity, educational qualification, length of service, current position, and national base (Table 4.1). These demographic factors helped the researcher understand the professional profile of the participants who filled out the survey. The full description of the survey development is presented in Chapter 3. A total of 60 participants completed the questionnaire. Hence, all of their responses are counted in this study. Due to this research's nature, it was essential to get a diverse pool of employees to fill out the survey. This was mandatory to gather diverse information on this phenomenon from the employees working in different departments, further enabling the researcher to cross-compare their views.

These employees work in different departments and sectors of Himalayan Bank and are also at diverse seniority positions such as junior level, middle managers, and senior executives.

Full details of the methods, processes, and protocols used to collect the data have been provided in the methodology chapter. As a reminder, this study seeks to explore and examine employees' insights on change and resistance to organisational change in Himalayan Bank Ltd. The research seeks to answer the following questions:

- RQ1: What nature of organisational change has occurred at this bank?
- RQ2: What are the perceptions of organisational change amongst employees?
- RQ3: What are the factors contributing towards resistance among employees?
- RQ4: What are the organisational strategies implemented to achieve the desired change?

Table 5.1 Demographic Profile of Survey Respondents

Demographic Questions		% Responses
Gender	Male	78%
	Female	22%
Age	18 - 24	3%
	25 - 24	26%
	35 - 34	35%
	45 - 54	26%
	55- 64	9%
Length of Service	0 to 1 Year	3%
	2 to 5 Years	5%
	6 to 10 Years	26%
	10+ Years	65%
Current Position	Junior Level	15%
	Middle Management	57%
	Upper Management	12%
	Senior Executive	15%

5.2 Findings from the Survey

In this section the results from the questionnaire are reported. The findings will be sub-divided into four themes based on the RTC scale referred above. The questions asked were linked to the elements of the RTC scale as follows:

- Routine Seeking: Items 1-5 questions
- Emotional Reaction: Items 6-9 questions
- Short-term Focus: Items 10-13 questions
- Cognitive Rigidity: Items 14-17 questions

In presenting the results, the focus is on the overall results across the whole sample. As stated above, the details behind the mechanics of the administration of the questionnaire have already been provided in chapter 3. In summary, the questionnaire was distributed to the employees working in various departments of Himalayan Bank in Nepal. A total of 59 respondents completed the questionnaire. Of those, 57% are middle managers, 12% of senior executives, and 12% are junior employees.

The questionnaire consisted of 17 closed-ended questions. Respondents are asked to rate the extent to which they agree with each item using a six-point Likert Scale. These points range from 1 (strongly disagree) to 6 (strongly disagree). The Y-axis presents the percentage and, the X-axis presents the 17 questions. The figure shows the percentage of the responses that the participants chose amongst the 6 Likert scale points.

The responses to the close-ended questions such as the RTC scale are imperative given the research topic's nature. They allow the researcher to analyze the questions statistically and descriptively. Moreover, in comparative studies, the answers from various respondents are easy to be compared and analysed.

The next section will highlight the four themes that are mentioned above using their respective questions in detail

5.2.1 Routine Seeking

Routine seeking (RS) falls under the behavioural components of the resistance to change. In an individualistic context, it is considered as people or individuals preferring stability over novelty. Mostly, the individuals have varying degrees of dependencies for routine. Although it is often necessary for individuals in organisations to adhere to routines, the introduction of change in terms of structure, policies, and culture led them to oppose the idea. This theme explains the individual behaviour by including factors like an individual's reluctance to abandon old habits while inclining low stimulation levels. The questions under this theme are as follows:

1. I generally considered changes to be a negative thing.
2. I'll take a routine day over a day full of unexpected events any time.
3. I like to do the same old things rather than try new and different ones.
4. Whenever my life forms a stable routine, I look for ways to change it.
5. I'd rather be bored than surprised.

These questions are the related to Routine Seeking and the results to these particular questions are reported in this section.

Figure 5.1 – Responses to whether changes are a negative thing

Figure depicts the responses of individuals on whether they felt changes to be a negative thing. Eighty percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree. Twelve percent of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 2% of individual responded to inclined to agree followed by 7% of individuals who responded to agree.

Figure 5.2– Responses of individuals on taking a routine day over a day full of unexpected events

Figure depicts the responses of individuals whether they would take a routine day over a day full of unexpected events any time. Thirty seven percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree. Fifteen percent of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 20% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 27% of individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree.

Figure 5.3 – Responses of individuals on doing the same old things rather than try new and different ones

Figure displays the responses of individuals on doing the same old things rather than try new and different ones. Seventy eight percent of individuals responded to as strongly disagree and disagree, 12% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 5% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 5% of individuals who responded to agree.

Figure 5.4 – Responses of individuals when their life forms a stable routine, they look for ways to change it

Figure demonstrates a mixture of responses of individuals on changing their life when it forms a stable routine. Nineteen percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 8% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 14% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 59% of individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree.

Figure 5.5 – Responses to whether the individuals rather be bored than surprised

Figure depicts a mixture of responses of individuals who would rather be bored than surprised. Sixty one percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 7% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 17% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 15% of individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree.

5.2.2 Emotional Reaction

Emotional reaction (ER) falls under the affective component of resistance to change. When changes are imposed on individuals in an organisational setting, there is a common manifestation of stress and uncertainty by an individual in response to the imposed change. This theme highlights the extent to which individuals show or experience discomfort, anxiety, and lack of interest when changes are being carried out around their professional and personal setting. This theme explains the emotional factors triggering resistance that includes factors like psychological resilience and an individual's reluctance to lose control. Furthermore, resistance is observed as an action of individuals to regain or establish control.

The questions under this theme are as follows:

6. If I were to be informed that there's going to be a significant change regarding the way things are done at work, I would probably feel stressed.
7. When I am informed of a change of plans, I tense up a bit.
8. When things don't go according to plans, it stresses me out.
9. If my boss changed the performance evaluation criteria, it would probably make me feel uncomfortable even if I thought I'd do just as well without having to do extra work.

These questions are related to Emotional Reaction and the results to these particular questions are reported in this section.

Figure 5.6 – Responses whether individuals would feel stressed if they were to be informed that there's going to be a significant change regarding the way things are done at work

Figure displays the responses of participants on being stressed if they were to be informed that there's going to be a significant change regarding the way things are done at work. Seventy percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 7% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree, whereas 12% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 12% of individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree.

Figure 5.7 – Responses of individuals feeling tense when informed of a change of plans

Figure displays the responses of individuals feeling tense when informed of a change of plans. Forty five percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree. Both inclined to disagree and agree shows a mixture of responses of 20% respectively followed by 14% of individuals who responded to agree.

Figure 5.8 – Responses of individual’s feeling stressed when things don’t go according to plans

Figure depicts a mixture of responses of individuals on feeling stressed When things don't go according to plans. Twenty percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree. Twelve percent of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 29% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 39% of individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree.

Figure 5.9 – Responses to whether changing the performance evaluation criteria would make individual’s feel uncomfortable even if they thought they would do just as well without having to do extra work.

Figure displays a mixture of responses of individuals feeling uncomfortable if their Boss changed the performance evaluation criteria. Fifty three percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 15% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 10% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 22% of individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree.

5.2.3 Short-term Focus

Short-term focus (SF) falls under the effective component of resistance to change. Short-term focus involves the extent to which individual stress upon and are preoccupied with short-term inconveniences instead of the potential long-term benefit he/she might gain from the change. Hence, an individual's hesitance towards change rises despite an individual's awareness of the future benefits of the change. Some individuals can foresee and focus on the long-term benefits of the change, whereas others who oppose the idea of change tend to strain on the short-term hassles that are a part of the change process. This theme helps to explain individuals' effective actions by including factors like intolerance for the adjustment involved in change and reluctant to lose control.

The questions under this theme are as follows:

10. Changing plans seems like a real hassle to me.
11. Often, I feel a bit uncomfortable even about changes that may potentially improve my life.
12. When someone pressures me to change something, I tend to resist it even if I think the change may ultimately benefit me.
13. I sometimes find myself avoiding changes that I know will be good for me.

These questions are the related to Short-term Focus and the results to these particular questions are reported in this section.

Figure 5.10 – Responses to whether Changing plans is like a real hassle to individuals

Figure displays a mixture of responses of individuals who consider changing plans like a real hassle. Forty one percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 17% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 20% individuals responded to inclined to agree followed 22% individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree.

Figure 5.11 – Responses whether individual’s Often feel a bit uncomfortable even about changes that may potentially improve their life

Figure displays a mixture of responses of individuals who often feel a bit uncomfortable even about changes that may potentially improve their life. Fifty percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 29% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 8% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 14% of individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree.

Figure 5.12 – Responses to individuals resisting change even if they think that change may ultimately benefit them

Figure presents the responses of individuals resisting changes even if they think the change may ultimately benefit them. Fifty three percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 17% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 12% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 19% of individuals who responded to agree.

Figure 5.13– Responses to whether individuals sometimes avoiding changes that they know will be good for them

Figure displays the responses of individuals who sometimes find themselves avoiding changes that they know will be good for them. Fifty four percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 12% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 19% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 15% of individuals responded to agree.

5.2.4 Cognitive Rigidity

Cognitive rigidity (CR) falls under the cognitive component of resistance to change. When change policies are being proposed or implemented, some individuals suffer from inflexibility in thinking and difficulty accepting change and new ideas. The last factor involves short-term thinking, which captures an individual's opposing view or stubbornness to consider new ideas as an irrational component, regardless of the long-term benefits of the change. This theme helps to explain the ease and frequency with which individuals change their minds and perceptions.

The questions under this theme are as follows:

14. I often change my mind.
15. I don't change my mind easily.
16. Once I've come to a conclusion, I'm not likely to change my mind.
17. My views are very consistent over time.

These questions are related to Cognitive Rigidity and the results to these particular questions are reported in this section.

Figure 5.14 – Responses of individuals who often change their mind

Figure displays the responses of individuals who often change their minds. Thirty six percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 22% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 24% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 19% of individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree

Figure 5.15 – Response of individuals who don't change their mind easily

Figure displays a mixture of responses of individuals who don't change their mind easily. Twenty seven percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 24% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 14% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 35% of individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree.

Figure 5.16 – Responses of individuals who have come to a conclusion, are not likely to change their mind

Figure displays a mixture of responses of individuals who are not likely to change their mind once they have come to a conclusion. Twenty one percent of individual responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 7% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 25% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 48% of individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree.

Figure 5.17 – Responses of individuals views being very consistent over time

Figure displays the responses of individuals who have views that are very consistent over time. Fifteen percent of individuals responded to strongly disagree and disagree, 10% of individuals responded to inclined to disagree whereas 20% of individuals responded to inclined to agree followed by 54% of individuals who responded to agree and strongly agree.

5.3 Summary of Key Findings Emerging from the Questionnaire

This chapter has presented the findings generated by the survey questionnaire that was undertaken by Himalayan Bank employees working in Nepal. Both male and female employees from different departments completed the online survey. The purpose of this section is to list the key findings that emerged from the questionnaire findings. The themes that emerged from the overall survey findings are summarised as follows:

- Routine seeking behaviour where individuals prefer predictable and conventional tasks and environment. The participants' responses are a mixture between disagree and agree. It can be argued that a high percentage of individuals (92%) do not consider changes to be negative. Furthermore, individuals are also willing to try different routines and look forward to changes rather than being bored with their work.
- Emotional reaction of participants that is when individuals experience discomfort and anxiety regarding the changes that are imposed on them. The responses are a mixture between disagree and agree. Responses show that individuals do not feel stress when they are evaluated differently at work or when they are informed of any changes to be implemented. However, there is a high percentage of individuals (68%) who do feel stressed when things don't go according to plan.
- Short-term focus of participants at work is when individuals do not consider the benefits of the changes rather than focus on the inconvenience that change may cause. The most common response under this theme is to disagree. The results display those participants do not resist and avoid changes. Furthermore, changing plans and procedures are neither considered to be stressful or a hassle.

- Cognitive rigidity is the inability of participants in accepting changes and adapting to new perspectives, methods, and situations. The responses are a mixture of disagree and agree. Half of the participants agree to change their minds whereas the other half disagree with changing their minds easily. Furthermore, a popular response from the participants is to agree on having firm and consistent opinions and options that are not likely to alter easily.

Besides, some points were derived from the analysis based on RTC questions and current position, focusing on the junior level participants and the senior executives. These are as follows:

- For RTC - 4 a large percentage of junior level participants responded to agree and strongly agree, whilst the senior executives responded towards strongly disagree and agree.
- For RTC -7 the majority of the junior level participants responded to disagree whereas the senior executives have a mix of responses amongst agree and disagree.
- For RTC -10 the most common response by junior level participants is disagree whereas the most common response from the senior executives is to agree.
- For RTC -16 the highest percentage of response by the junior level participants is agree whilst the highest response by the senior executive on this question is disagree.
- The rest of the questions have similar responses. The most common response amongst junior and senior participants (for the overall survey) is disagree.

5.4 Conclusion

This chapter presents the results and the findings that were generated by conducting the first stage of the fieldwork for this thesis. This involved the administration of a survey questionnaire to the Himalayan Bank (HBL) employees across various locations. The primary focus was on the employees working for HBL in Nepal.

The findings from the overall sample who completed the questionnaire suggested that the majority of the participants do not consider a change or changes to be negative. Furthermore, change is also not considered as stressful and like a hassle as more than 50% of the participants negated such views. From the overall scale, it was observed that the most common response from the participants were towards strongly disagree and disagree. On the other hand, a huge majority of the participants agreed to prefer having changing routines when their current practices are monotonous and stable. The majority of the participants disagree with hesitance associate with change and changing plans; however, there is an overwhelming view of agreement amongst the participants that when their things don't go according to plan, it causes them stress and anxiety. From observing the survey results, it is understood that change is not as negatively perceived by the participants as projected. The demographic questions/factors helped in gaining a better insight into the participants' views regarding the phenomenon of organisational change and resistance. Furthermore, these factors allowed the researcher to analyze the survey findings and see if there are any variations by demographic factors such as length of service and current position.

5.5 Summary of Key Findings and Research Objectives

The table 5.2 below summarizes the key findings in relation to the research objectives:

Research Objectives	Survey Findings
To identify the nature of organisational change that has occurred at the Bank	The survey findings could not conclude much on this objective as most of the questions on the RTC scale focus on the viewpoints and characteristics of the employees undergoing and managing change.
To gauge the perception of change amongst employees	A high majority of participants (92%) do not contemplate change as a negative thing and are willing to try new adjustments at work. The findings also depict that some participants do not resist and avoid the required and desired changes.
To identify factors contributing to resistance to change amongst employees	A significant proportion (68%) of employees discarded the issue of resistance and responded with not resisting and avoiding changes. In contrast, other participants' responses depict that changing plans at work is considered a hassle and sudden imposition of change policies causes stress. Thus, it can be argued that such factors do constitute resistance amongst the Bank employees.
To establish organisational strategies implemented to achieve desired changes	The survey findings could not conclude much on this objective as most of the questions on the RTC scale focus on the viewpoints and characteristics of the employees undergoing and managing change. On the other hand, this objective is thoroughly investigated with the interview participants.

The next chapter will be presenting the findings from stage two of the data collection phase that involves interviews with key participants. These are the junior level and the senior executives, working in Himalayan Bank in Nepal.

Chapter 6 – Interview Findings

6.1 Introduction

In this chapter, the focus is on presenting the results from stage two of the data collections phases which involved two sets of interviews. One set is with the senior executives and the other set with the junior level employees. The reason for separating these two sets is to understand the perceptions of employees from different working experiences and backgrounds in the Bank. Furthermore, the data from these interviews supplement the data gathered via the questionnaire. After completing stage one of the data collection phase – the survey questionnaire – stage two involved a series of in-depth interviews with key participants of Himalayan Bank. Full details of the methods, processes and protocols used to collect the data have been provided in the methodology chapter. Once the findings from the two sets of interviews are reported, they will be further cross analysed with the quantitative data set in detail in the next chapter.

The two sets of interviews represent the application of the qualitative aspect to this research. Given the nature of the topic and the objectives of this research, the collection of qualitative data was vital in order to fully achieve the aim of this research. King (2004) highlights the view that qualitative research is extremely important when gathering descriptions of real world of an interviewee with respect to interpreting the meaning of the described phenomenon. In this case, it allows the participants to report their views and stories of organisational change and resistance within the context of their personal values and experiences of working in Himalayan Bank.

As discussed in chapter 3, using more than one approach to address the research question allowed the researcher the opportunity to explore the perceptions of those who have a relationship to or interest in the topic area.

6.2 Findings from Interviews

This section presents the finding from in-depth interviews with employees and managers of Himalayan Bank. The term interviewees are used throughout this chapter. The finding of these interviews is based on the key themes that were explored in the interview guide (See appendix). In total 16 individuals took part in the interviews. These 16 participants are divided into two main categories of junior employees and senior executives. Eight are Senior executives and 8 are Junior Level Employees. The 8 senior executives also include middle level managers. Full details of interviewees and the reason for their inclusion (is presented in the appendix table. Quotes used in this chapter highlight the responses from individual interviewees according to their job titles or roles in Himalayan Bank. In order to comply with the ethical requirements of this project the names of interviewees are not revealed. Instead, interviewees are assigned a number to distinguish between them. This can be observed in table 6.1 and 6.2.

Table 6.1 Demographics of Senior Interviewees

Interviewee	Job title of Senior Executive
1	Human Resource Department Head
2	Senior Manager in Compliance Department
3	Manager in compliance Department
4	Senior Manager in Human Resource Department
5	Manager in Audit and Inspection Department
6	Manager in Information Technology Department
7	Manager in Human Resource Department
8	Senior Officer in General Administration Department

Table 6.2 Demographics of Junior Interviewees

Interviewee	Job title of Junior level employees
1	Supervisor in Human Resource Department
2	Training and Development Officer
3	Security Analyst in Information Technology Department
4	Supervisor in the Card Centre/Department
5	Junior Assistant in Card Centre/Department
6	Senior Assistant in Internal Audit Department
7	Junior Assistant in Operations
8	Auditor in the internal Audit Department

6.2 Findings from interviewees with senior executives

6.2.1 Views on Organisational Change

All the senior executives believed that organisational change means changing the current business processes and procedures to better the organisation. Although there was quite a diverse understanding of this phenomenon, some talked about changing their departmental practices, and the others focused on the overall change(s) in the Bank. Among the eight interviewees, most views on organisational change ranged from leadership/management change, change in internal and external factors (such as changes in job roles, structures, and technology) to cultural changes these can be seen from the following quotes:

“Organisational change is the changes that are happening over a period of time it can be a succession or leader who is in charge or the change on the top of the pinnacle and who is looking at the things from a different perspective and changes in our institution like changing behaviour, mindset of people ...to change with the change” (Interviewee 1: Human Resource Department Head).

“Organisational change is a gradual process that comes in every organisation but that is mainly influenced by internal and external factors. External factors such as rules and regulations set by the government, central Bank or other regulatory body...internal changes such change in structure, change in mission and vision of board, change in composition of management and demand of staff that, is which brings change in organisation” (Interviewee 5: Manager in the Audit and Inspection Department).

“Organisational change could be through many ways, since I'm in the human resources Department I think the biggest change would be the cultural changes ... so I think change should be driven through the culture of the institution” (Interviewee 7: Manager in Human Resource Department).

On the other hand, one of the interviewees believed that organisational changes are minor changes in the organisation which do not include the objective and goals of the organisation.

On this Interviewee 6 commented:

“Organisational change is basically change in minor working modality of the organisation without affecting the major business objective of organisation. The major business objective would remain the same but the way of achieving that business objective will change ... so basically, the business objective should not be changing

otherwise the organisation would completely become another organisation when their primary business goal changes” (Manager in the Information Technology Department).

6.2.2 Responses on Experiencing Organisational Change

All the senior executives selected for this interview have worked in the Himalayan Bank for more than five years. Three out of the eight interviewees have been working in the Bank for more than 10+ years. As per the interviewees, Himalayan Bank has undergone numerous changes since 2002 – 2003. The interviewees answered this question in detail. Few interviewees described organisational changes that were carried out within different departments, while others talked about the overall changes in Himalayan Bank.

Among the eight interviewees, most of the changes that the Bank has undertaken range from changes in structure, policies, time scheduling, technology, digitalisation, culture, the formation of the staff union, and training and development.

One of the interviewees talked about how suddenly he changed from the credit department to the Human Resource (HR) department. He considered that as a significant change for himself as he had to undergo training to learn the new department's practices and procedures. The majority of the interviewees talked about the technical change and the digitalisation of products and services. The Human resource department has digitalised the entire recruitment, appraisal, and transfer procedures. New software called 'Vigo' has been initiated, and all HR-related tasks have now performed using this software. All the HR department employees are provided with training and online courses to educate them with the new software.

Additionally, an interviewee also discussed that the computer banking system (CBS) of HBL has changed from the primary System to T24 (minutes). It enables the employees to input data from any branch (in or outside the valley) remotely. All the files have been secured in the password-protected forum.

“Since I've taken over this Department a lot of things have changed and our entire recruitment, transfer, appraisals now is done by IT using software and portal bases. It used to be done manually before now we don't have to use paper and ink ... All HR related works are now being done through the new software Vigo.” (Interviewee 1: Human Resource Department Head).

The customer service department of HBL has also digitalised, whereby the customer is offered facilities such as information on interest rates, loans, and landings using their mobile banking app. Three out of the eight interviewees talked about the cultural change and personnel change within the Bank. In terms of the working culture, time-schedule and uniform for the employees have changed. Their attendance has now monitored digitally using a biometric system. All the employees have been provided with a code of conduct that presents uniform guidelines. These are mandatory for all the employees to follow. Personnel change includes job structure and rotation. It became necessary for the employees working in any department (for at least three years or more) to transfer to another branch and/or departments from last year. This change has been introduced to initiate job rotations that will help employees in developing additional skills.

“I think the one change that occurred in the organisation is like a little bit say sharpening of the culture because it was quite lax at the time when I joined and after we've been working a lot on improving the discipline of the Bank and corporate governance part of the Bank ... so the Bank changed culturally in a sense that people are now more open to training and learning and adopting to the technological changes” (Interviewee 7: Manager in Human Resource Department).

Most of the interviewees mentioned being a part of technical and structural changes. Technological changes are complex when they involve the use of new software and forums. Therefore, all the employees are provided with the training to help them adapt smoothly to the digital changes.

“I joined almost 10 years ago, and I have experienced many types of changes in HBL whether it would be regarding the policy related to culture to human resources to the technology policies and creation of the staff union ... recently I've been working for digitisation of products ... basically our Bank is trying to provide the service through digital media as far as possible” (Interviewee 6: Manager in the Information Technology Department).

6.2.3 Participation of Senior Executive's in the Change Process

All the interviewees had a mixed response when asked whether they have been a part of the change processes. Three out of the eight interviewees have not directly been a part of the departmental changes. One of the interviewees is the departmental head, and he was not directly involved in the process but conversed the changes through his team. In contrast, the others are working in the compliance department, where the changes have been implemented by the regulatory bodies only.

“No, I have not been involved in current changes as such, but circulars are issued by the central Bank that we have to circulate to top management, and they take it from there... Those are compulsory changes” (Interviewee 3: Manager in compliance Department).

Alternatively, the remaining five have been actively involved in the change process within their departments. Detailed and in-depth answers were provided for this question. One of the interviewees commented that he is not directly involved in the change processes in HR departments because he had a team of individuals carrying out changes such as training and development courses. He did consider himself as the supervisor for the team and consulted when required. Concerning the formation of the staff union, all the employees were allowed to vote only after the regulatory bodies created the union. Personnel changes such as changes in

the working hours, working from home, and code of conduct have been implied to all the employees. On the other hand, one of the interviewees working in the HR department has been at the forefront of the new change. That includes providing training and courses to all level employees. He considers himself as the training provider, coach, and assessor of the change. As per his remarks, he is directly involved with the regulatory bodies and assesses the departmental and staff needs and conducts training with them regularly.

“Yes, I have changed certain working style in my own department. The change was basically a formation of a team that would observe the branches online rather than going physically... initially when we used to visit branch it would take three to five days for us to complete one branch... but now the department collects data from head office and we analyse the data simply by staying at the head office. This saves our time by two days” (Interviewee 5: Manager in Audit and Inspection Department).

Two have actively been a part of the digital change in their departments. Here, the input and output of data, transfer of documents, and communication with vendors are accomplished using the new software and databases. They further specified that their department heads regularly coordinate with the employees, so they are involved in decision making and aware of their assignments, ensuring the efficiency is maintained.

“Yes, I was a part of this change that is digitalisation of documents. Basically, the vendor sent us the documents in 2 passport files: financial and technical parts. The documents are sent in our email ID ...then those documents are forwarded to the senior executive. We can operate both the files from any branches instead of waiting for the hard copies” (Interviewee 8: Senior Officer in General Administration Department).

One of the interviewees also mentioned the culture change. He elaborated how the culture of the Himalayan Bank has changed over 27 years. Previously, the culture was pre-set and was

expected to be followed by all the employees. Over the years, the Bank has started involving the employees in decision-making and promoting young individuals to senior positions. Instead of top-down decision making, employees are encouraged in two-way communications. Follow-up meetings and target deadlines are regulated to ensure the change process has been executed smoothly.

Most of the interviewees mentioned how the Bank has started to encourage employees to take part in the change initiatives. That is through constant monitoring, discussions, analysis, and feedback.

6.2.4 Factors Influencing the Rationale for Change

One of the aspects of this research is to consider the rationale behind organisational change amongst the interviewees and analyse the different reasoning for implementing the change processes. When probed on this question, all the interviewees had diverse responses. Reasons for change ranged from improving efficiency, timesaving, improve the quality of data, improve technology, sustain competitors to complying with regulations.

Four out of the eight interviewees mentioned the need to improve efficiency. The HR department was carrying out all the tasks manually, which was very time-consuming. The quality of the output was not up to the standards of the international financial information units (FIU). Not just the management structure but the policies and the technology of the department needed change. Furthermore, training and development sessions have launched to provide employees with knowledge that would enhance their efficiency. The basis is installing a software (Vigo) that will carry out various tasks proficiently with fewer human errors and save time.

“The Know Your Customer (KYC) forms of the Bank were not as detailed and up to the international FIU and FAT standards so there was a gap in the CBS system of the Bank... the system was operated manually which was time consuming in handling and

assessing all files. The efficiency was low, and a lot of time was consumed with managing the data. So, after 3 years, the CBS system was upgraded, and all the forms were changed and digitalised” (Interviewee 2: Senior Manager in Compliance Department).

“Actually, in Nepal, in banking sector there is lack of induction training not just in our Himalayan Bank but all over. Staffs are recruited in short period of time then without giving them training, they are directly deployed to the respective department ... they lack knowledge and due to that they sometimes provide false information to customers that hampers the image of our Bank. Due to this, auditors and a compliance department have come to a view that staff needs training and coaching so accordingly we prepare and give them training and development courses with the approval from the top management. This also motivates them and improves their working capabilities” (Interviewee 4: Senior Manager in Human Resource Department).

An interviewee further explained why the formation of the staff union was essential. The Bank (as opposed to its competitors) did not have a staff union. To minimise the issues, maintain the employee's motivation, and improve efficiency, the staff union's formation was deemed necessary.

“After union has been formed staff has been benefited a lot from the union and for changing work processes to increase our efficiency so that we can produce better result with less effort, that was the main motive behind the change” (Interviewee 5: Manager in Audit and Inspection Department).

Three senior executives out of eight mentioned competition. This competition is interrelated with the technological need to change. These interviewees explained how technological change was desperately needed to sustain the competitors. Banks such as Nabil Bank, NIC Asia Bank,

and Everest Bank (considered significant competitors of HBL) use high-end technology in their CBS systems, marketing, and customer services. To retain the existing customers, technological changes such as digitalisation of documents, T24 and Vigo (software) was essential.

“The first and foremost important point is the competitive market...so many of the commercial Banks basically are targeting customers by transforming themselves as digital first pad... so that is the main need that we have felt for this change and obviously we also keep in mind that if we could go for digitisation, we would be able to improve our efficiency, we could better serve to our customer” (Interviewee 6: Manager in Information Technology Department).

6.2.5 Views on change impacting the work and working environment

When asked how the changes have improved employees working life and environment, seven out of the eight interviewees answered that the change has been positive for them and their departments. Alternatively, one of the employees talked about how the change has increased stress in his working environment. Timesaving, improved productivity, and efficiency are the most common responses to this question.

Four out of the eight interviewees mentioned how the technological changes within the Bank have saved time and improved productivity. They stated that the changes had improved the time management of tasks within their departments. For example, one interviewee mentioned how technological changes minimized the costs and time of visiting and auditing other branches. This had automatically improved productivity in the audit and inspection department.

“The change has saved us a lot of time and cost of going to other branches so eventually it improved the productivity of employees, especially in my department” (Interviewee 5: Manager in Audit and Inspection Department).

“Banking is the most cash incentive business, so regulation is important because chance of misusing funds and misusing institutions is becoming greater day by day. Hence, I make sure that the regulations are followed, and staff are informed of the changes... we are in early phase of digitisation and work is going successful. It will help us to perform better in the coming future and staffs will be more inspired by new trainings” (Interviewee 4: Senior Manager in Human Resource Department).

Another interviewee discussed how the new software had reduced the cost and time burden within the HR department. For example, employees can now view their facilities and reserves on the system and request holidays and commissions digitally. Adding to this, another interviewee mentioned although digitalization is in the early stages, the results are quite positive. The interviewee is now able to provide training online. These sessions can be accessed by employees anywhere. That not only benefits the employees in terms of efficiency and motivation but also management who are more reachable to their workforce.

One of the interviewees discussed that new software lowered the stress levels at work as previously the department employees would ask her how to do the tasks instead of reading the manual and going through the policy pages. That was not only time consuming but very chaotic. However, with the help of training, the employees are more fluent with the software and more attentive towards their tasks. She further added that due to this change, she is more efficient at her work and more active in thinking and solving problems. Working with central management has been a great learning experience for him and has also augmented his working morale.

On the contrary, one interviewee had a different response. He explained that the new changes added more responsibility and stress to his work. The digitalisation of new product and services requires a lot of time to research. Due to which the interviewee had to spend extra hours at work. He was unable to manage his work-life balance that triggered stress and job dissatisfaction.

“It has been a little difficult to work as before, but we do maintain to do the regular jobs ...technology has made the work easy but there are certain difficulties associated with the new changes that will take time for the employees to adjust” (interviewee 3: Manager in compliance Department).

The view of the senior interviewees reflects the enthusiasm and positive outlook on changes as the old practices were slow and incompetent. Hence, from this question it led to the understanding that technological changes are complexed and, employees are taking more time to adjust to those changes.

6.2.6 Views of Senior Executive on Change Benefitting to the Organisation

When asked if the changes have been of any value to the organisation, all the eight interviewees answered yes. According to them, time and cost savings, training, improved productivity and motivation, and technological developments are a few change factors that added value to the Bank.

One interviewee explained how changing the software and improving the data quality has boosted the Bank's overall image compared to its competitors. Not only the regulators are pleased with the Bank's progress, but they have also appraised HBL for their organisational transformations. Two interviewees mentioned time and cost savings. Senior managers and their teams are more focused on improving data quality instead of traveling, assessing, and handling paperwork. One of the interviewees, who is also the project manager for developing and

promoting new products, commended the launch of the mobile banking app. Due to the current situation, the app has been beneficial to the customers as it provides them with services that were earlier only possible when visiting the branches. Another interviewee commented on how changes in HBL have brought a positive impact on the junior employees. The changes in training strategies have heightened employee's motivation and openness of communication. As per the senior interviewee, the junior employees are now more open and comfortable to discuss work-related issues. Thus, being a part of discussions and training groups has improved their job insecurities and productivity and added good value to the Bank.

“Yes, obviously the changes have been of a substantial value and definitely it's a different, like a paradigm shift for our workers” (Interviewee 1: Human Resource Department Head).

“Definitely brought us a value because earlier departments were weak and consistent with limited manpower, that have been improved with digitalization and technical improvement” (Interviewee 3: Manager in compliance Department).

“Yes, for audit department it would cost money and other resources to visit the branches but once we started doing work from head office those costs were saved. Moreover, staff efficiency has also increased, and we could regularly monitor staff even when we did not visit the branches” (Interviewee 5: Manager in Audit and Inspection Department).

Although every interviewee answered yes for this question, there was still some uncertainty sensed amongst two interviewees. From their discussion, it was visible that although the changes had a positive impact on the Bank, in terms of the work-life balance, the changes have increased work stress and ambiguousness.

6.2.7 Views of Senior Executives briefing the employees on changes

When asked if and how the senior executives brief the employees on change, the interviewees had mixed responses. The majority of the interviewees talked about meetings, training, seminars, and circulars. This question's responses are quite detailed that the interviewees have answered concerning their departments and the overall Bank.

An interviewee addresses the changes enforced by the regulatory bodies. She explains how the central Bank provides circulars that highlight the guidelines that are essential to follow. After distributing the circular, the employees are briefed by the senior executives on the changes. These circulars are mandatory to be followed by all the employees. Otherwise, the compliance officers from the central Bank intervene and, that can sometimes delay the change processes. Likewise, another interviewee mentioned that general changes within HBL are conferred amongst the senior executives only. Once the changes are approved, the employees and the managers distributed the circulars about the need to change. There are mostly mandatory for the employees to follow once sanctioned. Therefore, there is minimal or no feedback from the employees. These are the general changes, which are carried out by the senior executives and or the stakeholders.

“If the change is about certain departments, then we issue circular to that department and all the staff of that department attends a meeting and they are normally preached about the scenario and the changing process. If the issue is concerning whole Bank, then senior management will issue a circular to all staffs and they will instruct all staffs to follow as per the circular. This is how change has been communicated in our Bank”

(Interviewee 5: Manager in the Audit and Inspection Department).

On the other hand, when discussing briefing about department's changes, interviewees focused on meetings and feedback. According to them, changes are discussed with the employees of the various departments by conducting group meetings. After that, the proposal and memos

with the feedbacks are sent to the senior executives. Once the suggestion is accepted and approved by the senior management and the stakeholders, only the new policies are formatted. Those are distributed to all the employees via email. Additional changes are mostly constructed on whether the assessment is positive or negative. Hence, the employees are aware of the changes within their departments.

“We have 7 provinces in Nepal, where we have province heads and branch managers and training units that look after training. First, we need to know what changes we're doing and then give training, so employees get familiar with changes...With the help of training they easily adapt to new transformations” (Interviewee 1: Human Resource Department Head).

“Yes, in our case normally when we have to implement a new change in our organisation, we are properly briefed by our management that this is our vision and reason, our strategic plan for the upcoming years and so on...documents, trainings or any type of seminars that are important are provided to us then we are encouraged to participate on those type of things and then the change initiative is taken forward” (Interviewee 6: Manager in the Information Technology Department).

In contrast, one interviewee had a completely different view of the briefing. As per his explanation, in Nepal, the workforce tends to perform better under autocratic authorisation. Thus, there are no meetings and feedbacks, just circulars and emails. That helps the management in maintaining discipline and the quality of the output.

According to these senior executives, the departmental leaders are encouraged to involve and guide their employees for a constructive change process. Constant monitoring of feedback and analysis is to sustain the organisation's efficiency. Nevertheless, from their view, it can also be

concluded that there are instances where these change initiatives are imposed rather than discussed.

6.2.8 Views on Employees Reaction to Change and Resistance

When asked how the employees react to change and the existence of resistance to change, the interviewees revealed varied responses. Six interviewees responded with yes whereas two responded with 'no' to resistance. The six interviewees that responded with yes explained that employees are mostly hesitant of any changes, initially. The two main changes that encountered resistance within HBL are digital/technological changes and the changes in transfer policies.

Interviewees of the human resource department discussed how the changes in the Bank transfer system spiked resistance amongst female employees. In the past 26 years, male employees were always transferred outside the valley to administer rural branches. When the policies transformed and female employees were asked to transfer, they were not happy about this change and resented the management decision. The management introduced a new salary package to minimise the employee hostility to change. The further the transfer of employees, the higher the salary. That shifted the perspective of employees immensely. Similarly, another interviewee stated that the creation of the staff union played a massive role in minimising resistance. Frequent meetings and surveys conducted by the staff union help in keeping conflicts under control. One interviewee shared an incident of resistance within his department. Due to the Central Bank's requirements, an important task was altered and managed within the compliance department. Extra employees were needed to perform the tasks. The other branches' employees refused to co-operate and therefore, existing employees spent extra hours and effort on completing the task. That caused resentment and resistance amongst the workers towards the Bank.

“Yes, there is a lot of resistance in this Bank. I have found out is that dealing with people is the most difficult kind of dealing because when we are dealing with numbers and figures and files all those things never question you back, but people will question you about everything ... it is difficult to explain to people about some change that will affect their lifestyle in totality ... minor change is not a problem but when there's a major change it's very difficult to explain and satisfy all the staff. We have to make sure the management as well as the staff are satisfied so sometimes, we have to be harsh” (Interviewee 7: Manager in Human Resource Department).

Interviewees also mentioned technological resistance. Most of the former and older employees found it difficult to adapt to technological changes. Many employees primarily disapproved of the digital changes as they were not ready to shift from paper-based tasks to digital tasks. That also decelerated employee's productivity. As a result, the HR department conducted rigorous training that eventually reduced employee uncertainty and ensured the smooth implementation of technological changes.

“Digitalisation caused plenty of resistance and to impose technological changes, staffs were told what to do because they did not realise that the change is beneficial for the organisation and themselves. They are given training especially the older staffs to keep up with the digital aspects... With time the reluctance towards change is automatically decreased” (Interviewee 4: Senior Manager in Human Resource Department).

On the other hand, two interviewees had a completely opposing view and stated that the Bank does not face any resistance. According to them, new policies or changes are conveyed to the employees that are mandatory to follow. They further added that employees take training to adapt to technological changes if necessary.

“No, there is no major resistance in this Bank. Some customers do not accept technological change well but most employees in urban areas are educated and they are adapting to the new technology. In rustic areas we have to help employees with online processes and give them training” (Interviewee 8: Senior Officer in General Administration Department).

6.2.9 Future Prospects and Recommendation of Senior Executives on Change

When the interviewees asked if their department or the Bank would carry out changes differently in the future, the responses were a mixture of yes and no. The majority of the senior executives mentioned how changes must be carried out in the future, whereas other interviewees listed the changes or improvements needed in the Bank. Three out of the eight interviewees stressed the importance of communication. They mentioned that the Bank needs to improve the strategies of communicating the change to employees. If the employees are not instructed on the changes and why they are essential for the Bank, there will be resistance. He mentioned that the staff's union must provide counseling sessions to the employees to encourage communication between the employees and the senior management.

“For future I would recommend that benefit systems in our Bank should be changed like salary and other financial benefits to the employees should be improved as we have one-post one-salary system. Differential salary and more promotion options should be introduced. This will motivate employees and they will strive harder to improve their productivity” (Interviewee 4: Senior Manager in Human Resource Department).

One interviewee added that management must set up a committee that should focus on communicating change to the workforce. Instead, employees are handed circulars that are compulsory to execute. In his discussion, he emphasised the logic and need for the change to

be educated to all employees. There is hesitance in the initial phase towards change, but with the help of open communication, that uncertainty can diminish. The interviewee concluded that most of the resistance is challenging because of the lack of communication. Hence, the Bank needs to monitor and encourage two-way communication amongst employees. Another interviewee had a similar opinion, and he explained that currently, HBL follows a top-down approach in management and decision making. The majority of the new employees are hesitant to communicate with the management. They solely follow orders, which leads to a higher level of job dissatisfaction and lower percentages of retention. For this reason, the HR department needs to involve junior employees in decision making.

“Actually, till now what I feel is that everything happening in our organisation is top-down approaches, management makes the decision, and staff have to follow but you know I have felt that at times management are also lacking some information to make decisions. So, in future if they involve all the staff in decision-making regarding change then the change strategies would be acceptable by all staff and there would be less hesitance” (Interviewee 5: Manager in Audit and Inspection Department).

“Change is inevitable, it has to be done anyway and due to the human nature, some do not accept it ... to implement change first of all the management must educate their employees why particular change is required, what are the advantages of this change and so on. In my view the counselling of the employees and monitoring would be most important before initiating any type of change in future” (Interviewee 6: Manager in the Information Technology Department).

One interviewee accentuated that currently, the Bank carries out changes once in 5 years or when there is pressure from the regulatory bodies to change. These changes should execute

frequently. If the Bank keeps up with the technological changes, then it can survive the competition.

On the other hand, one employee stated that the Bank carries out changes in the most efficient way and follows the Central Bank guidelines. As per his view, the Bank should continue following the guidelines, and the employees should be more open and accepting of the changes.

He also declared that autocratic leadership is the best for countries like Nepal as it helps in retaining efficiency.

6.2.10 Summary of the Key Findings Emerging from In-Depth Interviews with Senior Executives

Having presented the findings generated by the in-depth interviews with key participants from across Himalayan Bank, Table 6.3 summarizes the key findings that emerged from these interviews.

Table 6.3: Summary of Key Findings from In-Depth Interviews with Senior Executives:

- Some of the current changes in HBL are renewal of CBS systems, installation of Vigo and T24 software, changes in working hours and dress code, digital training and development programmes, change in transfer policies and formation of staff union.
- Staff union is formed to adhere to the employee's issues such as pay, transfers, holidays, leaves and promotions. This was needed to help employees communicate the changes and tasks that are required from them.
- A new HR management is stationed to transform the department's structure, employees' tasks, and the former HR policies. Currently, the HR department has a team that carries out mandatory training sessions for all the employees. The portal allows the employees to access the programs online from any location. This has helped motivate employees and assisted them in times of change. Also, it helped to minimise the resistance and uncertainty amongst employees.
- The installation of biometric systems has been an effective change strategy as it has improved employee's punctuality and assists the management in monitoring employee's attendance and leaves.
- Majority of the senior executives argued that change agents and the departmental leaders involve the employees in the change process. They communicate the change properly and encourage employees to provide their feedback. That feedback is vital when transforming organisational policies.

- Alternatively, junior interviewees stated that employees are not allowed to participate in the change process with very little feedback. Hence, change is mainly imposed by the top management to the bottom.
- Lack of efficiency, indigent data quality, higher labour costs and sustaining competition are the crucial factors for implementing technological/digital changes in the Bank.
- The digital transformations have improved the quality of data, saves time and has reduced costs.
- There is a mixed view on resistance according to the interviewees. Resistance is observed mostly in the older employees and the female employees regarding the technological and transfer changes. That resistance is managed by training and pay rise incentives. In contrast, few senior executives also highlighted that surprisingly there is no resistance or uncertainty amongst employees. Consequently, the Bank carries out changes based on the central Bank's regulations and international financial institutions.
- Interviewees hinted that the pressing need to improve efficiency and the quality of data and services had increased working hours, uncertainty, and work stress amongst employees. The employees are struggling to maintain the work-life balance that at times causes job dissatisfaction and decreases motivation. Thus, these factors are some of the lead causes of resistance.
- The senior executives stressed that the Bank needs to improve communication amongst employees when carrying out changes. Instead of being bossed around, employees must be educated on the logic and the need to change.

6.3 Findings from Interviewees with Junior Level Employees

6.3.1 Views on Organisational Change

The most common response of organisational change from the perception of junior interviewees is changing the current business setting to improve the employees' efficiency and working environment. For instance, change in organisational culture, structure, and policies. Amongst that, five junior interviewees also view organisational change as a change in the organisation's technology and technical aspects. A few participants responded in the context of their department, and others focused on the overall change(s) in the Bank.

“Any kind of change in the systems or operations or technology. Something that is very basic or something that is very big that reconstructs the entire organisation is considered all under organisational change” (Interviewee 1: Supervisor in Human Resource Department).

“Organisational change in my view is the process in which an organisation changes its policy and the rules so that it can go further. That may include it's all operational methods, technologies, structures and strategies” (Interviewee 3: Security Analyst in information Technology Department).

“Organisational change means adopting the new things in a technical way, anything that needs to be changed in the organisation and changing in the manner to adopt to the market or demand is called organisational change” (Interviewee 6: Senior assistant in Internal Audit Department)

Nearly all the interviewees underlined technological changes and answered this question according to their utmost understanding.

6.3.2 Responses of Junior Employees on Experiencing Organisational Change

When asked if the junior interviewees have been a part of a change in the Himalayan Bank, six answered with a ‘yes.’ In contrast, two answered with a ‘no.’ According to these six interviewees, the changes vary between technology and time-schedule.

When mentioning technological changes, one interview explained how the HR department introduced the HRIS system. Previously as the senior interviewees mentioned, the tasks were paper-based and, now they are managed electronically. Furthermore, the training assessments and branch evaluations are carried out through the software portals. The card center has also updated their software where all the files are password-protected, and transactions are automatically segregated according to customers and branches. Another interviewee explained the change in the IT department from SAP to T24 software. This change required all the employees to undertake training to shift to the new software successfully.

“We have started our own HBL learning resources centre where we are in an agreement with the international training Institute and they have given us different banking related programmes that we have launched for our staffs. All training is done through online portals and the work of the human resource department is been completely digitalised and lots of work has minimised for me” (Interviewee 2: Training and Development Officer).

“Yes, I have. We updated to a new software and my involvement was to monitor all the settlement amount and reconciliation of accounts. I settle all the files such as Visa, Mastercard etc and the data for all our customers. I am the one person in the team that

undertook change in the card centre. The change was not hard to implement because it was an upgrade from our previous system” (Interviewee 4: Supervisor in the Card Centre/Department).

Regarding changes in the time-schedule, the Bank has changed the timings from 9:45 am to 9:30 am. An interviewee explained that this change was compulsory for all the employees. He further explained that the biometric system helps the management monitor the employee’s attendance so, now the workforce cannot cheat or skip their working timings. This change has affected the majority of the workforce. Most of the interviewees praised the schedule changes and declared that they are accepted by employees positively.

“I feel all the employees have faced the change in working timings because previously the management was not that strict, so employees used to be late. The new start time from 9:30 am is compulsory for all senior and junior employee “(Interviewee 3: Security Analyst in Information Technology Department).

On the other hand, two interviewees that commented no for this question are new employees and have been working in this Bank for less than a year. Due to the global pandemic, their work is minimalised, and tasks are mostly performed digitally from home. Therefore, they were not able to provide much detail on this question. Although, they did mention the technological changes within the Bank but individually have not been a part of any radical changes.

6.3.3 Views of Junior Employees on their Involvement in the Change

Process

When questioning the junior interviewees on their involvement in the change process, four interviewees agreed on being involved in the change discussions and processes. In contrast, the remaining four were defensive and stated there is no direct communication with the senior management.

The interviewees who agreed upon participating in the change process explained how new strategies were communicated to all teams. One interviewee explained that the HR department is at the forefront of ensuring all the employees are aware of the changes. Even if the changes are small-scale, the HR department discusses them by conducting meetings and online sessions. She further stressed that this department supports the exchange of ideas between all the employees. Likewise, interviewees from the IT and settlement department emphasised dialogue and feedback before implementing any changes. The employees carry out research and discuss their findings before proposing change strategies to their senior management. An interviewee further elaborated that the IT department provided training with the help of the HR department to the technical as well as non-technical employees to reduce digital ambiguity.

“If my supervisor comes tells me that there will be some certain changes to the system so in that scenario first of all I need to study and understand the given scenario and then I need to consult with my supervisor to get some trainings for career development skills so that I can do better... the management is helpful, and we discuss about our work like what we are doing and why. As a supervisor he or she allows us to give better ideas on changes” (Interviewee 3: Security Analyst in Information Technology Department).

“Yeah, our department head was very cooperative, and he made us all part of the meetings and groups before introducing the new software system... he consulted us on what changes are needed and that it will help us in doing the work more easily and more efficiently, so yeah I think they did involve us in the new change process” (Interviewee 5: Junior Assistant in Card Centre/Department)

In contrast, the other interviewees who disregard (any type of) employees involved in the change process argued that employees generally receive a circular via email with conditions and guidelines that are mandatory to follow. Furthermore, one also mentioned that most of the

changes are imposed rather than being discussed. The involvement of a junior level participant is minimum as opposed to senior employees. Concerning this, an interviewee revealed that technological changes are obligatory and, most of the junior employees are not provided with the training to adapt to new software. The employees improve their skills by self-learning and seeking help from their colleagues. Unexpectedly, interviewees agreed to the fact that the autocratic form of leadership is merely a cultural issue in Nepal. The following quote is from the selected interviewee:

“In terms of technological change such a changing software they did not tell me or my department anything, it was just implemented, and I just learned it myself by doing work. No formal training...and in case of change in leadership my seniors told me that there is a new leader and there was no option to agree or disagree” (Interviewee 8: Auditor in the internal Audit Department).

6.3.4 Views on change impacting the work and working environment.

Most of the interviewees agreed that the changes are impacting their working life positively. This viewpoint is expressed by both male and female interviewees. The most common (positive) impact of change responded by the junior interviewees are timesaving and efficiency.

“Change in the software was helpful for me because my work became easy and fast. I had more time to do the reconciliation and manage all the records and files. It is positive to me overall because everyone at the senior level staff admire me for my knowledge and my work and my ideas “(Interviewee 4: Supervisor in the Card Centre/Department).

One interviewee explained how all the unnecessary paperwork had been reduced due to the implementation of T24 Minutes and Vigo software regarding timesaving. Consequently, employees have more time to complete their follow-up tasks efficiently. Another interviewee

applauded the digitalization of training portals. Previously, it used to take the HR department weeks to attain approval for training. Presently, the workforce is interconnected under one portal and has access to various training and development sessions online. The portal is not only saving time, but it is also easy for the employees to use. Also, employees have a platform where they share their views and discuss issues regarding their work. Another interviewee encouragingly expressed those technological improvements have enhanced his efficiency and time management resourcefully. These interviewees indicated that the changes are restoring job satisfaction levels amongst most of the employees.

“The positive change for me was my new leader who is very helpful and taught me how to handle each and every small micro thing... not like my previous boss. I actually learned a lot of things and main thing is calmness ... there was peace of mind and less pressure. Currently, I feel really happy and relaxed at work” (Interviewee 8: Auditor in the internal Audit Department).

In contrast, two interviewees stated that there is no direct impact of changes on their working lives and environment. It is assumed, these are employees that are newly recruited to the Bank and have been in limited or no contact with the change agents or change policies, directly.

“Actually, the change of office timing didn’t impact me much as I used to go office on time and most of the other changes were already in place when I joined. So, there are no big shift in my working life or environment” (Interviewee 6: Senior Assistant in Internal Audit Department).

6.3.5 Views on Whether Changes Undertaken were Necessary

The interviewees were in complete agreement with the Bank’s need to change. This viewpoint was shared by seven interviewees who considered the changes as necessary for the Bank.

According to the interviewees, the reasons to change contrasts between sustaining competition, enriching efficiency, and cost-savings.

One interviewee explained that recently the customer service was lacking behind and to maintain the efficiency and compete with the rival Banks, the changes were essential. She further stressed how important it was to improve the working etiquettes of HBL employees. For instance, circulars were distributed to employees that highlighted speaking and writing etiquette, which is mandatory to follow. Another interviewee supported this view and added that competing Banks were investing in high-end resources to improve their technology. To sustain competition and retain customers, the Bank needed to update its technological systems majorly in customer service areas.

“It was necessary to improve our customer service and maintain the standard of our service etiquettes. That is the rationale behind the change and in terms of training, we've digitised the portals... in terms of adding value, a lot of previous processes has been eliminated so in that sense efficiency has definitely increased. People are slowly adapting to new systems and digital change and taking it as something that facilitate them to perform their work better” (Interviewee 1: Supervisor in Human Resource Department).

“Yes, it was important because people are not flexible with the technology itself and in Nepal the central Bank has already imposed that we should use electronic payment system ... training programmes in person were very costly, so for future programmes can be conducted using digital medium. We will not only save cost but increase our profits and staff motivation” (Interviewee 2: Training and Development Officer).

“Office time change was important I think that it will helps the colleagues to be more productive and loyal ...This change was needed because staff used to get late in the past but now the HR can keep a track of everyone, and all the staffs have to come at exact time” (Interviewee 3: Security Analyst in Information Technology Department).

Likewise, two interviewees supported the view of timesaving. They explained how the merchandise payments would take days to get approved and subsequently take weeks for the customers to receive their product. As per their perspectives, switching to digital platforms for customer service was the first solution to recover customer service. Another interviewee added that Digital software such as T24 Minutes has simplified the process of downloading (large) files from other branches and accounts of customers. The software provides data security as there is no loss of data and, working processors takes less time.

6.3.6 Views of Interviewees on Organisation Carrying Out the Changes

Effectively

Opinions are divided amongst interviewees when asked if the changes were carried out effectively. Three interviewees expressed their views on the current changes whereas the remaining five recommended change strategies for future.

Interviewees corresponded with the changes and claimed that the management carried those as effectively as possible. According to their viewpoints, change policies were transmitted to all the employees via email. Therefore, the decision to implement new policies was determined by the senior management and the urgency to comply with the central Bank’s rules and regulation. They further applauded the Bank’s investments in online training and the digitalisation of the tasks.

“Firstly, I want to make all the services of the Bank very prompt like HR department, admin department, these are the back offices and they do not have pressure at all, the tasks and customer services is very slow... Secondly, the Banks should invest in

marketing because these days competitors are using digital marketing and that is very convenient for customers” (Interviewee 2: Training and Development Officer).

“The organisation has changed a lot from few years. Earlier there was no training and E-commerce but now it has been gradually increasing and more training has been provided to the newly appointed staff... But I feel the Bank should establish a proper code of conduct and ethics so that all the employees are bound by it they work more efficiently” (Interviewee 5: Junior Assistant in Card Centre/Department).

“In this Bank when you find some bigger issue where all senior team of the HBL is involved, then that case gets dismissed. I think it’s a duty of the senior manager to go to the upper levels and address the case or issues rather than dismissing it. That will not solve but create more problems for future. In future, if there is an issue the management should talk about it rather than outing it on side” (Interviewee 8: Auditor in the internal Audit Department)

It was interesting to observe that despite the Bank encouraging communication, many interviewees agreed otherwise. Although the HR department allows an open two-way communication amongst all its employees, the overall Bank follows the top-down approach. Furthermore, they revealed that employees were hesitant with changes initially because the new policies were not transparent. They have instructed the changes without proper communication and, that leads to resistance. Concerning this, one interviewee added that in the future, the management and the employees should be aware of the Banks’ internal and external issues. According to the interpretations, the Bank did not provide any training before implementing technological changes. Employees self-learned Vigo and T24 Minutes using books and online resources that were very time-consuming.

“Yes, I think change is important but for future the employees must know the changes that is going to happen and not suddenly like immediate change should not be populated. Everyone should be ready to change and then the Bank should also look to change our organisational culture and working style” (Interviewee 3: Security Analyst in Information Technology Department).

Apart from communication, the interviewees emphasised changing the Bank’s marketing strategies. The Bank is currently performing and acquiring customers based on goodwill. To sustain competition, in the long run, the Bank needs to change its out-dated marketing strategies. Digital marketing will allow the Bank to market their product to a broader consumer base and save cost.

6.3.7 Summary of the Key Findings Emerging from In-Depth Interviews with Junior Level Employees

Having presented the findings generated by the in-depth interviews with key participants from across Himalayan Bank, Table 6.4 summaries the key findings that emerged from these interviews.

Table 6.4: Summary of Key Findings from Interviews with Junior Participants

- Technological advancements have allowed employees to perform tasks swiftly. Saving cost, time and improving overall efficiency.
- Training and development sessions have increased employee's motivation levels. Not just a team of 50 but a maximum of 1000 employees can take training at the same time and expand knowledge. The more employees are given training the more it helps them to adjust to the changes.
- Views were divided amongst interviewees as to the Bank involving employees in the change process.
- Change strategies are broadcasted within HR and admin departments via group discussions. However, this view was rejected by other interviewees.
- Immediate change causes uncertainty amongst employees that leads to resistance. Majority of the employees recommended the Bank to improve communication amongst various departments.
- Whilst they agree on changes, the top-down approach is highly unfavoured by most of the junior interviewees.
- The Bank needs to change their marketing strategies particularly in the areas of digital and social media marketing to sustain competition.
- Some interviewees criticised the power structure in the Bank. The Bank should focus on recruiting more young individuals and promote middle management to senior levels. Only then, there will be fresh approaches and ideas to change that will help the Bank to prosper.
- Lack of promotion is another factor of job dissatisfaction amongst junior level employees that causes them to resist imposed changes.
- HR department is criticised for exploiting its power over other departments. A task that can be completed within a day takes 3-5 working days because of the inefficiency of the department.

Tables 6.5: Common Themes Emerging from Survey and Interview

Participants' Findings

- Employees perceive changes positively for the organisation
- Diverse perceptions of employees on nature of organisational change being carried out in Himalayan Bank
- Imposed changes lead to fear and stress amongst employees
- Varying opinions of junior and senior participants on resistance to change; and
- Junior employees are observed to be more adaptive to technological changes as opposed to senior employees
- Organisational change itself is recognized emphatically, but the ambiguity associated with those changes are opposed.

The findings from the two sets of data were cross-checked to identify common themes that emerged. The correspondence area identified from the exchange of the survey questionnaire and the interview is summarized in Table 6.5. Overall, it can be established that the results from the survey involving general participants complement the results from in-depth interviews with key junior participants and senior executives.

These themes that emerged from interviews and survey questionnaires, as demonstrated in Table 6.5, will be chosen again in the next chapter to discuss the themes in the context of the relevant literature.

6.4 Conclusion

This chapter has focused primarily on presenting the findings from the two sets of interviews conducted with key participants in the Himalayan Bank, Nepal. The interviews represent the qualitative dimension of this research and highlight insights provided by senior executives and junior-level employees on organisational change and resistance to change. Many interesting viewpoints are derived from the data that have been summarised above. These will further be used when analysing the following chapters. The researcher was able to get thorough information on the context of change and resistance that was not possible with just utilising survey strategy. Hence, the data derived from the interviews will be helpful for further elaborating the survey questionnaire responses.

Chapter 7 – Discussion

7.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the key themes emerging from this mixed-methods research study and links them back to the empirical literature critiqued in chapter 2. As stated in the onset, this thesis aimed to examine the perceptions of Himalayan Bank employees on experiencing organisational change and resistance to change amongst those working in this Bank in Nepal. This research further explores key participants views on their involvement in the current changes that are imposed and executed within the Bank. It also underlines employees' perceptions on resistance to those changes and change strategies employed within their departments. Finally, this thesis offers some insight into the extent to which the perceptions reported in this research can provide a meaningful understanding of the prospects of improving employee participation in change practices. Furthermore, executing changes in such a way would improve the Bank's overall productivity and decrease the level of resistance that is triggered due to sudden inflicted changes amongst employees. Concerning this research, this study seeks to answers the following research objectives:

- To identify the nature of organisational change that occurred at the Bank.
- To gauge the perceptions of change amongst employees.
- To identify factors contributing to resistance to change amongst employees.
- To establish organisational strategies implemented to achieve the desired change.

The key themes discussed in this research will be answering the above mentioned research aims and objectives and the findings from both sets of data. Adhering to Bryman and Bell (2011, p. 693) advice, the research has considered the qualitative and quantitative findings thematically across a different set of results to certify the integration as expected in a mixed-method research. The themes from the three sets of data collected (survey and interviews) aids

the research understand the various aspects and issues related to organisational change and the probable causes of resistance to change amongst the employees working in Himalayan Bank, Nepal.

These themes summarized in Table 6.5 of chapter 6 are restated here as a reminder:

- Employees perceive changes positively for the organisation;
- Diverse perceptions of employees on nature of organisational change being carried out in Himalayan Bank;
- Imposed changes lead to fear and stress amongst employees;
- Varying opinions of junior and senior participants on resistance to change; and
- Junior employees are observed to be more adaptive to technological changes as opposed to senior employees;
- Organisational change itself is recognized emphatically, but the ambiguity associated with those changes are opposed.

Employees have diverse perceptions regarding the changes that are executed in the Bank. This also contributes to the factors that cause resistance amongst these employees when adapting to those changes. Perceptions of senior executives and junior employees can support this research by uncovering the strategies implemented to achieve desired changes. The themes mentioned above will be discussed in turn in the following sections of this chapter.

7.2 The Nature of Organisational change occurred at this Bank

The research findings validate that the current body of knowledge informs us that significant organisations and co-operations implement change at least once to every four-five years (Kotter and Schlesinger, 2008). The findings confirm that the Bank has undergone various internal and external changes in the past five years. It uncovered that technological (Vigo and T24 software, CBS systems renewal) digital (HRIS and administrative tasks, online training via digital portals

and digitization of services) and structural (dress code, transfer policies and job rotations, working hours, and formation of a staff union) are the main changes driven by the internal forces within the Bank. In line with the literature, as explained by Brooks (2004), changes in an organisation and its process, to an extent, depends upon the external and internal forces to change. Any initiative for change in the organisation arises from opportunities and problems existing in the internal or external environment (Robbins & Barnwell, 2006). Furthermore, as supported by Senior (2002), who identifies that changes in technology, HR policies such as overtime work, pay, power reallocation and transfers, changes in administrative structures, and any changes in the internal design in terms of a group or an individual are the critical internal factors that force organisational change.

The findings also uncovered that Nepal's Banking industry has been under tremendous pressure due to external forces such as liberalisation, deregulation, technology, customer demands, industry competition, and politics. Hence, regulatory changes are imposed by the Central Bank, known as the Nepal Rastra Bank. Some of these set changes faced by Himalayan Bank are regulations in interest rates and loans and customer policies as supported by Senior (2002), who identifies economic forces that involve government economic policies such as employment rates, privatisation, corporate taxation, and competitors. Thus, as Dawson (2003) explained, fluctuation in the business cycle, such as changes in the level of national and international economies, can compel an organisation to introduce some changes.

The findings also confirm the evidence from the established literature regarding the extent and the origin of the changes. Organisational change is categorised as planned and emergent (Benn, Dunphy and Griffiths 2014; Brown and Osborne 2012; Weick 2012; Wilson 1992). As extracted from the findings, most of the internal changes such as technological advancement and digitalization of tasks and training portals within the Bank were gradual and slowly executed after thorough planning and consideration to meet the changing corporate

environment's demands and improve efficiency. Holbeche (2006) verified that planned change approaches are predicted and constructed on long-term corporate strategies that help the organisation achieve its desired goals. Adding to this, Ven Poole (1995) argued that planned changes are intentional actions taken after conscious reasoning to ensure the organisation will be meeting the demands of its internal and external environment. Likewise, interview findings underline another aspect of planned change. After the new HR manager's appointment, policies such as employee transferrals and job rotations to outside (valley) branches, dress code, office timings were reformed entirely, and programs to improve employee motivations were initiated. These changes were proposed after thoroughly examining the declining employee participation levels and morale and the HR department's inefficiency. A participant added that the senior executives instantly approved the new policies, but implementing these changes gradually helped employees transition with the change. This is supported by Thomas's (1991) view that when an organisation wishes to create an environment to qualify all the employees to reach their full potential, a planned change is considered necessary to achieve the coveted outcome. Furthermore, as described by Senior and Swailes (2010), planned change occurs whereby the agent authorising the change takes required deliberate actions to move organisational productivity from one state to another.

In terms of its intensiveness, change is divided into incremental and radical, as elaborated by Bessant and Caffryn (1997). From the interview findings, the researcher was able to capture the nature of the participants' changes. Thus, it was established that the renewal of CBS systems and the upgrade of software to Vigo were not radical but relatively continuous changes within the Bank. Moreover, previous systems such as SAP was upgraded to the new T24 core banking software to improve organisational performance. These changes were not imposed at once but were slowly upgraded over the past years. This is corroborated in the literature by Badarch

(2014), who argues that incremental change is based on routine and continuous modifications and is imperative for the business to adapt to withstand the business environment.

On the other hand, Burnes (2004) further distinguishes between incremental and continuous change and states that constant change allows the business to change frequently to adjust to the rapid and fast changing rhythm of change, such as transforming technology or structure. So, in light of this literature, it can be argued that the nature of technological changes carried out in HBL is gradual and continuous, correspondingly. Structural changes such as changing the dress code and the office timings for all the employees were explained as minor adjustments over time that enhanced employee's competence. Samuel (2011) outlined that incremental changes can either be small, but their primary purpose is to improve the overall business function.

A further investigation into the nature and extent of organisational changes from the findings disclosed that the formation of a staff union was one of the employees' fundamental changes. The persistent need to change the corporate culture and monitor staff resistance towards new modifications and alterations led to the transformational change of formulating a staff union. As explained earlier, before this union, employees did not have a defined division to address their matters, leading to chaos and discontent behaviour amongst employees. This is supported by Denison's (1996) views, who identify transformational change as reforming the organisational structure and the employee's behaviour that entails values, beliefs, goals, and the organisation's assumptions. Pragmatically, improving the culture and the corporate member's mindset is deemed crucial for the anticipated changes. However, from the findings, it can be observed that the nature of this transformational change occurs under the change classifications by Dunphy and Stace (1993), known as modular transformations. It involves significant reclassification of organisations departments, thus leading to structural changes to improve overall performance.

Similarly, the interpretations of the findings from this research further uncovered that the formation of staff unions was a change that was fundamental not just to improve the employee's contribution and to enhance the current status/position of the Bank. However, Himalayan Bank needed to survive the competitors and fluctuating business environment in the long run. This is backed by Cummings and Worley (1997) main emphasis, explaining that organisational transformation involves changes in the way people perceive, think, and behave at work. The organisational transformation consists of reshaping the organisation's culture and design elements; it goes well beyond just "making the organization better or fine-tuning the status quo." Instead, it entails the fundamental change of the character and culture of the organisation. A high percentage of participants emphasized the technological changes being carried out within the Bank. The findings revealed that the Bank is investing highly in technological innovation to sustain its market position and compete with the other rival Banks such as NIC Asia Bank and Nabil Bank. Hence, it is essential to cover those findings under the composed literature. As Eveleens (2010) mentioned, organisations are continually looking at innovative strategies because it helps organisations improve their profit and performance and helps them develop strategies that will either innovate them or move out of the competition. It was further argued that innovation is challenging, and changes in technology often attract resistance. However, the slow implementation of such changes helps the employees change their attitudes towards the new processes (Eveleens, 2010). Besides, organisational changes can be prompted by the technological factors driving changes to sustain competition. These factors include improving informational technology, new products and services, digitalization of processes, and changes in transport technology (Senior and Swailes, 2010).

The interview findings by junior participants also confirmed that the Bank changes are considered essential to enhance the overall productivity and improve employee efficiency. Many key participants echoed this view that Himalayan Bank is frequently changing its

structure and technology to keep up with the competitors. This viewpoint is verified by Chaudhary's (2012) research, which explains that over the past 20 years, vigorous growth has been monitored within Nepal's banking industry. The literature also confirms that despite the political uncertainty and the economic downfall, Himalayan Bank is observed to be progressing effectively with the undoubtful faith of customers, direct and indirect support of the shareholders' and creative initiatives adopted by the management (Himalayan Bank Limited, 2018).

These findings will also be matched with the three-step model developed by Kurt Lewin (1951) on a planned change that includes unfreeze, freeze (change), and refreeze as underlined in the literature. This approach is an appropriate way to explain the organisations implementing incremental and continuous changes such as financial institutions (French & Bell, 1995; Burnes, 2004b). The model applying Himalayan Bank changes is discussed below:

- At this stage, the bank acknowledged a need for change due to employees' inefficacy and weaker productivity. The Bank needed to undergo technological, digital, and structural changes. Resistance was monitored (particularly) amongst senior employees when executing digital changes.

- At this stage the new HRIS department digitalised most of the tasks such as training, appraisals, transfers, and salaries. Attendance is now monitored using a digital device that requires all the employees to sign in before entering their respective departments.

The Bank also changed the CBS system to meet the FIU (financial information units) demands regulated by the Central Bank. Employee support helplines and training assisted employees in adapting to new changes, especially technological changes.

Refreeze

- At this stage, the management monitors employee behaviour and attitudes to check if they comply with new changes. It is mandatory for employees in the technical department to comply with the new software. In-house and online training is given to employees that are mandatory for them to attend to understand and implement new changes.

The next section will discuss participants' viewpoints on organisational change and their experiences associated with those changes in connection with the empirical literature. The researcher can then thoroughly examine the resistance factors amongst the employees and strategies (if any) that were implemented to help the employees adapt to the change.

7.3 The Perception of Organisational Change amongst Employees

Surprisingly, the findings indicate varied responses and attitudes from the participants towards the changes occurring in their Bank. The majority of survey participants indicated that change was not negative, in their opinion. At the same time, they also expressed in the interviews that the implementation of new changes is obstructed by poor communication and negative attitudes to change. The findings further uncovered that the need to change was vital to improve the Bank's efficiency and productivity. Likewise, the changes not only focused on the operational levels of the Bank, but they were also a source of refining employee's capabilities and personal development. As discussed in the literature by Silvester *et al.* (1999), employees feel more

positive towards changes that do not involve staff reductions but instead offer skill development opportunities to progress innovative work methods.

The interview findings expose some similarities between the views of junior and senior participants. Junior level participants highlighted changes such as technological advancements and digitalization of tasks have not only improved their efficiency, but the unnecessary time spent on paper-based tasks is also diminished. Hence, time saved on administrative tasks due to digitalization gives employees more time to think about creative ways to improve their department and personal growth. This opinion is corroborated with the views outlined by Johnstone and Michel (2008) in the literature. They state that technological change is an essential initiator that allows people to do innovative things that have not been done before or done less efficiently. The findings indicate that both; the senior executives and the junior level participants have varied viewpoints. For example, senior executives are more concerned with diminishing the costs and improving their respective departments' productivity. On the other hand, junior levels participants are more concerned about the change affecting their personal wellbeing at work. These varied perceptions correspond with the literature by Armstrong-Stassen (2005) that supervisors and non-supervisory staff have different attitudes toward and perceptions about organisational change, arising from their disparate experiences of the change process, reflecting differences in power, autonomy, and influence.

The positive outlook on change by participants coincides with the literature that argues having engaged employees is a key to competitive advantage from the organisational point of view (Bakker & Schaufeli, 2008; Baumruk, 2004, Macey & Schneider, 2008; van Dam et al. 2008). A few of the participants explained that changes such as in the CBS system have massively improved their working ability and, in the long run, boost their career. The tasks are handled and completed much swiftly as before. They further argued that their work is now being recognised by their seniors, increasing their job satisfaction and motivating them to perform

their best. As discussed in the literature review by Näswall *et al.* (2008), modern organizations today not only need employees who are doing their job in order to survive, but they need employees who are willing to put in some extra effort. Such employees are dedicated, give their best, take responsibility for their professional development, and be committed to high-quality performance.

The findings also revealed the participant's perceptions of the nature of the change. A small number of participants explained that changes such as the HRIS systems' upgrade were incremental instead of being rapidly implemented. They further added that the slow adaptation of changes helped employees fully understand and grasp the new policies. As declared in the literature by Gallivan, Hofman and Orlikowski (1994), the implementation of incremental change is relatively more effective within an organisation than imposed changes. However, it has to be considered that a small number of participants were not able to express their views on the nature of the changes confidently. This is because they have been recently recruited and are not directly involved in any changes. Hence, this judgment is exclusively based on the findings from the percentage of actively involved participants affected by the change processes. On the other hand, the findings also display some undesirable perceptions by some participants. They argued that although the desired changes are implemented to benefit the organisation and the employees, those are associated with some discouraging factors. Participants explained that changes added extra on workload and due to which extra time to has to spend by employees at the Bank. This, in turn, affects their work-life balance that sometimes hampers their motivations and job satisfaction levels. This viewpoint is certified by Kotter and Cohen (2002), who stresses that organisation operates mechanically sometimes at the expense of compromising living human beings who want meaningful work that also allows them to have a stable life outside their work.

Similarly, this is backed by Ahmad (2000). He debates that the effect of organisational change depicts that non-supervisors, as change recipients, report higher role ambiguity and overload, lower job satisfaction and commitment, lower perceptions of job security, and lower acceptance of the organisational change. Moreover, Nelson *et al.* (1995) explain that job satisfaction and mental and physical health are declining more among manual and junior workers than managerial and supervisory staff overtime.

Positive insights are established from the findings in terms of the HR department. The HR leader's switching was a pragmatic decision for the management and the junior employees. According to junior participants, findings uncovered that the new HR leader encourages employee participation, feedback, and discussions. This is perceived positively amongst employees as they quoted that their leader understands, calmer, and allows employees to complete tasks as per their ability instead of their former leader. This viewpoint is corroborated with literature by Covin & Kilmann (1990) that states having a positive leader is crucial during organisational change as a leader provides a vision of change, supports employees, and model appropriate behaviour. Such actions help build stability during change and enhance employees' commitment to it (Schweiger *et al.*, 1987; Covin & Kilmann, 1990). Adding to this, employees described work stress levels as diminished as they felt much happier and relaxed at the Bank. This is connected to the literature with the research of Näswall *et al.* (2008), where they discuss that when employees are involved in any way within their departments, they tend to have a positive job-related attitude, a strong identification with work, improved mental health, performance, and motivation, as well as better access personal resources. Hence, a well-involved and guided employee feels, in general, more connected to its organisation and the leadership (Näswall *et al.*, 2008).

When questioned participants on their involvement in the change process and policies, the interview findings display varied responses amongst junior and senior participants' views. A

selected number of junior participants expressed that their managers and departmental leaders encouraged frequent meetings and discussions every morning, and any changes within their departments were consulted beforehand. It was relatively more straightforward for such employees to adapt to changes with minimum hesitancy in the long run. Piderit (2000) claimed that encouraging employee's participation in planning change and decision making helps to minimise the individual's resistance levels concerning those changes. Hence, the findings concluded that employees in some departments are not just involved in decision making but maintain a good employee-employer relationship. In a way, this is verified by Taylor & Tekleab's (2004) research on the psychological contract. It states that a psychological contract is a mutual exchange that sources trust amongst employers and employees in an organisational context. Literature also adds that encouraging involvement can strengthen the psychological contract between employees and managers, and the trust that is developed is manifested in employee's behaviour and attitudes positively (Weber and Weber, 2001).

Contrary to the above viewpoint, findings derived from junior participants also show that their seniors neither consulted some employees on change practices nor were involved in the decision making. On these lines, one to two participants explained that circulars and emails were handed out in their department, which is expected to be followed by all the employees. Likewise, most of the Bank changes are imposed from the top-level hierarchy that highlights top-down management behaviour. Hence, that creates uncertainty amongst employees, and in turn, they are bound to resist those changes. This viewpoint can be connected with Jaussi's (2007) argument that the more employees feel integrated and are involved in organisations, the better task persistence and performance will be. This argument also links with the research conducted by Cornelissen (2014). As per his work, the degree to which managers involve their employees in decision making and communicate with them directly impacts employee morale and commitment to the organisation. Lack of training, resources, and support from leadership

further add to discouraging views from participants in terms of their involvement. Participants' negative perceptions also highlighted that technological changes, such as transforming the current organisational software, were challenging and more complex in adopting when there is no proper training. Due to this, employees experienced higher stress levels and a high workload. The new processes were learned using resources online and consulting with other peers that were time-consuming and hectic for some employees. This viewpoint falls under Dent and Goldberg's (1999) work, whereby one of his points explains that employees oppose technological changes when such changes are undertaken without involving them. Besides, literature incorporates views by Metha (2006), who expresses that technological change can also lead to changes in job satisfaction, stress, working conditions, productivity, and operational efficiency.

Although the Bank encourages employee involvement as confirmed by the senior participants' findings, as per the junior participants, this is not always true. For example, 80% of the senior participants believe that most of the changes carried out within the Bank are executed after being discussed and communicated with employees. Only the central Bank's imposed changes are conveyed using circulars and emails, and employees from all hierarchal levels have to adhere to those. In contrary to that, findings uncovered that even though the senior management of the Bank fosters employee engagement, sometimes specific issues are underlined by the junior employees that are needed to be addressed by the upper management and are not entirely taken into consideration. Due to which there are distrust and scepticism amongst the employees that advances into resistance. As mentioned in the literature by Kotter and Schlesinger (2008), employees individually or in groups differ in their information concerning the execution of specific changes. Furthermore, literature by Waddell and Sohal (1998) also adds that differences in opinions create doubts within the workforce regarding the worth of change and may compel employees to stand opposite to their management.

This section's findings suggest that both junior and senior participants have diverse attitudes towards and perceptions about organisational changes carried out in their Bank. These might be due to their different experiences of the change process that may reflect differences in power, autonomy, and influence. Moreover, it is comprehended that employees appointed at a higher level of hierarchy in the Bank can influence decisions because they are directly involved in decision making, whereas lower-level employees are less directly involved.

7.4 The Factors Contributing Towards Resistance within Employees

The view from both junior and senior participants underlines that the Bank faces resistance from employees when executing changes. This view is held by more than 80% of the participants. The interview findings present that humans are far more complex and emotional to be controlled mechanically. To instigate any changes that may alter or transform their present circumstances, change agents must be prepared for resistance. As stated by Niccolò (Machiavelli 1995: 193), 'it is essential to understand that nothing is more challenging to carry out, nor more uncertain of success or more dangerous to manage than, to instigate a new order of things.' To understand both the perceptions (of junior employees and senior executives), the factors contributing to resistance within HBL are gauged in detail. These factors are selected from the findings and are relevant to this particular study. The interview findings helped the researcher understand that regardless of communication, employees, to an extent, will foresee different aspects to change as opposed to what was conducted. This compelled the researcher to understand dissimilar evaluations and perceptions amongst various HBL employees. As verified in the literature by Kotter and Schlesinger (2008), employees have dissimilar characteristics due to which information is possessed differently amongst individuals or groups. Thus, differences in analysis lead to resistance. Participants argued that changes are difficult to communicate to the employees because individuals have varied perceptions of their routines being altered and some of those perceptions are often negative. As confirmed in the

literature by Kotter and Schlesinger (2008), individuals resist change because, in organisations where there are many levels of hierarchy, information is perceived differently by general employees against the managers or change initiators. The literature further corroborates this factor with this viewpoint of Waddell and Sohal (1998), who stresses that resistance can transpire from employee's personal and rational assessment of outcomes and differs from the one envisioned by the management. Differences in opinions create doubts between employees and may compel them to stand opposite to their management.

The findings also highlighted that technological changes were difficult to execute within the Bank, and the older employees were far more hesitant and unfriendly to such changes. The senior employees' reactions were based on their personal preference and predisposition, so, therefore, initially, they did not wish to accept the technological changes. Initially, negative perceptions were also observed amongst female participants on changes regarding outside valley transfers. Due to the cultural factors and barriers, female employees resisted being transferred outside the city and preferred working in their existing departments. However, this attitude changed once they were offered higher salaries for relocation. Graham (1986) explained that the participants in this research believe that employees' actions to resist changes are simply motivated by selfishness until their personal goals are achieved.

Furthermore, Dent & Goldberg (1999) argued that examining employees' perceptions and experience of change may reveal that employees are not necessarily resisting the change itself, but rather perceived undesirable outcomes of change or the process of implementing the change. This compels the researcher to understand the perceptions of uncertainty amongst junior employees. The findings emphasise the uncertainty that spread amongst employees before some of the desired changes were carried out. The employees were not sure how the new policies would affect/benefit them and the organisation, and in turn, they challenged those. This type of resistance is prevalent and has been observed before by some senior participants

carrying out changes. The ambiguity amongst the employees matured into stress, anxiety, fear, and demotivation. This viewpoint is verified from the literature where it states, even though change is implemented for positive reasons (e.g., to adapt to changing environmental conditions and remain competitive), employees often respond negatively toward change and resist change efforts. This adverse reaction is large because change brings increased pressure, stress, and uncertainty for employees (Armenakis & Bedeian, 1999; McHugh, 1997). Additionally, the uncertainty that leads to stress and anxiety is related to the emotional component of resistance to change. The survey findings are consistent with the interview findings on this factor, with more than 68% of participants responding to stress when things do not go according to plan.

The findings indicate that convincing employee to change was very difficult because they were not comfortable changing their current environments. This leads the researcher in examining employee's reluctance to give up old habits and control. As mentioned in the literature by Tichy (1983), employees resist changes when they require changing their habits. The findings highlight this type of resistance. It was observed that changing the working hours from 9:45 am to 9:30 am was vital as employees were frequently negligent in coming to the Bank at their expected times, this also created chaos amongst other employees. Due to this, a biometrics system was introduced that digitally monitored attendances and fined employees for being late. As a result, there were feelings of resentments and resistance within employees.

Additionally, the findings highlight that older employees resisted the digitalization of tasks and meetings because they felt the loss of control over conducting their tasks manually and discussions in person. As verified in the literature by Oreg (2003), individuals resist changes because they feel control of the situation is taken away from them with imposed changes rather than it being self-initiated. Technological resistance being discussed in this factor can be linked with Kanter's (1985) research that sometimes employees do not have confidence in themselves,

whether they are confident that changes will positively affect them and the organisation. On the contrary, one participant exclaimed that some of the organisation's employees would resist and not change their habits unless desired changes are imposed on them by the senior management. Thus, when all else fails, management sent out circulars that are mandatory for employees to follow.

Although there is some negativity emerging from the findings of employees accepting and resisting the change, it has to be realised that this section exhibits the findings that are a depiction of the current situation of the Bank and the factors that prompt employees to resist specific changes. The findings suggest that the Bank, like any other organisation, encounters resistance. Hence the senior management must regulate any resistance because employees do react to organisational changes negatively and can also possess characteristics to negatively influence other individuals and groups during the change process (Kotter, & Schlesinger, 2008).

7.5 The Organisational Strategies Implemented to Achieve Desired Change

The finding highlighted some of the participants' views on the prominent strategies implemented by HBL, which will be discussed in this section. The first strategy majority of the participant applauded the management is training. Findings uncovered that recently the Bank had developed its training and development resource centre, accessible for all the employees. The resource centres provide training using a digital portal that allows more than 1000 employees to participate in the sessions. The findings have also uncovered that these sessions help communicate and teach the need for new changes and further enhance employees' competencies to help them transition effectively and efficiently with the change. As the literature mentioned, Dean and Linda (2010) claim that adequate training is an on-going process that brings impressive results in accepting the change by employees and helps them comprehend what the organisations expects them to do.

Furthermore, their works also argue that training can motivate employees because it helps them understand their work and envision the future (Dean and Linda, 2010). It was important for the Bank to develop its own training and learning centre because of its far-reaching branches and wide-ranging employees. The Bank provides its employees with continuous training sessions to help them grasp technicalities associated with changes, as verified by Bennet et al. (1999), who specifically views training functions in any organisation as the central part of the enterprises' continuous improvement efforts. Adding to this, Bolognese (2008) states that training can help employees improve their performance, behaviour, attitudes, and skills needed for change to occur.

To understand the Bank's culture, every new employee has to take mandatory training sessions once recruited. This helps them in familiarising themselves with the Bank's working ethics, culture, and environment. The findings revealed that previously the employees were not provided with induction training, and because of that, they found it challenging to understand the organisational shared beliefs and values. Those led to confusion and anxiousness amongst the new employees when Bank implemented or reformed policies. Linking it to the view of Greenberg and Cropanzano (2001), who argued that training is a crucial tool to avoid difficulties and resistance. It helps organisations reduce the gap between the present situation, values, beliefs, and new capabilities required to implement the change processes successfully. One of the significant changes the Bank has experience is technological advancements. The findings provide sufficient evidence that the management encourages and offers training to employees to help them accept and grasp the technical changes. Initially, employees were forcefully hesitant to technological changes. The senior/old-age employees were not comfortable switching from manual tasks to digital and online banking systems. Due to this, there was fear, anger, and uncertainty witnessed between them. To execute technical changes

smoothly, the Bank provided those employees with personal one-to-one training sessions and a 24/7 helpline that helped them understand the hi-tech changes.

Furthermore, technical training also helped younger employees develop skills and sharpen their abilities to improve the Bank's overall efficiency. As articulated in the literature by Butterfield (2010), new technology and procedures should be learned to improve productivity and quality in the workplace. Managers need to build a healthy environment by implementing innovative training sessions. These training sessions will provide a kind of motivation for their employees to improve their performance and achieve the organisational goals effectively. Briefly, the participants touched on the aspect of training provided to employees to restore their motivational levels. Nepal's fluctuating banking industry counters various changes, all of which are successfully executed by employees. Hence, in line with Rebecca and Rolf's (2009) views, the Bank provides motivation and sessions to employees where thorough guidance, assistance, and discussions help improve employee's performance and support them in adapting to changes. This is further backed by literature with the research of Yusoff, Kian, and Idris (2013) that in the initial stages of introduction to new technology, management must guide, motivate and train employees and inform them why the change is needed and what their duties are regarding the change process.

The second most suggested strategy implemented by the management is to reinforce employees' involvement/engagement and involve them in discussions. However, this is also the most provocative and debatable factor with contrasted responses amongst senior and junior participants. Many senior participants and some junior respondents applauded the Bank's policies for encouraging employee involvement instead of some junior participants who responded otherwise. The findings emphasise that the Bank encourages its various departmental leaders to frequently conduct discussions and meetings when new change policies are generated. Furthermore, the findings exhibit that any desired changes are communicated to

the employee's primary to their execution. Likewise, employees are involved in strategic planning and executing changes. Employee engagement empowered the workforce with a positive way of thinking and acting at work that, in the long run, helped the Bank in controlling resistance and refurbishing employee satisfaction levels. As stated in the literature by Näswall *et al.* (2008), when employees are involved in decision making, they develop a robust job-related attitude and identification with work, enhanced mental health, performance, and motivation.

Furthermore, due to decision-making involvement, employees (in general) feel more connected to the organisation (Näswall *et al.*, 2008). The findings also revealed that junior employees are involved in the discussion making and are also allowed to participate in change development processes. When the new system was being introduced in one of the departments, employees were in direct contact with the vendor to express the requirements and modifications needed for the system. This minimized uncertainty as the employees were aware of the system beforehand due to intensive training and strengthened their job security level. In line with Rick and Jeanenne (2011) views, one of the key strategies to ensure change is implemented successfully and without resistance is employee's involvement. Employees will feel they are an essential part of the organisation and the change process and will strive to perform their best to execute the desired change policies.

Lastly, the other key strategy emphasised was the improvement in employee salaries and benefits. Some of the interview participants revealed that after thorough consideration, it was put to a place that the farthest employee is willing to transfer, the higher their salary be. This was strategically carried out because female employees, in particular, were hesitant to move outside the valley (the central city) for transfers. This strategy was put into practice to motivate employees to relocate to rural area branches to manage their operations. This is following the literature by Dennis, Schraeder, and Mike (2009). It argues that each employee is motivated by

different things, and a rewarding strategy is the best motivation of all. Most employees are motivated by monetary reward; therefore, it is crucial to minimize resistance and enhance employee performance. Once this strategy was implemented, employees became excited and were willing to be transferred to other branches. Findings also disclose that employees are now frequently recognised for their performance and are given promotions based on outstanding performances. This keeps the employees motivated, especially the younger employees, and they are always striving to perform their best and be recognised by their senior management. This strategy is parallel to Stavrakakis (2008) view that claims, compensation, and recognition in the form of money or something of equal value brings satisfaction to employees and boosts their morale. Similarly, Rewards are extrinsic motivators that management can give to support and overcome the negative feelings and attitudes towards organisational change.

This section discussed a few of the strategies implemented by the Bank to help regulate resistance. There is a limitation to this area as the findings do highlight other strategies but rather vaguely. Thus, the researcher selected the ones that had the most strongest correlation to detail by most participants. On the other hand, even though these strategies sound prolific and positive for the Bank, it must be noted that any change strategies implemented take years to be successful. What is important is to control the levels of resistance organisation faces by the employees. In line with Jick's (1993) view, it has to be considered that resistance to change is reoccurring and should be treated as a regular part of adapting to change. The employees' observations, abilities, and skills compel them to take risks. In return, the management should facilitate the smooth execution of change policies but developing strategies to minimise the employee's defiance.

The next chapter will summarise the research by offering concluding remarks, recommendations, and contributions to this study.

7.6 Conclusion

The themes highlight the key findings from both survey and interview data and demonstrate a robust connection to the structure and culture and other key concepts and theories associated with organisational change within HBL and employees reacting to those changes positively and negatively constituting resistance. The findings revealed that the various changes had been carried out in the Bank in recent years. Some key ones are technological, structural, digitalization, training, development, and HRM. For employees to successfully understand the changes, the majority of the desired transformations were slow and planned in nature. As mentioned by Senior and Swailes (2010), planned change assists the organisation in moving from one state of organisational productivity to another. The findings from participants' perception reveal that changes are necessary for the Bank to increase productivity and maintain competitiveness. Participants further elaborated that the majority of the employees embraced the changes positively because they were communicated to them well, and their managers/leaders involved them in the change process. Employees were allowed to discuss and give their feedback on change practices that efficiently helped them adapt to the changes. On the other hand, some participants also expressed that technological changes lead to increased workload and stress, which was one of the key contributors to resistance. As per the findings, resistance is monitored in the Bank, which is then overcome using training, counseling, participation, and other benefits like rewards and pay.

When looking at change management within HBL, there is a generally favorable prognosis for the future; the managers/change agents should start involving their employees in the change process and communicate with them directly rather than circulars. The employees would then be more accepting of changes.

The next chapter will sum up the research by offering some concluding remarks and consider both the implications and contribution of the study.

Chapter 8 – Conclusion

8.1 Introduction

The main purpose of this chapter is to review the thesis and revisit the objectives of the research and demonstrate the extent to which the objectives have been met. This chapter will also discuss the implications of the research findings, offer possible recommendations, acknowledge the research limitations, and consider contributing to this work's knowledge. Furthermore, suggestions for future research are also provided.

8.2 Review of the Aim, Objectives, and Research Questions of the Study

The overriding aim of this research was to examine and investigate the nature of the organisational change and the factors causing resistance to change in Himalayan Bank Limited through the perception of employees working in the Bank in Nepal and eliciting the views of key junior and senior participants. To help achieve this aim, the thesis had four objectives:

- Objective one - To identify the nature of organisational change that has occurred at the Bank;
- Objective two - To gauge the perceptions of change amongst employees;
- Objective three - To identify factors contributing to resistance to change amongst employees; and
- Objective four - To establish organisational strategies implemented to achieve desired change.

This thesis has addressed each objective by establishing upon the descriptive approach and deploying mixed method, keeping in mind the emerging themes from data collected from both the data set and confirming that each objective has been met and underlined. Therefore, the researcher is confident that the overriding aim and objectives of this study have been achieved.

8.2.1 Review of Objective One

The first objective of this research has been met. In this study, it has been determined by employees' perceptions that the Bank carries out changes every three to five years. Some of these changes are the upgrading of technology (CBS systems), changes in structure, changes in transfer policies and pay, the inauguration of a learning and development resource centre, and the formation of a staff's union. In particular, technological changes are pivotal for the bank, and the findings underlined that the bank deploys and upgrades technology every year to ensure the effectiveness of the Bank's productivity. The majority of the changes are planned in nature and implemented gradually. In contrast, changes inflicted by Nepal Rastra Bank are radical and obligatory in nature that are often executed with force. The findings corroborate the literature on the change schemes conducted in the banking industry in Nepal.

8.2.2 Review of Objective Two

The second objective of this research has been met. The findings from this research reveal that most employees do not consider changes to be negative in their organisational setting. In fact, they applauded the change initiatives considered by the senior management because they helped improve the Bank's overall efficiency. The junior participants' findings signified that technological advancements and digitalisation of tasks have been very beneficial for employees. The tasks are now completed promptly and proficiently. Due to an increase in competence, employees are appreciated by their management and motivated to strive better. On the other hand, senior employees emphasised encouraging employee involvement before and during the change initiatives. In contrast, junior employees stressed on lack of involvement due to autocratic, top-down management and weak communication strategies amongst various departments. The findings are in line with the literature on varied perceptions amongst supervisory and non-supervisory employees in organisations. The participants in this research do not dismiss the idea of changes within their department and/or the overall bank. Still, they

advise being the new policies and procedures to be communicated before they are implemented.

8.2.3 Review of Objective Three

The third objective of this research has been met. The findings from this study disclose that most of the bank's changes have faced some form of resistance. Most of the participants believe that resistance occurs when the bank is changing certain structures and policies. Employees resist changes that are not communicated to them properly, and the reason to implement the desired change is not clear. The findings further revealed that the bank's senior employees tend to resist technological changes as opposed to the junior and middle age employees. The findings are also in line with the literature. They uncovered that most Bank employees resist changes initially due to the fear of uncertainty, added stress, and workload that is anticipated with the desired changes. The perception of junior employees indicated a powerful desire amongst young employees to perform their best and achieve career progressions by developing change strategies and decision making. However, due to the strict hierarchal system in the Bank, tasks are delegated to the employees instead of being conversed. Hence, the frustration amongst junior employees resists imposed changes.

On the other hand, a small number of participants indicated that employees' resistance is not as bad as it may look. With the help of training and monitoring, most employees learn to adapt to such changes.

8.2.4 Review of Objective Four

The fourth objective of this research has been met. The findings revealed several strategies that were highlighted by both senior and junior participants. The Bank has invested in developing its own training and development resource centre that provides digital and in-house training sessions to all the employees. These sessions help employees to adapt to the changes and also helps them enhance their working competencies. Upgrading CBS systems such as Vigo and

T24 have helped the Bank save costs and time and augmented overall productivity. The findings revealed that the Human Resource department frequently conducts meetings and discussion sessions with employees and encourages them to engage in that session even if they are not a part of the same department. This allows employees to feel a part of this organisation and further boosts their morale and job satisfaction levels. The findings are in line with the empirical studies reported in the literature. Hence, employees in departments such as credit, information technology, and human resources appreciate and applaud their managers/leaders for instigating such strategies. Improving the financial rewards such as pay, and bonus helped the Bank minimise resistance and persuade employees to relocate to branches outside the valley that needed to improve their efficiency. Equal pay and transfer opportunities amongst male and female employees are considered one of the most encouraging changes within Himalayan Bank.

In addressing the research aims, the study exhibited that communication and involvement are the employees' key factors when the senior management is undergoing new changes. These factors also determine a major percentage of resistance the Bank faces. However, the findings suggest that Nepal's working culture and employees' dogmatic behaviour compel the management to be autocratic in their leadership and sometimes impose changes that will benefit the employees in the future that they might not just realise.

Therefore, comparing the varied responses from senior and junior participants helped the researcher gain a richer understanding of participants' views at various organisational levels.

8.3 Implications and Recommendations

The research on this study reveals that senior employees' perceptions in comparison with junior employees do not vary considerably across the various departments and hierarchal levels and that there is a need to modify certain strategies when changes are being carried out. This implies that all the employees must understand the current reforms and strategies

of change, and they must be inspired to address their viewpoints on the new changes before they are implemented. This fits in well with the future research as the current environment of the Bank appears to be accepting change, especially the junior and young age employees who will represent the future of the Bank and the Banking industry of Nepal.

The findings have raised the big disparity between the old age and the middle/young age employees at the senior positions of the Bank. Most of the senior executives are 50 years and plus, and very few junior employees are given promotion opportunities to climb up the hierarchical ladder. Junior employees constitute 60 percent of the workforce, and thus, the management needs to promote young and efficient employees to more leadership and decision-making roles and take advantage of the skill set they have to offer. As the junior employees highlight most of the changes needed in the Bank and within their departments, this would give the younger workforce positions of encouragement where they will have the capacity to influence their experiences at work positively and the other young employees. To make this happen, the organisation would have to initiate a more bottoms-up approach and apply democratic leadership strategies. This will be a challenge, no doubt, because the organisational culture is pre-set and influenced by the national culture of autocracy, but the rewards will be greater and more satisfactory to the employees and the organisational efficiency.

Given that the findings inform that the poor communication strategies and channels lead to the majority of the changes being conversed to employees via circulars and emails. That is not favoured by most of the junior employees as it lacks explanation as to why the changes are necessary and what is expected of them. It was revealed that although employees show confidence in the Bank as it executes changes to improve efficiency, they also feel that the senior management are neither caring nor considerate; therefore, some of them are unwilling to commit to the Bank in the long run. Employees tend to evaluate an organisation with poor

communication approaches as slightly less reliable than an organisation that encourages open communication. The concept of employee involvement is based on the foundation of effective communication. Therefore, the management should develop communication strategies whereby all the employees are informed of the reasons to carry out the changes, why the desired changes are important for employees and the organisation, and the skill set required from the employees to execute those changes proficiently. Hence, just like the HR and IT departments, other departmental leaders and managers should also broaden their base of competence by utilising their employees' skills and believing that their employees can contribute great ideas and solutions when involved in the two-way communication strategies within their department.

The findings revealed poor marketing strategies of HBL and the desperate need to change marketing approaches to attract customers and maintain their market share. To date, the goodwill of the Bank is considered a key tool for attracting customers. The senior management and the directors should understand the value of having efficient marketing and digital marketing strategies to sustain the global competition. Hence, time and money should also be spent improving the marketing department's performance and capabilities, marketing policies, and procedures to help the Bank sustain global competition.

8.4 Contribution of The Thesis

This section will be stating the contributions that can be attributed to this thesis. As per Phillips et al. (2010), a contribution is a small or a big piece of work contributing to the research field. Furthermore, it must be original and based on the findings, and the researcher should ensure the contribution he or she makes is of value. To an extent, this study's contribution can already be derived from the fact that the findings that emerged have implications for change practices being administered and their effects on the perceptions of the senior executives and junior employees. Any thesis that has implications must be

concluded by contributing and hence the following section will present the practical contribution of this work.

The aim of this study was to investigate organisational change in HBL and its employee's viewpoints regarding the new practices. Due to the uniqueness of the phenomenon being investigated in this particular Bank, several contributions emerged from this research.

This is the first study that uses a mixed methods approach to gauge the nature and perceptions of employees on change and resistance to change in Himalayan Bank. The relatively few studies that are covering related areas on Nepalese commercial Banks such as those by Biswakarma, (2016), Sapkota *et al.*, (2018), K.C. and Neupane, (2020), Upadhaya, Munir and Blount, (2014) that either use a qualitative or a quantitative approach. Additionally, the quantitative element allowed the researcher to obtain a relatively larger sample from employees in various departments and branches of the Bank. The researcher was fortunate to exploit her contacts in the Bank that helped her in conducting the questionnaire as well as in-depth interviews from the key participants. Hence, this research plugs the gap in the literature till date has mainly reported studies pertaining to this topic that are either qualitative or quantitative. Secondly, this study is unique because it targets the current pool of human resources that Himalayan Bank will rely on for its growth opportunities and to maintain its market share. Therefore, it is the first study to gauge the viewpoints of those currently employed in the Nepalese banking industry. The views of junior participants are essential for this study as it allows a projection to be made about what the future might hold in terms of the Bank's development and production and differentiates this study from the other studies that are carried on the Nepalese being industry but not particularly at Himalayan Bank. Given the varied demographic bands such as age and positions, this sample is more relevant in evaluating the different discernments by respondents on organisational change.

Thirdly, this study contributes to embarking on a research topic suitable in the current and fluctuating corporate environment of Nepal, and that can help the directors and senior management take certain preventive measures when applying changes to minimise any kinds of barriers and resistances within the Himalayan Bank. This study uncovers fresh insight into the views of the key participants who have the potential to influence and shape the Bank's progression and prosperity in the future. The views from junior employees are particularly appropriate at this juncture, given that the banking industry is constantly changing and there is a need to transform the corporate governance that would guarantee a prosperous future for the Bank and investigate improving the corporate ethos for the overall employees. This could potentially challenge the traditional organisational practices and the dictatorial culture, so the Bank accommodates change strategies and values that will be focusing on employee equality, progression, and development.

8.5 Limitations

It is important to highlight that this study is about the key participant's perceptions on the factors associated with organisational change and resistance to change within Himalayan Bank Limited. Some of these participants have not directly been involved in change strategies, and therefore their responses are not based on actual experiences in the Bank but rather assumptions from what they have observed around them. Whilst there have been some qualitative (small-scale) studies of organisational change in the Nepalese Banking industry (Gautam, Shivakoti and Webb, 2004; Lama, 2018; Pradhan, 2020), there is still a gap existing in empirical literature on Himalayan Bank in Nepal. Thus, a large-scale survey of the Bank's employees would have provided additional insights on this phenomenon being researched and would have been substantially ideal for comparing employees' holistic perceptions from various departments and geographic locations. Nevertheless, this was not possible due to the time constraints, access,

and participation given the sensitive nature of the topic, some employees working in the rural branches are less approachable and receptive than the employees working in city branches.

One of the limitations the researcher faced was in terms of methodology – sample size. The researcher initially expected more responses from the participants, but the responses halted at a certain number due to the time-gap and time constraints. In the end, due to the inaccessibility of attaining large-scale data, the in-depth interviews were conducted with employees via Microsoft Teams. Likewise, it is admitted that the survey has its limitations. Even though a pilot study was conducted to test the validity of the questionnaire, as pointed out by Saunders et al. (2009), One cannot be certain that questions have been answered truthfully or indeed that all respondents have understood every question.

The other limitation that must be documented is that perceptions and judgments that emerged from this research are solely based on Himalayan Bank's employees. From these employees, the participant panel consisted of senior executives and junior employees. Therefore, the findings are restricted to this particular Bank, and there is no guarantee that these viewpoints represent the general employees working in other co-operations and banks in Nepal.

8.6 Future Research

This research does not represent the end of the story. Instead, it represents an important starting point which other researchers can use as a base to undertake further work. In particular, possible future research could be one that compares the perceptions attained in this research of a unique sample representing the current workforce of Himalayan Bank with other employees in other departments, branches, and maybe the competing Banks of Himalayan Bank.

Extracting employees' responses from various departments within the Nepalese Banking industry can also be a significant indicator of how other employees from other Banks in the country view the current reforms on organisational changes and if they express the same

insights as shared by the current participants. Furthermore, it is a key factor as it may determine the likelihood or otherwise of successful changes in their organisations.

This research has surely laid the foundations for further research on a topic that is attracted globally and understating the emerging factors of how employees across other branches and departments face similar circumstances in the context of Banks in Nepal.

8.7 Conclusion – Final Remarks

Undertaking a research topic as attention grabbing as organisational change and resistance to change in a developing authoritarian and culturally intact society like Nepal was an interesting endeavour. As someone interested in organisational behaviour and human resources and subjectively belonging from a developing country – Pakistan, which is also controlled and characterized by a relatively stricter authoritarian working culture, the researcher was keen and excited to understand the facets around the phenomenon of organisational change and resistance.

This research has been significant when the organisation being investigated was undergoing numerous technological and structural transformations. The raw and organic employees' perceptions highlighted several positive and negative elements and allowed the researcher to congregate interpretations from an integrated perspective. Nevertheless, the key findings underline that employees acknowledge the need for change within Himalayan Bank positively, whilst also accepting the fact that assorted levels of resistance will accompany any form of major or minor changes.

This study is deep-rooted in investigating the nature and types of organisational changes carried out in Himalayan Bank in Nepal through current employees' perception at various hierarchal levels and departments. The participants illustrated a mixed interplay between the necessity and effectiveness of executing change, the influences of resistance to those changes, and the strategies implemented to execute the new change practices smoothly. The research determines

that communication is the key factor affecting change strategies, structures, and procedures either negatively or positively. Thus, having effective communication (that further produces opportunities for employee involvement and engagement) has a multiplier effect of positivity, satisfaction, and acceptance on employees regarding the new changes. Regardless of some participants stressing on being the flag bearers of communication, employee involvement, and engagement in change strategies; the truth of the matter is this is not the case. They either personally nurse those practices in their department or communicate those to their colleagues and other managers, but these are surely not realised by the other executives. Hence, resistance transpires.

Nepal's financial sector is emerging with the inaugurations of swift technological and digital reforms. The measures of success of the new policies and reforms that have been implemented will depend momentously on the workforce also evolving and moving with the change. Nevertheless, it must be considered that the success of organisational changes at any level is predominantly based on the workforce and the effectiveness of the change agent carrying out desired changes. A shift to egalitarian culture will definitely be required for the full potential of the workforce to be utilised. Therefore, as mentioned above, a strong commitment from those in the position of authority and leadership will increase the likelihood of the new changes' success.

Even though this research's findings are based on the perceptions of key participants, we should not ignore the fact that they correspond with limited previous research and studies conducted into this area, as reported in the earlier chapters. Thus, these findings can reasonably be composed as an indicator of the current situation of organisational changes being carried out in the Nepalese banking industry, narrowing it down to Himalayan Bank. Harmony and mutuality between the change agent, organisational leaders, and the general workforce are necessary to facilitate the desired changes.

On the other hand, will the employees accept to invest in changes regardless of their advantages and disadvantages in the long run? Will the leaders gain trust to promote employees into senior positions of leading the required changes? Will the Bank be able to make necessary adjustments and shift from its traditional working cultures and practices? Moreover, can uncertainty associated with organisational changes be avoided regardless of the available training and development consultations in a revolutionary - fast-paced organisation? All of these are interesting questions that perhaps future research can address.

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Appendix 1

Questionnaire for HBL employees

Demographic Questions:

1. Gender
 - Male
 - Female

2. Age
 - 18 – 24
 - 25 – 34
 - 35 – 44
 - 45 – 54
 - 55 – 64

3. Ethnicity
 - White – British / Scottish / Irish
 - Asian – Indian / Pakistani / Bangladeshi / Nepalese / Chinese

4. Education Qualification
 - High School Graduate
 - Graduate
 - Post-Graduate
 - Professional Qualifications
 - Others

5. Length of Service
 - 0 to 1 Year
 - 2 to 5 Years
 - 6 to 10 Years
 - 10+ Years

6. Current Position

- Junior Level
- Middle Management
- Upper Management
- Senior Executive

Resistance to Change Scale (RTC)

Statement	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Inclined to disagree	Inclined to agree	Agree	Strongly agree
1. I generally consider changes to be a negative thing.	1	2	3	4	5	6
2. I'll take a routine day over a day full of unexpected events any time.	1	2	3	4	5	6
3. I like to do the same old things rather than try new and different ones.	1	2	3	4	5	6
4. Whenever my life forms a stable routine, I look for ways to change it.	1	2	3	4	5	6
5. I'd rather be bored than surprised.	1	2	3	4	5	6
6. If I were to be informed that there's going to be a significant change regarding the way things are done at work, I would probably feel stressed.	1	2	3	4	5	6
7. When I am informed of a change of plans, I tense up a bit.	1	2	3	4	5	6

Statement	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Inclined to disagree	Inclined to agree	Agree	Strongly agree
8. When things don't go according to plans, it stresses me out.	1	2	3	4	5	6
9. If my Boss changed the performance evaluation criteria, it would probably make me feel uncomfortable even if I thought I'd do just as well without having to do extra work.	1	2	3	4	5	6
10. Changing plans seems like a real hassle to me.	1	2	3	4	5	6
11. Often, I feel a bit uncomfortable even about changes that may potentially improve my life.	1	2	3	4	5	6
12. When someone pressures me to change something, I tend to resist it even if I think the change may ultimately benefit me.	1	2	3	4	5	6
13. I sometimes find myself avoiding changes that I know will be good for me.	1	2	3	4	5	6
14. I often change my mind.	1	2	3	4	5	6
15. I don't change my mind easily.	1	2	3	4	5	6
16. Once I've come to a conclusion, I'm not likely to change my mind.	1	2	3	4	5	6

Statement	Strongly disagree	Disagree	Inclined to disagree	Inclined to agree	Agree	Strongly agree
17. My views are very consistent over time.	1	2	3	4	5	6

- 1 Routine seeking: Items 1-5
- 2 Emotional reaction: Items 6-9
- 3 Short-term focus: Items 10-13
- 4 Cognitive rigidity: Items 14-17

Appendix 2

In-depth Interview Questions with Junior Employees

Q. Can you please introduce yourself, your age, educational qualification and ethnic background

Q. can you please tell me your current position (in this bank) and your job role in detail

1. What does the term organisational change mean to you?
2. During your time as a bank employee, have you ever experienced organisational change? If yes, how would you describe your experience? If yes, please continue and provide details of the nature of the change.
3. Did your employer/manager involve/consult you in the change process? If yes, please provide details.
4. What impact, if any; did the change have on your working life and work environment?
5. Do you think the change undertaken was necessary? Please explain your answer.
6. From your experience, do you think the organisation carried out change in the most effective way? Please explain your answer.

Appendix 3

In-depth Interview Questions with Senior Executives

Q. Can you please introduce yourself, your age, educational qualification and ethnic background

1. What is your role within the organisation?
2. How would you define organisational change?
3. Has your organisation ever undertaken change? If no, then thank you for your time. If yes, please continue.
4. Were you involved in the change process? If yes, please continue and describe the nature of your involvement.
5. What was the rationale for the change?
6. What impact did the change have on you and your experience at work?
7. Do you feel the change has been of any value to the organisation?
8. Were the employees briefed on the changes? If yes, how?
9. How did the employees react to the change? Did the organisation encounter any resistance?
10. If your organisation undertook change again, would you advise them to do anything different?